

Replication of Genomes in Eukaryotes: Analyses of the Structure and Functions of the Replicative ϵ Polymerases from Yeasts, Plants and Animals

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Abstract

In all living organisms, genome replication is an indispensable activity in their life cycle. As compared to prokaryotes, genome replication in eukaryotes is much more complex. In eukaryotes, the genome replication is accomplished by a more specialized, multi-protein complex known as replisome. Therefore, for a complete understanding of the replication process in eukaryotes, the structure-function relationship of their replisome complex is important. The eukaryotic replisome complex is mainly composed of 3 replicative polymerases (pols), viz. α , ϵ and δ . The initiation of genome replication starts with the synthesis of primers by the α pol (a primase), which is followed by the synthesis of leading- and lagging-strands by the next two replicative pils, viz. ϵ and δ , respectively. Among them, the pol ϵ is an essential enzyme that links the DNA replication machinery to S-phase checkpoint-control in eukaryotes. The active sites of pol and proofreading (PR) domains of α and δ were analyzed from yeasts, animal and plant sources and reported by this author already [1, 2]. The third replicative enzyme, viz. the pol ϵ is analyzed and reported here. Interestingly, the yeast, animal and plant ϵ pils possess almost identical pol, PR and carboxyl terminal domains (CTD) with the same active site amino acids. Their catalytic cores use the same template-binding pair (-YG-), the catalytic amino acid (K), the nucleotide selection amino acid (Q) and similar catalytic metal-binding motifs in the pol domain as reported for the other replicative pils. However, they exhibit poor identities among themselves, e.g., the human pol ϵ showed only 46.69% and 43.19% identities to the plant (*Arabidopsis thaliana*) and yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) pol ϵ sequences, respectively. Furthermore, these eukaryotic ϵ pils use the same active site amino acids in the PR exonuclease domain, and belong to the DEDD(Y)-superfamily of PR exonucleases. Moreover, similar to the other two replicative enzymes, the ϵ pils also use similar regulatory Zn²⁺-binding motifs (ZBMs) in their CTD. In addition, it harbours a unique ZBM in their pol domain. Interestingly, the two invariant motifs, viz -SLYPS- and -YGDTD- which are the characteristic motifs found in the other replicative α and δ pils and B-family of DNA pils, are not found in ϵ pils. Many specialized, conserved sequence motifs are also identified in the ϵ pils and discussed.

Keywords: Eukaryotic genome replication; DNA polymerase δ ; DNA polymerase ϵ ; DNA polymerase ϵ active sites; Proofreading exonuclease active sites; *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*; *Arabidopsis thaliana*; *Homo sapiens*

1. Introduction

In all living organisms, DNA pils play a central role in DNA replication to ensure faithful transmission of genetic information from one generation to another. Therefore, to accomplish this important task in their lifecycle, organisms have evolved and possess a high-fidelity genome replication machinery to preserve and maintain the blueprint of life. The replication machinery possesses several types of DNA pils and repair mechanisms to ensure the duplication of an exact copy of the original genome. To date, five different DNA pils have been characterized in *Escherichia coli*, eight in *S. cerevisiae*, and as many as 16 in humans [3]. However, only three of these DNA pils, viz. α , ϵ and δ are involved in the duplication of the nuclear genome in all eukaryotes [4]. Even though more than a dozen different DNA pils have also

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been reported to perform various replicative and repair functions in plant cells, yet the detailed properties of them are still very limited. Whereas the α pol (the primase) is involved in the synthesis of the DNA primers to initiate the DNA duplication process, the other two replicative pols, viz. δ and ϵ , use these DNA primers and replicate the whole genome and make an exact copy of the original genome. All three replicative pols belong to B-family pols which are not only involved in replication, but also in repair any error that may occur during the replication process [5]. The B-family DNA pols are reported to function in both prokaryotes and eukaryotes, e.g., pol II, pol B, pol α , pol ϵ , pol δ , pol ζ . They are bifunctional enzymes, i.e., in addition to polymerization, they also exhibit 3'→5' PR exonuclease (PR exo) repair function [6]. Even though the replicative pols have an efficient PR function, mutation(s) that rarely escape the replication and repair processes generate the most important new genetic variants in plants and animals. The structural and functional aspects of the replicative pols, viz. α and δ , from yeasts, higher fungi and animals have been extensively analyzed and reported by this author [1, 2]. In this article, the third replicative pol ϵ from yeasts, higher fungi, plants and animals is analyzed and reported.

The DNA replication process is highly conserved in all domains of life [7]. Though genome replication in eukaryotes is known to be incredibly more complex, but it is successfully accomplished by a highly sophisticated and coordinated series of molecular events. The replication process, apart from the essential roles played by the three replicative pols, also depends on the participation of other enzymes and regulatory proteins like, primases, cell-cycle kinases, replicative helicases, single-strand binding proteins (SSBs), additional repair enzymes, ligases, etc. Given the importance of accurate DNA replication, proper functioning of all these enzymes and the accessory proteins is critical to maintain the genome integrity.

The first step in genome replication in both prokaryotes and eukaryotes is the initiation. This is accomplished by a multi-structural enzyme and protein complex known as a primosome. The primosome essentially consists of an origin-of-replication initiator protein, a replicative helicase, a helicase loader, SSBs, a primase, a topoisomerase, etc. [8]. After successful initiation of replication, the replication process is taken over by a next multi-protein complex known as the replisome, which extends the replication process and completes it. In both prokaryotes and eukaryotes, the initiation step is performed by the enzyme, RNA primase, which synthesizes the required RNA primer (short segment of SS-RNA typically of 10-20 nucleotides) to initiate the replication process. However, for eukaryotic replications, in addition to the RNA primer, an additional primer, viz. a DNA primer is also required for further extension, which is provided by the enzyme, DNA pol α . The DNA pol α extends the RNA primers by synthesizing short stretches of DNA, which is used by the pol ϵ and pol δ for further extension of the DNA synthesis in a processive manner and complete the replication process. During replication, the leading-strand is synthesized by pol ϵ (pol2), and the lagging-strand is synthesized by pol δ (pol3). During replication the leading-strand is synthesized continuously, whereas the lagging-strand is synthesized discontinuously, in fragments of ~200 nucleotides long, known as the Okazaki fragments (OFs), named after the discoverer. All these OFs are connected together in the next step to form a complete complementary strand by a DNA ligase [9].

1.1. Eukaryotic ϵ DNA Polymerases

From the above discussions, it is clear that the bulk of the DNA synthesis in eukaryotes is performed by only two of the three replicative polymerases, viz. pols ϵ and δ . DNA pol ϵ (also known as Pol2 in yeasts and plants and PolE in humans) completes the leading- and lagging-strand syntheses, respectively. Pol ϵ was first isolated and characterized from yeast cells as early as 1970 as a nuclear polymerase [10]. It was initially considered to be a form of pol δ that was processive in the absence of proliferating cell nuclear antigen (PCNA) and replication factor C (RFC) [11] (The function of RFC is to load PCNA, the processivity factor of the eukaryotic DNA polymerases δ and ϵ , onto primed DNA templates). Later, it was found that pol ϵ is an independent replicative enzyme in all eukaryotes. Nowadays, its catalytic subunit is isolated and characterized and its gene is cloned and sequenced from several eukaryotes [11 and references therein]. This enzyme, along with the other two eukaryotic replicative (pols α and δ), are grouped under the B-family polymerases [12]. A great deal of information is available now on the structure and functions of the DNA pols ϵ from a large number of eukaryotes like yeasts, higher fungi, plants and animals. The plant enzyme from *A. thaliana* has been characterized in sufficient detail and used for further analysis and comparison.

1.1.1. Subunit structure

Interestingly, all the pol ϵ enzymes from eukaryotes are composed of 4 subunits exhibiting similar subunit structures. Figures 1A, B and C show the subunit structures of the ϵ pols from yeasts, plants and animals. For example, the yeast enzyme's 4 subunits are named as, Pol2, Dpb2, Dpb3 and Dpb4 (with the molecular masses of 256, 79, 23 and 22 kDa, respectively) and the plant enzyme also follows more or less the same nomenclature as the yeast enzyme as, Pol2A, Dpb2, Dpb3 and Dpb4 (with the molecular masses of 249, 60, 23 and 24 kDa, respectively), but the human enzyme subunits are named as, PolE1-PolE4 (with the molecular masses of 262, 60, 17 and 12 kDa, respectively). The 4 subunits

are assembled with a stoichiometry of 1:1:1:1. Thus, the DNA pol ϵ is a heterotetrameric enzyme, made up of the main catalytic subunit (Pol2/Pol2A/PolE1) which assumes a biloped structure, where the NTD and CTD lobes are connected by a linker region and the non-catalytic subunit (Dpb2/PolE2). The Dpb2/PolE2 subunit mediates the homodimerization of the enzyme to its active form and therefore, is essential for the enzyme activity and cell viability. Genetic and biochemical studies indicate that the putative zinc-finger regions in the catalytic subunit (Pol2/Pol2A/PolE1) are important for its interactions with the Dpb2/PolE2 essential subunit. The other two smaller subunits (Dpb3/PolE3 and Dpb4/PolE4) are found to be nonessential for the catalytic activity of the enzyme, but are found to play important regulatory roles [11]. For example, each of the smaller subunits, viz. PolE3 and PolE4 possess H2A/H2B type histone folds and form a tight PolE3-PolE4 dimer. The dimer interacts with the larger catalytic subunit of the enzyme. (For example, PolE3 interacts with subunits PolE1 and PolE4; and the PolE4 interacts with subunits PolE1 and PolE3 and with the subunit of chromatin remodelling complex, (CHRAC), a multi-protein assembly that regulate gene expression and chromatin structure. Though the non-catalytic subunits are highly conserved from yeasts to humans, they largely differ in their sizes in humans [11 and references therein].

Among the plant ϵ pols (Pol2), the pol ϵ from *A. thaliana* has been the most studied one. The pol ϵ complex in *A. thaliana* has been shown to play diverse regulatory roles. For example, it is implicated in DNA replication, DNA repair (nucleotide and base excision repairs), DNA recombination and also in epigenetic gene-silencing activities [11]. Unlike the yeast and human enzymes, the *Arabidopsis* enzyme possesses two isoenzymes, viz. Pol2A and Pol2B. The *Pol2A* gene is ~16 kb long (49 exons) and encodes a protein of 2,161 amino acids (pI/Mw: 6.19/2,48,897), whereas the ~13 kb long *Pol2B* gene with same number of exons (49 exons) encodes a protein of 2,138 amino acids which shows 78.5% identity to Pol2A [13]. Importantly, both the isozymes contain all the motifs that are necessary for a functional Pol2 catalytic subunit. However, the expression of *Pol2B* has been detected mostly under adverse environmental conditions and loss of function of *Pol2B* has resulted in no visible phenotype, suggesting that the Pol2A forms the main enzyme [13]. Furthermore, the knockout mutants of the (Pol2A) are found to be lethal, suggesting its importance [14, 12]. The non-enzymatic CTD plays a crucial role and it not only mediates the interaction of the main catalytic subunit with the other three smaller regulatory subunits, but also links the replication machinery to the S-phase checkpoint [15, 16]. However, its overall subunit composition and various domains of its catalytic subunit's structure are mostly understood from the data available from yeast and human enzymes.

Adapted from [11, 12].

The pol ϵ subunit p17 has been identified as an integral subunit of the chromatin-remodelling factor, CHRAC (Chromatin Accessibility Complex). CHRAC is an ISWI (Imitation Switch), i.e., a chromatin remodelling nuclear-ATPase containing complex that regulates chromatin accessibility and nucleosome spacing. In CHRAC, the p17 forms a dimer with p12 subunit that can interact with histones as well as DNA [17].

Figures 1A, B and C. Subunit structures of the eukaryotic DNA pol ϵ (*S. cerevisiae*, *A. thaliana* and *Homo sapiens*) (the numbers in brackets indicate molecular masses of the subunits in kDa)

1.1.2. Domain organization of the pol ϵ catalytic subunit

The domain organization of the pol ϵ 's (pol2) catalytic subunit from the yeast, *S. cerevisiae*, has been extensively studied and characterized. It contains two pol modules, one in the N-terminal domain (NTD) and the other in the CTD. The NTD pol ϵ module possesses both the pol and PR exonuclease activities, whereas the CTD mediates the crucial interactions between the three smaller regulatory subunits with the catalytic subunit and also links the replication machinery to the S-phase checkpoint [11]. The pol ϵ exhibits the highest processivity as compared to the other two replicative pols, viz. pols α , and δ . This high processivity was found to be increased even further by the nonessential subunits, Dpb3 and Dpb4, through their interactions with the replication clamp, the PCNA. Furthermore, the genetic and biochemical studies indicate that the putative ZFMs in the main catalytic subunit of the enzyme are important for their interactions with the other subunits and for the catalytic efficiency of the enzyme [18].

The main catalytic subunit of the yeast pol ϵ holoenzyme is dissected into different functional domains as, NTD (31–281), PR exonuclease domain (282–527) and the palm (528–950), fingers (769–833), and thumb (951–1186) subdomains of the pol domain (that are organized into a toroid) [19], and a linker domain which connects the pol to the CTD. Figures 2A, 2B and 2C show the various domains and the interactions of the subunits with the CTD of the pols ϵ from different eukaryotic sources.

Figures 2A, B and C. Tentative domain organization the main catalytic subunit of the ϵ pols from eukaryotes (*S. cerevisiae*, *A. thaliana* and *Homo sapiens*) and their interacting accessory subunits

2. Materials and Methods

The protein sequence data of ϵ DNA pols from yeasts, higher fungi, plants and animals were obtained from PUBMED and SWISS-PROT databases. The advanced version of Clustal Omega was used for protein sequence analysis. Along with the conserved motifs identified by the bioinformatics analysis, and the data already available from biochemical, SDM, cryogenic-Electron Microscopy (cryo-EM) and X-ray crystallographic analyses on the ϵ pols are used to confirm the possible amino acids at the active sites of the pol, PR exonuclease domains and regulatory motifs.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. MSA analysis of DNA polymerase ϵ from various plant sources

The DNA pol ϵ was analyzed from yeasts, higher fungi, plants and animal sources. The structural and functional aspects of this enzyme from yeasts and higher fungal sources were already reported by this author [8]. Fig. 3 shows the MSA of pol ϵ from various plant sources (only the required regions for the discussions are shown). The model plant, *A. thaliana*'s sequence is used as the standard and highlighted. All the major domains (NTD, PR Exo, Pol, Linker and CTD) are indicated with arrow marks. Large numbers of highly conserved small and large peptides are found from NTD to CTD. It is interesting to note that the highly conserved active site amino acids are usually embedded within these conserved peptides (highlighted). The NTD is conserved in all, but aligned with some gaps. It harbours 3 conserved -DxD- type metal-binding motifs and 3 polybasic peptides (highlighted) and some are implicated as nuclear localization signal (NLS). The NTD is followed by the PR exonuclease and pol domains. The proposed PR exonuclease active site amino acids are highly conserved in all the enzymes (highlighted) and it belongs to the DEDD-superfamily of exonucleases and uses an invariant Y as proton acceptor during catalysis. This is in complete agreement with the other DNA-dependent DNA pols (DdDps) from prokaryotes and eukaryotes [1, 6]. An invariant motif, -SYLPQGS- (highlighted in yellow) is found within the PR exo region in the plant ϵ pols as found in yeasts, higher fungi and animals [8]. This sequence is somewhat similar to the characteristic -SLYPS- motif found in the other two eukaryotic replicative DNA pols, α and δ . In both the cases, this motif is implicated in dNTP-binding. In the former, it is found within the proposed PR exo region, whereas in the latter two pols, it is located in the pol region itself. The PR exo domain is followed by the pol domain and

is also highly conserved in all. The proposed template-binding and catalytic pairs, and metal-binding sites are highlighted in yellow and green, respectively. The template-binding pair (-YG-), catalytic amino acid (K) and the nucleotide selection amino acid (Q) are in close agreement with other DdDps and DdRps [6]. Unlike other two eukaryotic replicative pols, the pol ε domain contains a ZBM (highlighted) within. The pol domain is followed by a linker region which connects the pol domain to the CTD. Interestingly, a second putative pol active site amino acids are identified in the CTD and highlighted in yellow. The CTD contains the two typical, highly conserved ZBMs and one of them (CysB) is known to bind the 4Fe-4S cluster (highlighted in orange). It is interesting to note that these 2 ZBMs are found invariably in all three replicative pols at their CTDs. In addition to the Cs which make these ZBMs, there are invariant Cs found throughout the sequence (data not shown) which may be involved in disulphide bond formation. The CTD also contains a -DxD- type metal-binding motif within the CysA. It is interesting to note that the NTD, pol and linker regions contain conserved polybasic peptides within them (highlighted) and are implicated as NLSs. (A NLS is a short amino acid sequence that tags proteins for transport into the nucleus of a cell. NLSs are made up of positively charged amino acids, such as Ks and Rs, that are exposed on the protein's surface, with a consensus sequence of -KK/RxK/R- e. g., -PKKKRKV- is the first discovered NLS from the SV40 large antigen. Interestingly, the deletion of an NLS usually disrupts the nuclear import process. In the same way, fusing a non-nuclear protein to an NLS often results in the protein being imported into the nucleus). A large number of invariant Ws are found throughout the sequence.

CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) MSA of the ε DNA polymerases from various plant sources

tr A0A8D9D0I3 A0A8D9D0I3_BRACM	-----MSGDMRRWRDKD- SRRSNTQKVVVKTAEDELESKLGFG	36
tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM	-----MSGDMRRWRDKD- SRRSNTQKVVVKTAEDELESKLGFG	36
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	-----MSGDMRRWRDKD- TRWSKKPKVVNTAEDELESKLGFG	36 NLS
tr D7KI06 D7KI06_ARALL	-----MSGDMRRWRDKD- TRWSKKPKVVNTAEDELESKLGFG	36
tr A0A9Q0FIP5 A0A9Q0FIP5_9ROSI	-----MKADGRRWNRKDSGRS SKKQKLI RNAAEELDLKFGPD	37
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034_TRIWF	-----MNGDSRRRDRDLTRS SKKQKQI FSAEEEELESKLGID	37
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	-----MNGDARRRDLRDFGRS SKKQKLI RNSEELDLKFGPD	37
tr A0A2C9VYG0 A0A2C9VYG0_MANES	-----MNGDARRRDLRDFGRS SKKQKLI RNSEELDLKFGPD	37
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976_FAGSY	-----MSGNGRKNWDRD- PRS FKKQKLI RTAEELLESKLGFD	36
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6_QUELO	-----MNGEARRRDRD- PRS SKKQKLI RTAGEELLESKFGFD	36
tr A0A7I8KHB8 A0A7I8KHB8_SPIIN	-----MAKGEGRGW- EKGRDRKRVSEQKLRFSKEDALEAKLGFD	37
tr A0A619QIG1 A0A619QIG1_ELAGV	-----MNSGGKWRER- S SRNPSKQKLR LNAAEVLERKLGFD	35
tr A0A8B8JBU2 A0A8B8JBU2_PHODC	-----MNINGGRRRER- S SRNPSKQKLR LNAAEVLERKLGFD	35
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2_PHODC	-----MNINGGRRRER- S SRNPSKQKLR LNAAEVLERKLGFD	35
tr A0A816WFC8 A0A816WFC8_HORVV	MSGGDGRRRRP SAGGGGGGGGGGGGGGGGGGSSAAKEQRLRLGAEELLEGLGFA	60
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6_AEGTS	-----MSGGDGRRRRP SAGGGGGV-----GGVGGSWGRRSSAAKEQRTLGAEEELLEGLGFA	55
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT	---MSGRRRPAATGGGG---GGGGGGGNW---RRSGSAKAKEQRLRLGAEELLESLGFA	52
tr A0A3L6E143 A0A3L6E143_MAIZE	---MSGRRRPAATGGGG---GGGGGGGNW---RRSGSAKAKEQRLRLGAEELLESLGFA	52
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE	---MSGRRRPAAGGG---GGGGGNW---RRGSSAAKEQRLRLGAEELLESLGFA	46
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357_9POAL	---MSGRRRPAAGGGGG---GGGGGGGNW---RRGSSAAKEQRLRLGAEELLESLGFA	51
tr A0A835EHQ0 A0A835EHQ0_9POAL	---MSGRRRPAAGGGGG---GGGGGGGNW---RRGSSAAKEQRLRLGAEELLESLGFA	51
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL	---MSGRRRPAAGGGGG---GGGGGGGNW---RRGSSAAKEQRLRLGAEELLESLGFA	51
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62_SETIT	---MSGRRRPAAGGGGGGGGGGGGGGGGNW---RRGSSAAKEQRLRLGAEELLESLGFA	55

tr A0A8D9D0I3 A0A8D9D0I3_BRACM	LFSEGETRLGWLTLFASSSWEDDPDFGKTYSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKTKYKFRPYFYAATKE	96
tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM	LFSEGETRLGWLTLFASSSWEDDPDFGKTYSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKTKYKFRPYFYAATKE	96
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	LFSEGETRLGWLTLFASSSWEDRDTGKTYSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKTKYKFRPYFYAATKD	96
tr D7KI06 D7KI06_ARALL	LFSEGETRLGWLTLFASSSWEDRDTGKTYSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKTKYKFRPYFYAATKD	96
tr A0A9Q0FIP5 A0A9Q0FIP5_9ROSI	LFSQGDRLGWLTLFAPSSWEDDFTGRVYHSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKSKYKFRPYFYAATKG	97
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034_TRIWF	LFSEGDRLGWLTLFASSSWEDDFTFNKYSCIDLYFVTDGDFYFKSKCREPYFYAATKE	97
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	LFTEGDKRLGWLTLFASSSWEDDFTFRKYHSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKSKFKFRPYFYAATKD	97
tr A0A2C9VYG0 A0A2C9VYG0_MANES	LFTEGDKRLGWLTLFASSSWEDDFTFRKYHSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKSKFKFRPYFYAATKE	97
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976_FAGSY	IFSEGEKRLGWLTLFAPSSWEDDFTFRKYHSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKAKHKFRPYFYAATKD	96
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6_QUELO	LFSEGDRLGWLTLFAPSSWEDDFTQHVYHSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKSKYKFRPYFYAATKE	96
tr A0A7I8KHB8 A0A7I8KHB8_SPIIN	LFTEGETRLGWLTLFSTSSLEDEQANKIYSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKCKYKFRPYFYAATKE	97
tr A0A619QIG1 A0A619QIG1_ELAGV	LFTEGEKRLGWLTLFAPSSWEDDFTFNKYHSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKVKYFRPYFYAATKE	95
tr A0A8B8JBU2 A0A8B8JBU2_PHODC	LFTEGEKRLGWLTLFAPSSWEDDFTFNKYHSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKVKYFRPYFYAAAKE	95
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2_PHODC	LFTEGEKRLGWLTLFAPSSWEDDFTFNKYHSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKVKYFRPYFYAAAKE	95
tr A0A816WFC8 A0A816WFC8_HORVV	PYTDGERLRLGWLTLFAPSSWEDDFTGKIYSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKVKYFRPYFYAATKE	120
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6_AEGTS	PYTDGERLRLGWLTLFAPSSWEDDFTGKIYSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKVKYFRPYFYAATKE	60
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT	PYTDGERLRLGWLTLFAPSSWEDDFTGNIYSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKVKYFRPYFYAATKE	115
tr A0A3L6E143 A0A3L6E143_MAIZE	PYTDGERLRLGWLTLFAPSSWEDDFTGKIYSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKAKYKFRPYFYAATKD	112
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE	PYTDGERLRLGWLTLFAPSSWEDDFTGKIYSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKVKYFRPYFYAATKD	112
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357_9POAL	PYTDGERLRLGWLTLFAPSSWEDDFTGKIYSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKVKYFRPYFYAATKD	106
tr A0A835EHQ0 A0A835EHQ0_9POAL	PYTDGERLRLGWLTLFAPSSWEDDFTGKIYSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKVKYFRPYFYAATKD	111
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL	PYTDGERLRLGWLTLFAPSSWEDDFTGKIYSCVDLYFVTDGDFYFKVKYFRPYFYAGTKD	111
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62_SETIT	PYTDGERLRLGWLTLFAPSSWEDDFTGKIYSCIDLYFVTDGDFYFKVKYFRPYFYAATKD	115

tr A0A8D9D0I3 A0A8D9D0I3_BRACM	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	DDKFRQRKLD MFSSANKDGVLDK-----	1219
tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	DDKFRQRKLD MFSSANKDGVLDK-----	1219
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	DDKFRQRKLD MFSSANKDGVLDLDT-----	1167 NLS
tr D7KI06 D7KI06_ARALL	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	DDKFRQRKLD MFSSANKDGGLET-----	1184
tr A0A9Q0FIP5 A0A9Q0FIP5_9ROSI	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	EDKFRQRKLD DIFSLCNKDAVLRNTTDDGT	1189
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034_TRIWF	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	EDKFRQRKLD DIFSSSHRNDLLEKANN-SI	1173
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	EDKFRQRKLD DIFSLNSNGDESSRRTSD--S	1173
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	EDKFRQRKLD DIFSLNSNGDESSRRTSD--S	1172
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976_FAGSY	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	EDKFRQRKLD DIFSLNKKDDLKIKNSDAAG	1158
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6_QUELO	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	EDKFRQRKLD DIFSSLNDRDEFLLKIKNSDAAG	1173
tr A0A7I8KHB8 A0A7I8KHB8_SPIIN	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	DDKFRQRKLD DMFGPIINGGTMQNHAS-VD	1173
tr A0A6I9QIG1 A0A6I9QIG1_ELAGV	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	EDKFRQRKLD DIFSTVKNKDETIMQ-----	1166
tr A0A8B8JBU2 A0A8B8JBU2_PHODC	SI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	EDKFRQRKLD DIFNTVKNKDETIMQ-----	1165
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2_PHODC	SI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	EDKFRQRKLD DIFNTVKNKDETIMQ-----	1165
tr A0A8I6WFC8 A0A8I6WFC8_HORVV	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	DDKFRQRKLD DMFSPLNKDMGM-H-----	1189
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6_AEGTS	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	DDKFRQRKLD DMFSPLNKDMGM-H-----	1129
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	DDKFRQRKLD DMFSPLNKDMGM-H-----	1184
tr A0A3L6EI43 A0A3L6EI43_MAIZE	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	DDKFRQRKLD DIFSPLAKEEGL-H-----	1162
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	DDKFRQRKLD DIFSPLAKEEGL-H-----	1162
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357_9POAL	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	DDKFRQRKLD DIFSPLAKEEGL-H-----	1175
tr A0A835EHQ0 A0A835EHQ0_9POAL	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	DDKFRQRKLD DIFSPLAKEEGL-H-----	1180
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	DDKFRQRKLD DIFSPLAKEEGL-H-----	1180
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62_SETIT	TI PAAMQKV ANPVPRLV HPDWL HKKVREK	DDKFRQRKLD DIFSPLAKEEGL-H-----	1184

tr A0A8D9D0I3 A0A8D9D0I3_BRACM	-NHSVAQDDMDIEEFCENK-PGVKGPKP--IARSYEVNKEQFGRQQE-----	1265
tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM	-NHSVAQDDMDIEEFCENK-PGVKGPKP--IARSYEVNKEQFGRQQE-----	1265
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	-DLFVTKDNVDEIEFCENK-PSVKGPKP--IARSYEVNKKQSECEQQE-----	1213
tr D7KI06 D7KI06_ARALL	-DHPVTKNVDEIEFCENK-PSVKGPKP--IARSYEVNKKQSEREQE-----	1230
tr A0A9Q0FIP5 A0A9Q0FIP5_9ROSI	SNH-LADRNVQDIEEFLNQS--SSVNGPRP--IVRSYEVSNKGVKKTG---KVDSEAQ	1241
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034_TRIWF	INPVTNGEHEVDEEFGSKTR-SPVNGPRP--VVNSYEFNKNKRPVQITIG---QVESLQQ	1227
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	ADHIMNKENVEDEEFGNKS--SSKNGPRP--IVRLYEMNKGKCLQATG---RMDSSQQ	1226
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	ADHIMNKENVEDEEFGNKS--SSKNGPRP--IVRLYEMNKGKCLQATG---RMDSSQQ	1225
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976_FAGSY	TGDMVNEEIVEDEEFGNKK--SSVNGPRP--IVRCYEVNRRQHSVKTNG---QVGHLLR	1212
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6_QUELO	ANGVMNEEIVKDEEFGNKR--KSVTGRPP--IVRCYEVNRRQHSVKTND---QVGLLQQ	1227
tr A0A7I8KHB8 A0A7I8KHB8_SPIIN	SNHELHEMIEVDEEFLMKENR-SSVNGPRP--IVRSYEVNRRQHSVKTND---QVGLLQQ	1231
tr A0A6I9QIG1 A0A6I9QIG1_ELAGV	-----DEMNVGDEEFLIAKDV-S-KGPRP--VVHSYEVNKENYSSKQSCPEAGLLSHK	1217
tr A0A8B8JBU2 A0A8B8JBU2_PHODC	-----DGTNVGDEEFLVTRKRV-SEVGLRP--VAHSYEVNKENYSSKQSCPEAGLLSHK	1217
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2_PHODC	-----DGTNVGDEEFLVTRKRV-SEVGLRP--VAHSYEVNKENYSSKQSCPEAGLLSHK	1217
tr A0A8I6WFC8 A0A8I6WFC8_HORVV	-----NLNGTGDEEFLVTRKRV-SEVGLRP--VAHSYEVNKENYSSKQSCPEAGLLSHK	1217
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6_AEGTS	-----NLNGTGDEEFLVTRKRV-SEVGLRP--VAHSYEVNKENYSSKQSCPEAGLLSHK	1217
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT	-----NLNGTGDEEFLVTRKRV-SEVGLRP--VAHSYEVNKENYSSKQSCPEAGLLSHK	1217
tr A0A3L6EI43 A0A3L6EI43_MAIZE	-----NLNRTGDEEFLVTRKRV-SEVGLRP--VAHSYEVNKENYSSKQSCPEAGLLSHK	1210
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE	-----NLNRTGDEEFLVTRKRV-SEVGLRP--VAHSYEVNKENYSSKQSCPEAGLLSHK	1210
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357_9POAL	-----NLNRTGDEEFLVTRKRV-SEVGLRP--VAHSYEVNKENYSSKQSCPEAGLLSHK	1223
tr A0A835EHQ0 A0A835EHQ0_9POAL	-----NLNRTGDEEFLVTRKRV-SEVGLRP--VAHSYEVNKENYSSKQSCPEAGLLSHK	1228
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL	-----NLNRTGDEEFLVTRKRV-SEVGLRP--VAHSYEVNKENYSSKQSCPEAGLLSHK	1228
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62_SETIT	-----SLNGTGDEEFLVTRKRV-SEVGLRP--VAHSYEVNKENYSSKQSCPEAGLLSHK	1232

tr A0A8D9D0I3 A0A8D9D0I3_BRACM	---S-----KDPKDDDISFENIDKNVDYQGWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1315
tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM	---S-----KDPKDDDISFENIDKNVDYQGWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1315
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	---S-----WDFEF-HDISFQNIKDSVNYQGWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1262 NLS
tr D7KI06 D7KI06_ARALL	---S-----WDFEF-HDISFQNIKDSVNYQGWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1279
tr A0A9Q0FIP5 A0A9Q0FIP5_9ROSI	QSSHTAEIHEFSSQLNTPSEDIKDNVDYQGWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1301
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034_TRIWF	QTDGK-----RESIELLQNASSTESIDRNVDYQGWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1275
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	QINN-----RESIELLQNASSTESIDRNVDYQGWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1281
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	QINN-----RESIELLQNASSTESIDRNVDYQGWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1281
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976_FAGSY	QDDHSENVLQELPPLQNASSTESIDRNVDYQGWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1272
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6_QUELO	QTDHRL-----PALSENIDKNVDYQGWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1276
tr A0A7I8KHB8 A0A7I8KHB8_SPIIN	QEDGAHGKHPQLSPMENLISTSDSIDRNVDYQGWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1291
tr A0A6I9QIG1 A0A6I9QIG1_ELAGV	QQNA--TLCRPLLSFNQNGTCESEVDRNIDYQAWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1275
tr A0A8B8JBU2 A0A8B8JBU2_PHODC	QQNA--TLCRPLLSFNQNGTCESEVDRNIDYQAWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1275
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2_PHODC	QQNA--TLCRPLLSFNQNGTCESEVDRNIDYQAWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1275
tr A0A8I6WFC8 A0A8I6WFC8_HORVV	QQKSVIRSNP-----LRDSDADERVDSTDYQGWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1295
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6_AEGTS	QQKSVIRSNP-----LRDSDADERVDSTDYQGWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1235
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT	QQKSVIRSNP-----LRDSDADERVDSTDYQGWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1290
tr A0A3L6EI43 A0A3L6EI43_MAIZE	QQNCMTGLNVPCPSIQNAASYEVTVDKGTDYQGWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1270
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE	QQNCMTGLNVPCPSIQNAASYEVTVDKGTDYQGWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1270
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357_9POAL	QRNSKTGLNAPLSSQMPNVADEITDRSSDYQGWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1288
tr A0A835EHQ0 A0A835EHQ0_9POAL	QRNSKTGLNAPLSSQMPNVADEITDRSSDYQGWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1288
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL	QQNSVTGLNVPLSSQIENAADEITDRSTDYQGWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1288
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62_SETIT	QQNSITGLNVPLSSQIENAADEITDRSTDYQGWLVEKRRKWKVIVEKRRRRLGDRSL	1292

tr A0A8D9D0I3 A0A8D9D0I3_BRACM	KQIESH-----EIKKVVTVRRGVGS	FFRRPEEALTSSSHQI-----	1352
tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM	KQIESH-----EIKKVVTVRRGVGS	FFRRPEEALTSSSHQI-----	1352
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	NQVDTH-----EINQKVGQGRGGVGS	YFRRPEEALTSSSHQI-----	1299
tr D7KI06 D7KI06_ARALL	NQSDAH-----EINQKVGQGRGGVGS	YFRRPEEALTSSSHQVCT-----	1318
tr A0A9Q0FIP5 A0A9Q0FIP5_9ROSI	RGSDGAFEHGLGSLGTEKE	YFTRPEVVLTRCHWQ-----	1343
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034_TRIWF	HRADGASEVMEGMISKRG----	YFRRHEVALTRCHWQ-----	1317
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	NRANGASEPLGLSLINNK----	YFATHEISLTRCHWQ-----	1324
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	NRANGASEPLGLSLINNK----	YFATHEISLTRCHWQ-----	1323
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976_FAGSY	HRNGVSDLLGGVTNGKD----	YFRRQVALTRCHWQ-----	1314
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6_QUELO	RRGKGVLEVLGDVTHNKD----	YFRRHEVALTRCHWQ-----	1318
tr A0A7I8KHB8 A0A7I8KHB8_SPIIN	SQFVAMAGNHESMTSNKH----	YFRRQELLVHNNHWQ-----	1333
tr A0A6I9QIG1 A0A6I9QIG1_ELAGV	QQSAGAALKPASMENYRRG----	YFRRQELALVQSHWQ-----	1317
tr A0A8B8JBU2 A0A8B8JBU2_PHODC	QQSAGAALKPASMENYRRH----	YFRRQELALVQSHWQ-----	1317
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2_PHODC	QQSAGAALKPASMENYRRH----	YFRRQELALVQSHWQ-----	1317
tr A0A8I6WFC8 A0A8I6WFC8_HORVV	EGSPNN-----LFSARNGSQLHGNGRNRST	FFQKQELSLFRSHWQ-----	1335
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6_AEGTS	EGSPNN-----LFSARNSQLHGNSRNRST	FFQKQELSLFRSHWQ-----	1275
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT	EGSPNN-----LFSARNSQLHGNGRNRST	FFQKQELSLFRSHWQ-----	1330
tr A0A3L6EI43 A0A3L6EI43_MAIZE	HVS-LL-----LPGWVLPPLLTLLTLCRSP	YFRRQELALVQSHWQ-----	1295
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE	DDP-NA-----LLSARHANQLPNSRNRST	FFQKQELALFRSHWQACV--FCYLLCSVA	1321
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357_9POAL	DGPTNA-----LLSSRNANQLPNSRNRST	FFQKQELALFRSHWQ-----	1323
tr A0A835EHQ0 A0A835EHQ0_9POAL	DGPTNA-----LLSSRNANQLPNSRNRST	FFQKQELALFRSHWQ-----	1328
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL	DGPTNA-----LLSSRNANQLPNSRNRST	FFQKQELALFRSHWQ-----	1328
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62_SETIT	DGPTNA-----LLSSRNANQLPNSRNRST	FFQKQELALFRSHWQ-----	1332

tr A0A8D9D0I3 A0A8D9D0I3_BRACM	LHKVMQKVFALLLTDLRR	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKFDLSAAKAY	CSLLTAVGNSDIF	1866
tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM	LHKVMQKVFALLLTDLRR	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKFDLSAAKAY	CSLLTAVGNSDIF	1866
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	LHKVMQKVFALLLTDLRR	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	VKFDLSAAKAY	CSLLTAVGNSDIF	1847
tr D7KI06 D7KI06_ARALL	LHKVMQKVFALLLTDLRR	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	VKFDLSAAKAY	CSLLTAVGNRVS	1865
tr A0A9Q0FIP5 A0A9Q0FIP5_9ROSI	LHKVMQKVFALLLAEELRR	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKFNLSAAQAY	CSLVKTLQSRMF	1907
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034_TRIWF	LHKVMQKVFALLLAEELRR	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKSDIAAAKAY	CSLVKALQTRFL	1866
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	LHKVMQKVFALLLAEFRK	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKLSLSAAKAY	CSLLKTLQSRFL	1874
tr A0A2C9VYGO A0A2C9VYGO_MANES	LHKVMQKVFALLLAEFRK	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKLSLSAAKAY	CSLLKTLQSRFL	1873
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976_FAGSY	LHKVMQKVFALLLAEFRK	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKFDLSAAKAY	CSLLKTLQNRDLF	1864
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6_QUELO	LHKVMQKVFALLLAEFRK	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKFDLSAAKAY	CSLLKTLQKRDLF	1867
tr A0A7I8KHB8 A0A7I8KHB8_SPIIN	LHKVMQKVFALLLAEFRK	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKFDLSAAKAY	CSLLKALQARDLL	1874
tr A0A6I9QIG1 A0A6I9QIG1_ELAGV	LHKVMQKVFALLLAEFRK	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKIDLSAAKAY	CSLLKTLQTRDLF	1864
tr A0A8B8JBU2 A0A8B8JBU2_PHODC	LHKVMQKVFALLLAEFRK	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKIDLSAAKAY	CSLLKTLQTRDLF	1864
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2_PHODC	LHKVMQKVFALLLAEFRK	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKIDLSAAKAY	CSLLKTLQTRDLF	1867
tr A0A8I6WFC8 A0A8I6WFC8_HORVV	LHKVMQKVFALLLAEFRK	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKVDLPSARAY	CSLLKTLQTRDLF	1879
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6_AEGTS	LHKVMQKVFALLLAEFRK	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKVDLPSARAY	CSLLKTLQTRDLF	1819
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT	LHKVMQKVFALLLAEFRK	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKVDLPSARAY	CSLLKTLQTRDLF	1874
tr A0A3L6EI43 A0A3L6EI43_MAIZE	LHKVMQKVFALLLAEELRR	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKVDLSAAHAY	CSLLKTLQTRDLF	1870
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE	LHKVMQKVFALLLAEELRR	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKVDLSAAHAY	CSLLKTLQTRDLF	1887
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357_9POAL	LHKVMQKVFALLLAEFRK	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKVDLSAAQAY	CSLLKTLQTRDLF	1865
tr A0A835EHQ0 A0A835EHQ0_9POAL	LHKVMQKVFALLLAEFRK	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKVDLSAAQAY	CSLLKTLQTRDLF	1872
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL	LHKVMQKVFALLLAEFRK	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKVDLSAAHAY	CSLLKTLQTRDLF	1872
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62_SETIT	LHKVMQKVFALLLAEFRK	LGATIIYADFSKVIIDT	GKVDLSAAHAY	CSLLKTLQTRDLF	1876

tr A0A8D9D0I3 A0A8D9D0I3_BRACM	-----VMKRNLLKYINVKEFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2066
tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM	-----ILFLKLCFAVMKRNLLKYINVKEFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2080
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	-----VMKRNLLKYINVKEFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2046
tr D7KI06 D7KI06_ARALL	SNLISGNLVLETMTNRMKRNLLKYINVKEFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2126
tr A0A9Q0FIP5 A0A9Q0FIP5_9ROSI	-----VMRNLKLVYRVREFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2145
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034_TRIWF	-----VMRNLKLVYRVREFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2091
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	-----VMRNLKLVYRVREFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2111
tr A0A2C9VYGO A0A2C9VYGO_MANES	-----VMRNLKLVYRVREFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2110
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976_FAGSY	-----VMRNLKLVYRVREFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2054
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6_QUELO	-----VMRNLKLVYRVREFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2094
tr A0A7I8KHB8 A0A7I8KHB8_SPIIN	-----RMRNLLKLVYRVREFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2103
tr A0A6I9QIG1 A0A6I9QIG1_ELAGV	-----RMRNLLKLVYRVREFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2097
tr A0A8B8JBU2 A0A8B8JBU2_PHODC	-----RMRNLLKLVYRVREFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2097
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2_PHODC	-----RMRNLLKLVYRVREFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2100
tr A0A8I6WFC8 A0A8I6WFC8_HORVV	-----RMRNLLKLVYRVREFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2108
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6_AEGTS	-----RMRNLLKLVYRVREFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2048
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT	-----RMRNLLKLVYRVREFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2103
tr A0A3L6EI43 A0A3L6EI43_MAIZE	-----RMRNLLKLVYRVREFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2094
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE	-----RMRNLLKLVYRVREFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2111
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357_9POAL	-----RMRNLLKLVYRVREFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2093
tr A0A835EHQ0 A0A835EHQ0_9POAL	-----RMRNLLKLVYRVREFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2098
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL	-----RMRNLLKLVYRVREFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2098
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62_SETIT	-----RMRNLLKLVYRVREFAAEAEFLDPGPFILPNV	CSNC	DAYR	2102

tr A0A8D9D0I3 A0A8D9D0I3_BRACM	LDIGRDPALLTEKEW	CS	2126
tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM	LDIGRDPALLTEKEW	CS	2140
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	LDICRDPALLTEKEWS	CS	2106
tr D7KI06 D7KI06_ARALL	LDICRDPALLTEKEWS	CS	2186
tr A0A9Q0FIP5 A0A9Q0FIP5_9ROSI	LDICRDPALLTEKEWS	CS	2204
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034_TRIWF	LDICRDSALL-AQEWRC	CS	2150
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	LDICRDPALLTEKEWS	CS	2170
tr A0A2C9VYGO A0A2C9VYGO_MANES	LDICRDPALLTEKEWS	CS	2169
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976_FAGSY	LDICRDSVLL-AQEWRC	CS	2113
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6_QUELO	LDICRDPALLTEKEWS	CS	2153
tr A0A7I8KHB8 A0A7I8KHB8_SPIIN	LDICRDSALL-AQEWRC	CS	2162
tr A0A6I9QIG1 A0A6I9QIG1_ELAGV	LDICRDSALS-DNEWR	CS	2156
tr A0A8B8JBU2 A0A8B8JBU2_PHODC	LDICRDSALS-DSEWR	CS	2159
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2_PHODC	LDICRDSALS-DSEWR	CS	2157
tr A0A8I6WFC8 A0A8I6WFC8_HORVV	LDICRDPALLTEKEWS	CS	2169
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6_AEGTS	LDICRDPALLTEKEWS	CS	2107
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT	LDICRDPALLTEKEWS	CS	2162
tr A0A3L6EI43 A0A3L6EI43_MAIZE	LDICRDSALO-GQEWRC	CS	2153
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE	LDICRDSALO-GQEWRC	CS	2170
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357_9POAL	LDICRDPALLTEKEWS	CS	2152
tr A0A835EHQ0 A0A835EHQ0_9POAL	LDICRDPALLTEKEWS	CS	2157
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL	LDICRDPALLTEKEWS	CS	2157
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62_SETIT	LDICRDPALLTEKEWS	CS	2161

tr A0A8D9D0I3 A0A8D9D0I3_BRACM	AAHLTEC	CS	2186
tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM	AAHLTEC	CS	2200
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	AAHLTEC	CS	2161
tr D7KI06 D7KI06_ARALL	AAHLTEC	CS	2241
tr A0A9Q0FIP5 A0A9Q0FIP5_9ROSI	AAHLTEC	CS	2257
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034_TRIWF	AAHLTEC	CS	2203
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	AAHLTEC	CS	2223
tr A0A2C9VYGO A0A2C9VYGO_MANES	AAHLTEC	CS	2222
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976_FAGSY	AAHLTEC	CS	2166
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6_QUELO	AAHLTEC	CS	2206
tr A0A7I8KHB8 A0A7I8KHB8_SPIIN	AAHLTEC	CS	2215
tr A0A6I9QIG1 A0A6I9QIG1_ELAGV	AAHLTEC	CS	2209
tr A0A8B8JBU2 A0A8B8JBU2_PHODC	AAHLTEC	CS	2209
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2_PHODC	AAHLTEC	CS	2212
tr A0A8I6WFC8 A0A8I6WFC8_HORVV	AAHVSEC	CS	2218
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6_AEGTS	AAHVSEC	CS	2160
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT	AAHVSEC	CS	2215
tr A0A3L6EI43 A0A3L6EI43_MAIZE	AAHLSEC	CS	2206
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE	AAHLSEC	CS	2223
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357_9POAL	AAHLSEC	CS	2205
tr A0A835EHQ0 A0A835EHQ0_9POAL	AAHLSEC	CS	2210
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL	AAHLSEC	CS	2210
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62_SETIT	AAHLSEC	CS	2214

//End of the plant pol ε sequences		
tr A0A8D9D0I3 A0A8D9D0I3_BRACM	GRHHS	2191
tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM	GRHHS	2205
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	-----	2161
tr D7KI06 D7KI06_ARALL	-----	2241
tr A0A9Q0FIP5 A0A9Q0FIP5_9ROSI	-----	2257
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034_TRIWF	-----	2203
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	-----	2223
tr A0A2C9VYG0 A0A2C9VYG0_MANES	-----	2222
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976_FAGSY	-----	2166
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6_QUELO	-----	2206
tr A0A7I8KHB8 A0A7I8KHB8_SPIIN	-----	2215
tr A0A6I9QIG1 A0A6I9QIG1_ELAGV	-----	2209
tr A0A8B8JBU2 A0A8B8JBU2_PHODC	-----	2209
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2_PHODC	-----	2212
tr A0A8I6WFC8 A0A8I6WFC8_HORVV	-----	2218
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6_AEGTS	-----	2160
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT	-----	2215
tr A0A3L6EI43 A0A3L6EI43_MAIZE	-----	2206
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE	-----	2223
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357_9POAL	-----	2205
tr A0A835EHQ0 A0A835EHQ0_9POAL	-----	2210
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL	-----	2210
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62_SETIT	-----	2214

NLS, Nuclear Localization Signal

A0A8D9D0I3_BRACM, <i>Brassica campestris</i>	A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM, <i>Brassica campestris</i>
F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH, <i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	D7KI06_ARALL, <i>Arabidopsis lyrata</i> subsp. <i>lyrata</i>
A0A9Q0FIP5_9ROSI, <i>Turnerasubulata</i>	A0A7J7C034_TRIWF, <i>Tripterygium wilfordii</i>
A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES, <i>Manihot esculenta</i>	A0A2C9VYG0_MANES, <i>Manihot esculenta</i>
A0A2N9F976_FAGSY, <i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	A0A7N2KME6_QUELO, <i>Quercus lobata</i>
A0A7I8KHB8_SPIIN, <i>Spirodela intermedia</i>	A0A6I9QIG1_ELAGV, <i>Elaeagnus tenuis</i> var. <i>tenera</i>
A0A8B8JBC2_PHODC, <i>Phoenix dactylifera</i>	A0A8B8JBU2_PHODC, <i>Phoenix dactylifera</i>
A0A8I6WFC8_HORVV, <i>Hordeum vulgare</i>	A0A452YAR6_AEGTS, <i>Aegilops tauschii</i> subsp. <i>stragulata</i>
A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT, <i>Triticum aestivum</i>	A0A3L6EI43_MAIZE, <i>Zea mays</i>
A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE, <i>Zea mays</i>	A0A835B357_9POAL, <i>Digitaria exilis</i>
A0A835EHQ0_9POAL, <i>Digitaria exilis</i>	A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL, <i>Panicum hallii</i>
A0A368PL62_SETIT, <i>Setaria italica</i>	

Figure 3 MSA of the catalytic subunit of the DNA pol ε (Pol2A) from various plant sources

Figure 4 shows the MSA of the DNA pol ε from various animal sources (only the required regions for the discussions are shown here). The human sequence is used as the standard and highlighted. The PR exo and pol regions in the human sequence are highlighted in red and green, respectively, and the PR active site amino acids are highlighted in light blue and the pol active site amino acids are highlighted in yellow. The typical, completely conserved –DEDD– superfamily of PR exonuclease active site amino acids are found with an invariant Y as proton acceptor in the NTD and is in close agreement with the other RdRps/DdDps [8]. The proposed template-binding pair (-YG-), catalytic amino acid (K) and the dNTP selection amino acid (Q) are found in the pol domain and are in close agreement as reported in other DdDps and DdRps [8,16] and also with the plant enzymes (Fig.3). Unlike other two eukaryotic replicative pols, the pol ε harbours a unique ZBM within the pol domain, similar to the pol ε from the plant sources (highlighted). A dNTP selecting –SYLPVGS– motif is found within the first PR exo region as found in plant enzymes, –SYLPQGS–. However, a second PR exonuclease active site and a putative pol catalytic core are also identified in the CTD (highlighted). Similar to the –SYLPXXS– at the NTD, a –SYLEPGS– motif (highlighted in yellow) is found within the second PR exo region in the CTD. A large NTD deletion analysis has implicated a possible second pol region in the CTD, e.g., a large N-terminal deletion (Δ176-1134 amino acids) of the yeast *pol ε* gene (which deletes both the pol and PR exo domains), but retains the C-terminal region intact, showed that the yeast was viable, but grew slowly, suggesting a possible second pol active site in the CTD as discussed elsewhere [20]. The CTD contains the two regular ZBMs and one of them (CysB) binds the 4Fe-4S cluster (highlighted in orange) as found in all the three eukaryotic replicative pols. The putative NLSs are highlighted. Many conserved Ws are observed in the CTD, suggesting their possible involvement in interactions with the other subunits.

CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) MSA of ε DNA pols from various animal sources

		Pol-ZBM		
tr	IA0A6Q2WNN8 IA0A6Q2WNN8_ESOLU	ARHEKRLADYCKRAYKK HHTRLERVTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	770
tr	IA0A673YLH4 IA0A673YLH4_SALTR	ARHEKRLADYCKRAYKK RQTKLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	776
tr	IA0A4W5MAK2 IA0A4W5MAK2_9TELE	ARHEKRLADYCKRAYKK RQTKLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	776
tr	IA0A6P6MI98 IA0A6P6MI98_CARAU	ARHEKRLADYCKRAYKK HHTRLERVTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	775
tr	IA0A498LK69 IA0A498LK69_LABRO	ARHEKRLADYCKRAYKK HHTRLERVTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	751
tr	IA0A3Q2YTI5 IA0A3Q2YTI5_HIPCM	AKHEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	775
tr	IM4A042 IM4A042_XIFMA	AKHEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	776
tr	IA0A6P8SZE0 IA0A6P8SZE0_GYMAC	AKHEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	774
tr	IA0A3Q2PG22 IA0A3Q2PG22_FUNHE	AKHEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	776
tr	IA0A6A4SMP2 IA0A6A4SMP2_SCOMX	AKHEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	754
tr	IA0A673CZR7 IA0A673CZR7_9TELE	AKHEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	776
tr	IA0A671YAK3 IA0A671YAK3_SPAAU	AKHEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	776
tr	IA0A6P7J2Q5 IA0A6P7J2Q5_9TELE	AKHEKRLADYCKRAYKK HITKVEERLTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	776
tr	IA0A7N8YN60 IA0A7N8YN60_9TELE	AKHEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	784
tr	IA0A3P8N896 IA0A3P8N896_ASTCA	AKHEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	775
tr	IA0A3B4GLI9 IA0A3B4GLI9_9CICH	AKHEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	775
tr	IA0A6A5F6M3 IA0A6A5F6M3_PERFL	AKHEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	776
tr	IA0A3Q1FLK4 IA0A3Q1FLK4_9TELE	AKHEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	776
tr	IA0A4W6G9K4 IA0A4W6G9K4_LATCA	AKHEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	776
tr	IA0A3B4YTJ5 IA0A3B4YTJ5_SERLL	AKHEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	776
tr	IA0A665X3K2 IA0A665X3K2_ECHNA	AKHEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	776
tr	IA0A7J7RQ84 IA0A7J7RQ84_RHIFE	AKYEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	748
tr	IA0A6P6DOR3 IA0A6P6DOR3_PTEVA	AKYEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	767
tr	IA0A7J8H4F1 IA0A7J8H4F1_ROUAE	AKYEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	781
tr	IA0A5F4D2S5 IA0A5F4D2S5_CANLF	AKYEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	810
sp	IQ07864 DPOE1_HUMAN	AKYEKRLADYCKRAYKK HITKVEERLTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	773
tr	IA0A2I3S482 IA0A2I3S482_PANTR	AKYEKRLADYCKRAYKK HITKVEERLTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	775
tr	IA0A2K6CI58 IA0A2K6CI58_MACNE	AKYEKRLADYCKRAYKK HITKVEERLTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	775
tr	IA0A834DIT3 IA0A834DIT3_9CHIR	AKYEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	775
tr	F62911 F62911_HORSE	AKYEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	775
tr	IA0A5G2RB90 IA0A5G2RB90_PIG	AKYEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	748
tr	IA0A670JP16 IA0A670JP16_PODMU	AKYEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	773
tr	IA0A852LC41 IA0A852LC41_UROIN	AKYEKRLADYCKRAYKK HVTLEERVTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	792
tr	F62FB6 F62FB6_ORNAN	AKYEKRLADYCKRAYKK HITKVEERLTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	650
tr	IA0A6P5LNS3 IA0A6P5LNS3_PHACI	AKYEKRLADYCKRAYKK HITKVEERLTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	776
tr	IA0A4X2K1K8 IA0A4X2K1K8_VOMUR	AKYEKRLADYCKRAYKK HITKVEERLTTI	DRENSFYVDTVRAFDRDRRYEFGGLHKVV	760
		*:***:*.***:***:*	:*::**	*****

tr	IA0A6Q2WNN8 IA0A6Q2WNN8_ESOLU	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	830
tr	IA0A673YLH4 IA0A673YLH4_SALTR	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	836
tr	IA0A4W5MAK2 IA0A4W5MAK2_9TELE	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	836
tr	IA0A6P6MI98 IA0A6P6MI98_CARAU	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	835
tr	IA0A498LK69 IA0A498LK69_LABRO	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	811
tr	IA0A3Q2YTI5 IA0A3Q2YTI5_HIPCM	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	835
tr	IM4A042 IM4A042_XIFMA	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	836
tr	IA0A6P8SZE0 IA0A6P8SZE0_GYMAC	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	836
tr	IA0A3Q2PG22 IA0A3Q2PG22_FUNHE	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	836
tr	IA0A6A4SMP2 IA0A6A4SMP2_SCOMX	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	814
tr	IA0A673CZR7 IA0A673CZR7_9TELE	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	836
tr	IA0A671YAK3 IA0A671YAK3_SPAAU	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	836
tr	IA0A6P7J2Q5 IA0A6P7J2Q5_9TELE	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	836
tr	IA0A7N8YN60 IA0A7N8YN60_9TELE	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	844
tr	IA0A3P8N896 IA0A3P8N896_ASTCA	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	835
tr	IA0A3B4GLI9 IA0A3B4GLI9_9CICH	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	835
tr	IA0A6A5F6M3 IA0A6A5F6M3_PERFL	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	836
tr	IA0A3Q1FLK4 IA0A3Q1FLK4_9TELE	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	836
tr	IA0A4W6G9K4 IA0A4W6G9K4_LATCA	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	836
tr	IA0A3B4YTJ5 IA0A3B4YTJ5_SERLL	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	836
tr	IA0A665X3K2 IA0A665X3K2_ECHNA	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	836
tr	IA0A7J7RQ84 IA0A7J7RQ84_RHIFE	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	808
tr	IA0A6P6DOR3 IA0A6P6DOR3_PTEVA	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	827
tr	IA0A7J8H4F1 IA0A7J8H4F1_ROUAE	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	841
tr	IA0A5F4D2S5 IA0A5F4D2S5_CANLF	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	870
sp	IQ07864 DPOE1_HUMAN	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	835
tr	IA0A2I3S482 IA0A2I3S482_PANTR	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	835
tr	IA0A2K6CI58 IA0A2K6CI58_MACNE	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	835
tr	IA0A834DIT3 IA0A834DIT3_9CHIR	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	835
tr	F62911 F62911_HORSE	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	835
tr	IA0A5G2RB90 IA0A5G2RB90_PIG	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	808
tr	IA0A670JP16 IA0A670JP16_PODMU	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	833
tr	IA0A852LC41 IA0A852LC41_UROIN	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	852
tr	F62FB6 F62FB6_ORNAN	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	710
tr	IA0A6P5LNS3 IA0A6P5LNS3_PHACI	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	836
tr	IA0A4X2K1K8 IA0A4X2K1K8_VOMUR	KKKLSAQAQSGDAALVKRC NMELIYDLSL	LAH KCI LNS FY V VMR GAR WY SMEMAG V	820
		*:***:*.***:***:*	:*::**	*****

tr	IA0A6Q2WNN8 IA0A6Q2WNN8_ESOLU	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		890
tr	IA0A673YLH4 IA0A673YLH4_SALTR	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		896
tr	IA0A4W5MAK2 IA0A4W5MAK2_9TELE	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		896
tr	IA0A6P6MI98 IA0A6P6MI98_CARAU	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		895
tr	IA0A498LK69 IA0A498LK69_LABRO	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		871
tr	IA0A3Q2YTI5 IA0A3Q2YTI5_HIPCM	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		895
tr	IM4A042 IM4A042_XIFMA	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		896
tr	IA0A6P8SZE0 IA0A6P8SZE0_GYMAC	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		894
tr	IA0A3Q2PG22 IA0A3Q2PG22_FUNHE	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		896
tr	IA0A6A4SMP2 IA0A6A4SMP2_SCOMX	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		874
tr	IA0A673CZR7 IA0A673CZR7_9TELE	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		896
tr	IA0A671YAK3 IA0A671YAK3_SPAAU	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		896
tr	IA0A6P7J2Q5 IA0A6P7J2Q5_9TELE	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		896
tr	IA0A7N8YN60 IA0A7N8YN60_9TELE	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		904
tr	IA0A3P8N896 IA0A3P8N896_ASTCA	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		895
tr	IA0A3B4GLI9 IA0A3B4GLI9_9CICH	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		895
tr	IA0A6A5F6M3 IA0A6A5F6M3_PERFL	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		896
tr	IA0A3Q1FLK4 IA0A3Q1FLK4_9TELE	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		896
tr	IA0A4W6G9K4 IA0A4W6G9K4_LATCA	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		896
tr	IA0A3B4YTJ5 IA0A3B4YTJ5_SERLL	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		896
tr	IA0A665X3K2 IA0A665X3K2_ECHNA	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		896
tr	IA0A7J7RQ84 IA0A7J7RQ84_RHIFE	CFTGASIIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		868
tr	IA0A6P6DOR3 IA0A6P6DOR3_PTEVA	CFTGASIIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		887
tr	IA0A7J8H4F1 IA0A7J8H4F1_ROUAE	CFTGASIIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		901
tr	IA0A5F4D2S5 IA0A5F4D2S5_CANLF	CFTGASIIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		930
sp	IQ07864 DPOE1_HUMAN	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		895
tr	IA0A2I3S482 IA0A2I3S482_PANTR	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		895
tr	IA0A2K6CI58 IA0A2K6CI58_MACNE	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		895
tr	IA0A834DIT3 IA0A834DIT3_9CHIR	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		895
tr	F62911 F62911_HORSE	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		895
tr	IA0A5G2RB90 IA0A5G2RB90_PIG	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		868
tr	IA0A670JP16 IA0A670JP16_PODMU	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		893
tr	IA0A852LC41 IA0A852LC41_UROIN	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		912
tr	F62FB6 F62FB6_ORNAN	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		770
tr	IA0A6P5LNS3 IA0A6P5LNS3_PHACI	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		896
tr	IA0A4X2K1K8 IA0A4X2K1K8_VOMUR	CYTGANIITQARELVEIQGRPLEL DD G IWC VLP NT FP EN FV KTS NEK KPK VT SY PGA		880
		*:***:*.***:***:*	:*::**	*****

tr	AOA6Q2WNN8	AOA6Q2WNN8_ESOLU	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYQELVDPASLTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	950
tr	AOA673YLH4	AOA673YLH4_SALTR	MLNIMVKEGFTNNQYQELVDPASLTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	956
tr	AOA4W5MAK2	AOA4W5MAK2_9TELE	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYQELVDPASLTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	956
tr	AOA6P6MI98	AOA6P6MI98_CARAU	MLNIMVKEGFTNHQYQELVDPASLTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	955
tr	AOA498LK69	AOA498LK69_LABRO	MLNIMVKEGFTNNQYQELVDPASLTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	931
tr	AOA3Q2YTT5	AOA3Q2YTT5_HIPCM	MLNILVKEGFTNDQYHELVDPAALTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	955
tr	M4A042	M4A042_XIPMA	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYHELVDPAALTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	956
tr	AOA6P8SZ0	AOA6P8SZ0_GYMAC	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYHELVDPAALTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	954
tr	AOA3Q2PG22	AOA3Q2PG22_FUNHE	MLNILVKEGFTNDQYHELVDPAALTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	956
tr	AOA6A4SMP2	AOA6A4SMP2_SCOMX	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYHELVDPAALTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	934
tr	AOA673CZR7	AOA673CZR7_9TELE	MLNILVKEGFTNDQYHELVDPAALTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	956
tr	AOA671YAK3	AOA671YAK3_SPAAU	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYHELVDPAALTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	956
tr	AOA6P7J2Q5	AOA6P7J2Q5_9TELE	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYHELVDPAALTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	956
tr	AOA7N8YN60	AOA7N8YN60_9TELE	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYHELVDPAALTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	964
tr	AOA3P8N896	AOA3P8N896_ASTCA	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYHELVDPAALTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	955
tr	AOA3B4GL19	AOA3B4GL19_9CICH	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYHELVDPAALTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	955
tr	AOA6A5F6M3	AOA6A5F6M3_PERFL	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYHELVDPAALTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	956
tr	AOA3Q1FLK4	AOA3Q1FLK4_9TELE	MLNILVKEGFTNDQYHELVDPAALTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	956
tr	AOA4W6G9K4	AOA4W6G9K4_LATCA	MLNILVKEGFTNDQYHELVDPAALTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	956
tr	AOA3B4YTJ5	AOA3B4YTJ5_SERLL	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYHELVDPAALTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	956
tr	AOA665X3K2	AOA665X3K2_ECHNA	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYHELVDPAALTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	956
tr	AOA7J7RQ84	AOA7J7RQ84_RHIFE	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYQELAPASLTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	928
tr	AOA6P6D0R3	AOA6P6D0R3_PTEVA	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYQELAPASLTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	947
tr	AOA7J8H4F1	AOA7J8H4F1_ROUAE	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYQELAPASLTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	961
tr	AOA5F4D2S5	AOA5F4D2S5_CANLF	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYQELAPASLTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	990
tr	AOA2I3S482	AOA2I3S482_PANTR	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYQELAPSSLT	YVTRSENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	955
tr	AOA2K6CI58	AOA2K6CI58_MACNE	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYQELAPSSLT	YVTRSENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	955
tr	AOA834DIT3	AOA834DIT3_9CHIR	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYQELAPSSLT	YVTRSENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	955
tr	F62911	F62911_HORSE	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYQELAPSSLT	YVTRSENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	955
tr	AOA5G2RB90	AOA5G2RB90_PIG	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYQELAPSSLT	YVTRSENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	928
tr	AOA670JP16	AOA670JP16_PODMU	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYQELVDPASLTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	953
tr	AOA852LC41	AOA852LC41_UROIN	MLNILVKEGFTNDQYHELVDPAALTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	972
tr	F62FB6	F62FB6_ORNAN	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYQELADPASLTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	830
tr	AOA6P5LNS3	AOA6P5LNS3_PHACI	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYQELTEPTSLTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	956
tr	AOA4X2K1K8	AOA4X2K1K8_VOMUR	MLNIMVKEGFTNDQYQELTEPTSLTYETRA	ENSIFFEVDGPGYLAMILPASKEEG	KLLKRR	940
tr	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****

tr	AOA6Q2WNN8	AOA6Q2WNN8_ESOLU	VLYSKAANMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1070
tr	AOA673YLH4	AOA673YLH4_SALTR	VLYSKAANMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1076
tr	AOA4W5MAK2	AOA4W5MAK2_9TELE	VLYSKAANMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1076
tr	AOA6P6MI98	AOA6P6MI98_CARAU	VLYSKAANMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1075
tr	AOA498LK69	AOA498LK69_LABRO	VLYSKAANMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1051
tr	AOA3Q2YTT5	AOA3Q2YTT5_HIPCM	VLYSKAANMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1075
tr	M4A042	M4A042_XIPMA	VLYSKAANMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1076
tr	AOA6P8SZ0	AOA6P8SZ0_GYMAC	VLYSKAANMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1074
tr	AOA3Q2PG22	AOA3Q2PG22_FUNHE	VLYSKAANMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1076
tr	AOA6A4SMP2	AOA6A4SMP2_SCOMX	VLYSKAANMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1054
tr	AOA673CZR7	AOA673CZR7_9TELE	VLYSKAANMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1076
tr	AOA671YAK3	AOA671YAK3_SPAAU	VLYSKAANMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1076
tr	AOA6P7J2Q5	AOA6P7J2Q5_9TELE	VLYSKAANMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1076
tr	AOA7N8YN60	AOA7N8YN60_9TELE	VLYSKADNMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1084
tr	AOA3P8N896	AOA3P8N896_ASTCA	VLYSKAANMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1075
tr	AOA3B4GL19	AOA3B4GL19_9CICH	VLYSKAANMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1075
tr	AOA6A5F6M3	AOA6A5F6M3_PERFL	VLYSKAANMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1076
tr	AOA3Q1FLK4	AOA3Q1FLK4_9TELE	VLYSKAANMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1076
tr	AOA4W6G9K4	AOA4W6G9K4_LATCA	VLYSKAANMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1076
tr	AOA3B4YTJ5	AOA3B4YTJ5_SERLL	VLYSKAANMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1076
tr	AOA665X3K2	AOA665X3K2_ECHNA	VLYSKAANMPDAELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1076
tr	AOA7J7RQ84	AOA7J7RQ84_RHIFE	VLYSKAANMPDSELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1048
tr	AOA6P6D0R3	AOA6P6D0R3_PTEVA	VLYSKAANMPDSELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1067
tr	AOA7J8H4F1	AOA7J8H4F1_ROUAE	VLYSKAANMPDSELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1081
tr	AOA5F4D2S5	AOA5F4D2S5_CANLF	VLYSKAANMPDSELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1110
tr	AOA2I3S482	AOA2I3S482_PANTR	VLYSKAANMPDSELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1075
tr	AOA2K6CI58	AOA2K6CI58_MACNE	VLYSKAANMPDSELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1075
tr	AOA834DIT3	AOA834DIT3_9CHIR	VLYSKAANMPDSELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1075
tr	F62911	F62911_HORSE	VLYSKAANMPDSELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1075
tr	AOA5G2RB90	AOA5G2RB90_PIG	VLYSKAANMPDSELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1048
tr	AOA670JP16	AOA670JP16_PODMU	VLYSKAANMPDSELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1073
tr	AOA852LC41	AOA852LC41_UROIN	VLYSKAANMPDSELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1092
tr	F62FB6	F62FB6_ORNAN	VLYSKAANMPDSELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	950
tr	AOA6P5LNS3	AOA6P5LNS3_PHACI	VLYSRAANMPDSELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1076
tr	AOA4X2K1K8	AOA4X2K1K8_VOMUR	VLYSRAANMPDSELFELIENRSMRSRKL	EDYGEQKSTSI	STAKRLAEFLGDQMVKDAGLS	1060
tr	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****

tr	AOA6Q2WNN8	AOA6Q2WNN8_ESOLU	RYVISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKTPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1129
tr	AOA673YLH4	AOA673YLH4_SALTR	CRYIISRKPPEGTPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKMPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1135
tr	AOA4W5MAK2	AOA4W5MAK2_9TELE	CRYIISRKPPEGTPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKMPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1135
tr	AOA6P6MI98	AOA6P6MI98_CARAU	RYVISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKMPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1134
tr	AOA498LK69	AOA498LK69_LABRO	CRYVISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKMPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1110
tr	AOA3Q2YTT5	AOA3Q2YTT5_HIPCM	RYVISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKMPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1135
tr	M4A042	M4A042_XIPMA	CRYVISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKMPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1135
tr	AOA6P8SZ0	AOA6P8SZ0_GYMAC	RYVISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKMPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1133
tr	AOA3Q2PG22	AOA3Q2PG22_FUNHE	RYVISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKMPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1135
tr	AOA6A4SMP2	AOA6A4SMP2_SCOMX	RYVISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKMPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1113
tr	AOA673CZR7	AOA673CZR7_9TELE	RYVISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKMPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1136
tr	AOA671YAK3	AOA671YAK3_SPAAU	RYVISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKMPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1135
tr	AOA6P7J2Q5	AOA6P7J2Q5_9TELE	RYVISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKMPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1135
tr	AOA7N8YN60	AOA7N8YN60_9TELE	RYVISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKMPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1143
tr	AOA3P8N896	AOA3P8N896_ASTCA	RYVISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKMPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1134
tr	AOA3B4GL19	AOA3B4GL19_9CICH	RYVISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKMPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1134
tr	AOA6A5F6M3	AOA6A5F6M3_PERFL	RYVISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKMPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1135
tr	AOA3Q1FLK4	AOA3Q1FLK4_9TELE	RYVISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKMPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1135
tr	AOA4W6G9K4	AOA4W6G9K4_LATCA	RYVISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKMPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1135
tr	AOA3B4YTJ5	AOA3B4YTJ5_SERLL	RYVISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKMPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1135
tr	AOA665X3K2	AOA665X3K2_ECHNA	RYVISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVKKHFLRKWLKMPSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1135
tr	AOA7J7RQ84	AOA7J7RQ84_RHIFE	CRYIISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVRRHFLRKWLKSSSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1107
tr	AOA6P6D0R3	AOA6P6D0R3_PTEVA	CRYIISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVRRHFLRKWLKSSSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1126
tr	AOA7J8H4F1	AOA7J8H4F1_ROUAE	CRYIISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVRRHFLRKWLKSSSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1140
tr	AOA5F4D2S5	AOA5F4D2S5_CANLF	CRYIISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVRRHFLRKWLKSSSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1169
tr	AOA2I3S482	AOA2I3S482_PANTR	RYIISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVRRHFLRKWLKSSSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1134
tr	AOA2K6CI58	AOA2K6CI58_MACNE	CRYIISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVRRHFLRKWLKSSSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1134
tr	AOA834DIT3	AOA834DIT3_9CHIR	RYIISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVRRHFLRKWLKSSSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1134
tr	F62911	F62911_HORSE	CRYIISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVRRHFLRKWLKSSSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1134
tr	AOA5G2RB90	AOA5G2RB90_PIG	RYIISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVRRHFLRKWLKSSSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1107
tr	AOA670JP16	AOA670JP16_PODMU	CRYIISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVRRHFLRKWLKSSSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1132
tr	AOA852LC41	AOA852LC41_UROIN	CRYIISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVRRHFLRKWLKSSSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1151
tr	F62FB6	F62FB6_ORNAN	RYIISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVRRHFLRKWLKSSSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1009
tr	AOA6P5LNS3	AOA6P5LNS3_PHACI	CRYIISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVRRHFLRKWLKSSSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1135
tr	AOA4X2K1K8	AOA4X2K1K8_VOMUR	RYIISRKPPEGSPVTER	-AIPLAIFQAE	SSVRRHFLRKWLKSSSL	DIRSILDWYSYI	1119
tr	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	

				ZBM-CTD-Pol →	
tr A0A6Q2WNN8 A0A6Q2WNN8 ESOLU	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTA	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1724
tr A0A673YLH4 A0A673YLH4 SALTR	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTA	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1731
tr A0A4W5MAK2 A0A4W5MAK2 9TELE	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTA	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1729
tr A0A6P6MI98 A0A6P6MI98 CARAU	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTA	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1727
tr A0A498LK69 A0A498LK69 LABRO	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTA	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1723
tr A0A3Q2YTI5 A0A3Q2YTI5 HIPFCM	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTA	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1728
tr M4A042 M4A042 XIFMA	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTA	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1728
tr A0A6P8SZE0 A0A6P8SZE0 GYMCA	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTA	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1727
tr A0A3Q2PG22 A0A3Q2PG22 FUNHE	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTV	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1729
tr A0A6A4SMP2 A0A6A4SMP2 SCOMX	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTA	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1706
tr A0A673CZR7 A0A673CZR7 9TELE	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTA	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1729
tr A0A671YAK3 A0A671YAK3 SPAAU	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTA	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1723
tr A0A6P7J2Q5 A0A6P7J2Q5 9TELE	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTA	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1727
tr A0A7N8YN60 A0A7N8YN60 9TELE	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTA	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1736
tr A0A3P8N896 A0A3P8N896 ASTCA	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTS	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1727
tr A0A3B4GLI9 A0A3B4GLI9 9CICH	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTS	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1727
tr A0A6A5F6M3 A0A6A5F6M3 PERFL	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTA	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1728
tr A0A3Q1FLK4 A0A3Q1FLK4 9TELE	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTS	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1725
tr A0A4W6G9K4 A0A4W6G9K4 LATCA	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTA	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1728
tr A0A3B4YTJ5 A0A3B4YTJ5 SERLL	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTS	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1728
tr A0A665X3K2 A0A665X3K2 ECHNA	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTS	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1728
tr A0A7J7RQ84 A0A7J7RQ84 RHIFE	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTS	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1700
tr A0A6P6D0R3 A0A6P6D0R3 PTEVA	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTS	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1719
tr A0A7J8H4F1 A0A7J8H4F1 ROUAE	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTS	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1733
tr A0A5F4D2S5 A0A5F4D2S5 CANLF	GSDLFLARHLRKK	NNHLLWLSPTS	RPDLGGKEADD	SRLVMEADDRGSMENAQQ	1762
sp Q07864 DPOE1 HUMAN	GSDLFFARHLRKH	NNHLLWLSPTA	RPDLGGKEADD	NCLVMEFDDQATVEINSSG	1727
tr A0A2I3S482 A0A2I3S482 PANTR	GSDLFFARHLRKH	NNHLLWLSPTA	RPDLGGKEADD	NCLVMEFDDQATVEINSSG	1727
tr A0A2K6C158 A0A2K6C158 MACNE	GSDLFFARHLRKH	NNHLLWLSPTA	RPDLGGKEADD	NCLVMEFDDQATVEINSSG	1704
tr A0A834DIT3 A0A834DIT3 9CHIR	GSDLFFARHLRKH	NNHLLWLSPTC	RPDLGGKEADD	NCLVMEFDDQATVEINSSG	1726
tr F6Z911 F6Z911 HORSE	GSDLFFARHLRKH	NNHLLWLSPTS	RPDLGGKEADD	NCLVMEFDDQATVEINSSG	1727
tr A0A5G2RB90 A0A5G2RB90 FIG	GSDLFFARHLRKH	NNHLLWLSPTS	RPDLGGKEADD	NCLVMEFDDQATVEINSSG	1700
tr A0A670JP16 A0A670JP16 PODMU	GSDLFFARHLRKH	NNHLLWLSPTS	RPDLGGKEADD	NCLVMEFDDQATVEINSSG	1723
tr A0A852LC41 A0A852LC41 UROIN	GSDLFFARHLRKH	NNHLLWLSPTS	RPDLGGKEADD	NCLVMEFDDQATVEINSSG	1744
tr F6ZPB6 F6ZPB6 ORNAN	GSDLFFARHLRKH	NNHLLWLSPTS	RPDLGGKEADD	NCLVMEFDDQATVEINSSG	1602
tr A0A6P5LNS3 A0A6P5LNS3 PHACI	GSDLFFARHLRKH	NNHLLWLSPTS	RPDLGGKEADD	NCLVMEFDDQATVEINSSG	1728
tr A0A4X2K1K8 A0A4X2K1K8 VOMUR	GSDLFFARHLRKH	NNHLLWLSPTS	RPDLGGKEADD	NCLVMEFDDQATVEINSSG	1712
	*:***::**	:****:***	*****	.*:***::**	:***::**

				ZBM-CTD-Pol	
tr A0A6Q2WNN8 A0A6Q2WNN8 ESOLU	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1844
tr A0A673YLH4 A0A673YLH4 SALTR	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITRYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1850
tr A0A4W5MAK2 A0A4W5MAK2 9TELE	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITRYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1848
tr A0A6P6MI98 A0A6P6MI98 CARAU	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1846
tr A0A498LK69 A0A498LK69 LABRO	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1822
tr A0A3Q2YTI5 A0A3Q2YTI5 HIPFCM	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1847
tr M4A042 M4A042 XIFMA	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1847
tr A0A6P8SZE0 A0A6P8SZE0 GYMCA	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1846
tr A0A3Q2PG22 A0A3Q2PG22 FUNHE	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1848
tr A0A6A4SMP2 A0A6A4SMP2 SCOMX	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1825
tr A0A673CZR7 A0A673CZR7 9TELE	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1848
tr A0A671YAK3 A0A671YAK3 SPAAU	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1843
tr A0A6P7J2Q5 A0A6P7J2Q5 9TELE	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1846
tr A0A7N8YN60 A0A7N8YN60 9TELE	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1855
tr A0A3P8N896 A0A3P8N896 ASTCA	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1847
tr A0A3B4GLI9 A0A3B4GLI9 9CICH	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1847
tr A0A6A5F6M3 A0A6A5F6M3 PERFL	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1847
tr A0A3Q1FLK4 A0A3Q1FLK4 9TELE	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1844
tr A0A4W6G9K4 A0A4W6G9K4 LATCA	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1847
tr A0A3B4YTJ5 A0A3B4YTJ5 SERLL	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1847
tr A0A665X3K2 A0A665X3K2 ECHNA	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1847
tr A0A7J7RQ84 A0A7J7RQ84 RHIFE	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1819
tr A0A6P6D0R3 A0A6P6D0R3 PTEVA	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1838
tr A0A7J8H4F1 A0A7J8H4F1 ROUAE	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1852
tr A0A5F4D2S5 A0A5F4D2S5 CANLF	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1881
sp Q07864 DPOE1 HUMAN	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1846
tr A0A2I3S482 A0A2I3S482 PANTR	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1846
tr A0A2K6C158 A0A2K6C158 MACNE	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1823
tr A0A834DIT3 A0A834DIT3 9CHIR	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1845
tr F6Z911 F6Z911 HORSE	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1846
tr A0A5G2RB90 A0A5G2RB90 FIG	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1819
tr A0A670JP16 A0A670JP16 PODMU	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1842
tr A0A852LC41 A0A852LC41 UROIN	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1863
tr F6ZPB6 F6ZPB6 ORNAN	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1721
tr A0A6P5LNS3 A0A6P5LNS3 PHACI	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1847
tr A0A4X2K1K8 A0A4X2K1K8 VOMUR	CSNTEF	RILKSMVVGWVRE	ITQYHN	VYADNVQMHFYRWLRSPS	1831
	*:***::**	:****:***	*****	.*:***::**	:***::**

				ZBM-CTD-Pol	
tr A0A6Q2WNN8 A0A6Q2WNN8 ESOLU	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1904
tr A0A673YLH4 A0A673YLH4 SALTR	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1910
tr A0A4W5MAK2 A0A4W5MAK2 9TELE	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1908
tr A0A6P6MI98 A0A6P6MI98 CARAU	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1906
tr A0A498LK69 A0A498LK69 LABRO	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1882
tr A0A3Q2YTI5 A0A3Q2YTI5 HIPFCM	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1907
tr M4A042 M4A042 XIFMA	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1905
tr A0A6P8SZE0 A0A6P8SZE0 GYMCA	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1906
tr A0A3Q2PG22 A0A3Q2PG22 FUNHE	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1908
tr A0A6A4SMP2 A0A6A4SMP2 SCOMX	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1905
tr A0A673CZR7 A0A673CZR7 9TELE	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1888
tr A0A671YAK3 A0A671YAK3 SPAAU	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1903
tr A0A6P7J2Q5 A0A6P7J2Q5 9TELE	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1906
tr A0A7N8YN60 A0A7N8YN60 9TELE	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1915
tr A0A3P8N896 A0A3P8N896 ASTCA	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1907
tr A0A3B4GLI9 A0A3B4GLI9 9CICH	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1907
tr A0A6A5F6M3 A0A6A5F6M3 PERFL	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1907
tr A0A3Q1FLK4 A0A3Q1FLK4 9TELE	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1904
tr A0A4W6G9K4 A0A4W6G9K4 LATCA	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1907
tr A0A3B4YTJ5 A0A3B4YTJ5 SERLL	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1907
tr A0A665X3K2 A0A665X3K2 ECHNA	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1907
tr A0A7J7RQ84 A0A7J7RQ84 RHIFE	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1879
tr A0A6P6D0R3 A0A6P6D0R3 PTEVA	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1898
tr A0A7J8H4F1 A0A7J8H4F1 ROUAE	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1912
tr A0A5F4D2S5 A0A5F4D2S5 CANLF	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1941
sp Q07864 DPOE1 HUMAN	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1906
tr A0A2I3S482 A0A2I3S482 PANTR	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1906
tr A0A2K6C158 A0A2K6C158 MACNE	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1883
tr A0A834DIT3 A0A834DIT3 9CHIR	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1905
tr F6Z911 F6Z911 HORSE	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1906
tr A0A5G2RB90 A0A5G2RB90 FIG	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1879
tr A0A670JP16 A0A670JP16 PODMU	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1902
tr A0A852LC41 A0A852LC41 UROIN	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1923
tr F6ZPB6 F6ZPB6 ORNAN	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1781
tr A0A6P5LNS3 A0A6P5LNS3 PHACI	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1907
tr A0A4X2K1K8 A0A4X2K1K8 VOMUR	KVFLQLVAE	FPKRLG	STVVYGNFNRI	ILCTKKRR	1891
	*:***::**	:****:***	*****	.*:***::**	:***::**

tr A0A6Q2WNN8 A0A6Q2WNN8_ESOLU	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PSNHGGVVKKLPSSVLYGHTAQK--KK--GTGDEEGSEDEDEA---DG	1957
tr A0A673YLH4 A0A673YLH4_SALTR	FSRWCFEFLMWM	LANYGGVVKKLPSSVLYGHPVSSSAKY---EDGEEEGSEDEDEEA---DE	1965
tr A0A4W5MAK2 A0A4W5MAK2_9TELE	FSRWCFEFLMWM	LANYGGVVKKLPSSVLYGHPVSSS---DGDEEGSEDEDEEA---D-	1958
tr A0A6F6MI98 A0A6F6MI98_CARAU	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PANCCGGVVKKLPSSVLYGHPANEKKNKNDGEE-EDGSEDEE---DDEEN	1963
tr A0A498LK69 A0A498LK69_LABRO	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PANCCGGVVKKLPSSVLYGHPANEKKNKNDGEE-EDGSEDEE---DDEEN	1939
tr A0A3Q2YTI5 A0A3Q2YTI5_HIPCM	FSCQWFLMWM	PANNGGVVKKLPSSVLYGHPANVQVOT-----DEDEEEDEN	1952
tr M4A042 M4A042_XIPMA	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PSNYGGVVKKLPSSVLYGHPGAKQKRRKQGEDEEGSEDEDE---DD	1951
tr A0A6P8SZE0 A0A6P8SZE0_GYMAC	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PSNYGGVVKKLPSSVLYGHPGAKQKRRKQGEDEEGSEDEDE---DP	1962
tr A0A3Q2PG22 A0A3Q2PG22_FUNHE	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PANYGGVVKKLPSSVLYGHPGAKQKRRKQGEDEEGSEDEDE---DEAD	1959
tr A0A6A4SMP2 A0A6A4SMP2_SCOMX	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PANYGGVVKKLPSSVLYGHPGAKQKRRKQGEDEEGSEDEDE---DEAN	1941
tr A0A673CZR7 A0A673CZR7_9TELE	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PANYGGVVKKLPSSVLYGHPGAKQKRRKQGEDEEGSEDEDEDEAD	1964
tr A0A671YAK3 A0A671YAK3_SPAAU	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PANCCGGVVKKLPSSR---AKQKKNRQGEDEEGSEDEDEE---A	1953
tr A0A6P7J2Q5 A0A6P7J2Q5_9TELE	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PANYGGVVKKLPSSVLYGHPGAKQKRRKQGEDEEGSEDEDEDE---N	1962
tr A0A7N8YN60 A0A7N8YN60_9TELE	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PSNYGGVVKKLPSSVLYGHPGAKQKRRKQGEDEEGSEDEDEDE---DEAD	1973
tr A0A3P8N896 A0A3P8N896_ASTCA	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PANYGGVVKKLPSSVLYGHPGAKQKRRKQGEDEEGSEDEDEDE---DEEN	1958
tr A0A3B4GLI9 A0A3B4GLI9_9CICH	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PANYGGVVKKLPSSVLYGHPGAKQKRRKQGEDEEGSEDEDEDE---DEEN	1958
tr A0A6A5F6M3 A0A6A5F6M3_PERFL	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PANYGGVVKKLPSSVLYGHPGAKQKRRKQGEDEEGSEDEDEDE---DEAV	1965
tr A0A3Q1FLK4 A0A3Q1FLK4_9TELE	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PANYGGVVKKLPSSVLYGHPGAKQKRRKQGEDEEGSEDEDEDE---EED	1960
tr A0A4W6G9K4 A0A4W6G9K4_LATCA	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PANYGGVVKKLPSSVLYGHPGAKQKRRKRE--GDEGSDSE--EDEDAG	1963
tr A0A3B4YTJ5 A0A3B4YTJ5_SERLL	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PANYGGVVKKLPSSVLYGHPGAKQKRRKQGEDEEGSEDEDEDE---DEAD	1965
tr A0A665X3K2 A0A665X3K2_ECHNA	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PANHGGVVKKLPSSVLYGHPGAKQKRRKQGEDEEGSEDEDEDEDEAD	1967
tr A0A7J7RQ84 A0A7J7RQ84_RHIFE	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PSNYGGIKGVSSGTHCGQDSPKKGGSTQDDE---DDEDD-----	1928
tr A0A6P6D0R3 A0A6P6D0R3_PTEVA	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PSNYGGIKGVSSGTHCGQDSPKKGGSTQDDE---DDEDD-----	1947
tr A0A7J8H4F1 A0A7J8H4F1_ROUAE	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PSNYGGIKGVSSVHCQDQDQNEGKQDDEDE---GD---G-----	1959
tr A0A5F4D2S5 A0A5F4D2S5_CANLF	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PSNYGGIKGVSSVHYGQDQDQNEGKQDDEDE---EEDDEE---EE---	1992
sp Q07864 DPOE1_HUMAN	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PSNYGGIKGVSSRTHCGQDQDQNEGKQDDEDE---ENEDD---EEDR---	1959
tr A0A2I3S482 A0A2I3S482_PANTR	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PSNYGGIKGVSSRTHCGQDQDQNEGKQDDEDE---ENEDD---EEDR---	1959
tr A0A2K6C158 A0A2K6C158_MACNE	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PSNYGGIKGVSSRTHCGQDQDQNEGKQDDEDE---ENEDD---EEDR---	1936
tr A0A834DIT3 A0A834DIT3_9CHIR	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PSNYGGIKGVSSRTHCGQDQDQNEGKQDDEDE---EEDDEE---EEDPFG	1960
tr F62911 F62911_HORSE	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PCNYGGIKGVSSVTHCGQDQDQNEGKQDDEDE---EE---E---EEDPFG	1959
tr A0A5G2RB90 A0A5G2RB90_PIG	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PSNYGGIKGVSSRTHCGQDQDQNEGKQDDEDE---AE---E---E---E	2168
tr A0A670JP16 A0A670JP16_PODMU	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PSNYGGIKGVSSVTHCGQDQDQNEGKQDDEDE---EED---E---E	1950
tr A0A852LC41 A0A852LC41_UROIN	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PSNYGGIKGVSSRTHCGQDQDQNEGKQDDEDE---DSEDE---E---E	1974
tr F62FB6 F62FB6_ORNAN	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PSNYGGIKGVSSVTHCGQDQDQNEGKQDDEDE---GSDDE---EED---E	1834
tr A0A6P5LNS3 A0A6P5LNS3_PHACI	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PANYGGIKGVSSRTHCGQDQDQNEGKQDDEDE---EEDDEE---EED---E	1961
tr A0A4X2K1K8 A0A4X2K1K8_VOMUR	FSRWCFEFLMWM	PANYGGIKGVSSVTHCGQDQDQNEGKQDDEDE---EEDDEE---EED---E	1940

CTD-Pol

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tr A0A4W5MAK2 A0A4W5MAK2_9TELE	LVDVGFSEDAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2186
tr A0A6F6MI98 A0A6F6MI98_CARAU	LVDVGFSEDAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2192
tr A0A498LK69 A0A498LK69_LABRO	LVDVGFSEDAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2168
tr A0A3Q2YTI5 A0A3Q2YTI5_HIPCM	LVDVGFSEEAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2181
tr M4A042 M4A042_XIPMA	LVDVGFSEEAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPTVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2180
tr A0A6P8SZE0 A0A6P8SZE0_GYMAC	LVDVGFSEEAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2191
tr A0A3Q2PG22 A0A3Q2PG22_FUNHE	LVDVGFSEEAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2016
tr A0A6A4SMP2 A0A6A4SMP2_SCOMX	LVDVGFSEEAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2170
tr A0A673CZR7 A0A673CZR7_9TELE	LVDVGFSEEAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSMAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2193
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tr A0A6P7J2Q5 A0A6P7J2Q5_9TELE	LVDVGFSEDAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSMAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2191
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tr A0A3P8N896 A0A3P8N896_ASTCA	LVDVGFSEDAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2190
tr A0A3B4GLI9 A0A3B4GLI9_9CICH	LVDVGFSEDAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2015
tr A0A6A5F6M3 A0A6A5F6M3_PERFL	LVDVGFSEEAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2194
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tr A0A4W6G9K4 A0A4W6G9K4_LATCA	LVDVGFSEDAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2195
tr A0A3B4YTJ5 A0A3B4YTJ5_SERLL	LVDVGFSEDAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2194
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tr A0A7J7RQ84 A0A7J7RQ84_RHIFE	LVDVGFSEEAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2157
tr A0A6P6D0R3 A0A6P6D0R3_PTEVA	LVDVGFSEEAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2184
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tr A0A2I3S482 A0A2I3S482_PANTR	LVDVGFSEEAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2188
tr A0A2K6C158 A0A2K6C158_MACNE	LVDVGFSEEAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2165
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tr A0A5G2RB90 A0A5G2RB90_PIG	LVDVGFSEEAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2159
tr A0A670JP16 A0A670JP16_PODMU	LVDVGFSEEAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2179
tr F62FB6 F62FB6_ORNAN	LVDVGFSEEAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2061
tr A0A6P5LNS3 A0A6P5LNS3_PHACI	LVDVGFSEEAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2190
tr A0A4X2K1K8 A0A4X2K1K8_VOMUR	LVDVGFSEEAQFRDPCNSYILPEVICHQCNFCRDLLELCK---DPSVAQDGSVLPQWFC3	2169

CysA

tr A0A6Q2WNN8 A0A6Q2WNN8_ESOLU	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2246
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tr A0A4W5MAK2 A0A4W5MAK2_9TELE	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2246
tr A0A6F6MI98 A0A6F6MI98_CARAU	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2252
tr A0A498LK69 A0A498LK69_LABRO	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2199
tr A0A3Q2YTI5 A0A3Q2YTI5_HIPCM	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2241
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tr A0A3Q2PG22 A0A3Q2PG22_FUNHE	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2201
tr A0A6A4SMP2 A0A6A4SMP2_SCOMX	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2242
tr A0A673CZR7 A0A673CZR7_9TELE	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2251
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tr A0A6P7J2Q5 A0A6P7J2Q5_9TELE	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2252
tr A0A7N8YN60 A0A7N8YN60_9TELE	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2036
tr A0A3P8N896 A0A3P8N896_ASTCA	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2036
tr A0A3B4GLI9 A0A3B4GLI9_9CICH	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2015
tr A0A6A5F6M3 A0A6A5F6M3_PERFL	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2010
tr A0A3Q1FLK4 A0A3Q1FLK4_9TELE	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2255
tr A0A4W6G9K4 A0A4W6G9K4_LATCA	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2254
tr A0A3B4YTJ5 A0A3B4YTJ5_SERLL	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2256
tr A0A665X3K2 A0A665X3K2_ECHNA	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2257
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tr A0A6P6D0R3 A0A6P6D0R3_PTEVA	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2244
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tr A0A2I3S482 A0A2I3S482_PANTR	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2248
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tr A0A834DIT3 A0A834DIT3_9CHIR	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2249
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tr F62FB6 F62FB6_ORNAN	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2251
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tr A0A4X2K1K8 A0A4X2K1K8_VOMUR	NCDQAYETESIEMALVEALQKLLMSYTLQDLVCPKRGVKEANMPLCSAGDFELTFTT	2229

CysA

4Fe-4S

//End of ε pol sequences from animal sources

tr A0A6Q2WWN8 A0A6Q2WWN8_ESOLU	AAHYNMNFLEETIDWLLVMSPQISQAARH--	2288
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tr A0A4W5MAK2 A0A4W5MAK2_9TELE	AAHYNMNFLEETIDWLLVMSPQISQSR---	2286
tr A0A6P6MI98 A0A6P6MI98_CARAU	AAHYNMNFLEETIDWVLSMNA-----	2286
tr A0A498LK69 A0A498LK69_LABRO	AAHYNMNFLEETIDWVLSMNA-----	2232
tr A0A3Q2YTI5 A0A3Q2YTI5_HIPCM	ASHYNMSFLKETIDWLMVMSFPQISQSAS--	2282
tr M4A042 M4A042_XIPMA	ASHYNMRFLEETIDWLLVMSFPQISQSRH--	2281
tr A0A6P8SZE0 A0A6P8SZE0_GYMAC	ASHYSMSYLGETIDWLLVMSPQISQSAL--	2292
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tr A0A6A4SMP2 A0A6A4SMP2_SCOMX	ASHYNMSFLEETIDWLLVMSPHVGQSIH--	2236
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tr A0A671YAK3 A0A671YAK3_SPAAU	ASHYSMSFLEETIDWLVVMSPHINQSAR--	2283
tr A0A6P7J2Q5 A0A6P7J2Q5_9TELE	ASHYNMTFLEETIDWLLMSFPQISQSAR--	2292
tr A0A7N8YN60 A0A7N8YN60_9TELE	ASHYNMRFLEETIDWLLVMSPQISQSAH--	2303
tr A0A3P8N896 A0A3P8N896_ASTCA	-----	2036
tr A0A3B4GLI9 A0A3B4GLI9_9CICH	-----	2015
tr A0A6A5F6M3 A0A6A5F6M3_PERFL	ASHYKMSFLDETLDWLLVMSPQISQNAH--	2295
tr A0A3Q1FLK4 A0A3Q1FLK4_9TELE	-----	2010
tr A0A4W6G9K4 A0A4W6G9K4_LATCA	ASHYSMSFLEETIDWLLVMSPQISQSAR--	2296
tr A0A3B4YTJ5 A0A3B4YTJ5_SERLL	ASHYNMSFLEETIDWLLAMSPQISQSAH--	2295
tr A0A665X3K2 A0A665X3K2_ECHNA	ASHYNMSFLEETIDLLAMSPQISQTAH--	2297
tr A0A7J7RQ84 A0A7J7RQ84_RHIFE	AQHYGMSYLMETLEWLLKPNPQLGH-----	2255
tr A0A6P6D0R3 A0A6P6D0R3_PTEVA	AQHCMSYLMETLEWLLQKNPQLGH-----	2282
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tr A0A5F4D2S5 A0A5F4D2S5_CANLF	AQHYGMSYLTETLEWLLQKNPQLGH-----	2319
sp Q07864 DPOE1_HUMAN	AQHYGMSYLTETLEWLLQKNPQLGH-----	2286
tr A0A2I3S482 A0A2I3S482_PANTR	AQHYGMSYLTETLEWLLQKNPQLGR-----	2286
tr A0A2K6CI58 A0A2K6CI58_MACNE	AQHYGMSYLTETLEWLLQKNPQQRGR-----	2263
tr A0A834DIT3 A0A834DIT3_9CHIR	AQHYGMSYLMETLEWLLQKNPQLSH-----	2287
tr F6Z911 F6Z911_HORSE	AQHYGMSYLMESLEWLLQKNPQLGH-----	2286
tr A0A5G2RB90 A0A5G2RB90_PIG	AQHYGMSYLTETLEWLLQKNPQLGH-----	2257
tr A0A670JP16 A0A670JP16_PODMU	ARHYNMDYLLLENIKWLLQMNPLQLL-----	2277
tr A0A852LC41 A0A852LC41_UROIN	ARHYSMALHLEETIEWLLSTNPLQLRP-----	2300
tr F6ZFB6 F6ZFB6_ORNAN	AQHYAMSYLEETIEWLLQMNPLQLR-----	2159
tr A0A6P5LNS3 A0A6P5LNS3_PHACI	ARHYGMTYLTETIEWLLQMNPLQLAN-----	2288
tr A0A4X2K1K8 A0A4X2K1K8_VOMUR	ARHYGMTYLTETIEWLLQMNPLQLAN-----	2267

A0A6Q2WWN8_ESOLU, <i>Esox lucius</i>	A0A673YLH4_SALTR, <i>Salmo trutta</i>
A0A4W5MAK2_9TELE, <i>Hucho hucho</i>	A0A6P6MI98_CARAU, <i>Carassius auratus</i>
A0A498LK69_LABRO, <i>Labeo rohita</i>	A0A3Q2YTI5_HIPCM, <i>Hippocampus comes</i>
M4A042_XIPMA, <i>Xiphophorus maculatus</i>	A0A6P8SZE0_GYMAC, <i>Gymnodraco acuticeps</i>
A0A3Q2PG22_FUNHE, <i>Fundulus heteroclitus</i>	A0A6A4SMP2_SCOMX, <i>Scophthalmus maximus</i>
A0A673CZR7_9TELE, <i>Sphaeramia orbicularis</i>	A0A671YAK3_SPAAU, <i>Sparus aurata</i>
A0A6P7J2Q5_9TELE, <i>Parambassis ranga</i>	A0A7N8YN60_9TELE, <i>Mastacembelus armatus</i>
A0A3P8N896_ASTCA, <i>Astatotilapia calliptera</i>	A0A3B4GLI9_9CICH, <i>Pundamilia nyererei</i>
A0A6A5F6M3_PERFL, <i>Perca fluviatilis</i>	A0A3Q1FLK4_9TELE, <i>Acanthochromis polyacanthus</i>
A0A4W6G9K4_LATCA, <i>Lates calcarifer</i>	A0A3B4YTJ5_SERLL, <i>Seriola lalandi dorsalis</i>
A0A665X3K2_ECHNA, <i>Echeneis naucrates</i>	A0A7J7RQ84_RHIFE, <i>Rhinolophus ferrumequinum</i>
A0A6P6D0R3_PTEVA, <i>Pteropus vampyrus</i>	A0A7J8H4F1_ROUAE, <i>Rousettus aegyptiacus</i>
A0A5F4D2S5_CANLF, <i>Canis lupus familiaris</i>	Q07864 DPOE1_HUMAN, <i>Homo sapiens</i>
A0A2I3S482_PANTR, <i>Pan troglodytes</i>	A0A2K6CI58_MACNE, <i>Macaca nemestrina</i>
A0A834DIT3_9CHIR, <i>Phyllostomus discolor</i>	F6Z911_HORSE, <i>Equus caballus</i>
A0A5G2RB90_PIG, <i>Sus scrofa</i>	A0A670JP16_PODMU, <i>Podarcis muralis</i>
A0A852LC41_UROIN, <i>Urocolius indicus</i>	F6ZFB6_ORNAN, <i>Ornithorhynchus anatinus</i>
A0A6P5LNS3_PHACI, <i>Phascolarctos cinereus</i>	A0A4X2K1K8_VOMUR, <i>Vombatus ursinus</i>

Figure 4 MSA of ε DNA polymerases from various animal sources

3.2. 'Mix and Match' MSA analysis of the DNA pols ε from yeasts, higher fungi, plants and animals

Figure 5 shows the 'Mix and Match' MSA of the ε pols from all the four eukaryotic sources, viz. yeasts, higher fungi, plants and animals (only the required regions for the discussions are shown). *S. cerevisiae*, *Aspergillus niger*, *A. thaliana* and human sequences are used as the standards and highlighted. All the major domains (NTD, PR Exo, Pol, Linker and CTD) are indicated tentatively with arrow marks. The NTDs show many gaps in the alignment, but with a small number of conserved peptides. Strikingly, a highly conserved dodecapeptide is found in this region. The NTD is followed by a highly conserved PR exo domain. The proposed PR exonuclease active site amino acids are completely conserved in all (highlighted) and it belongs to the DEDD-superfamily with an invariant Y as a proton acceptor. The presence of a typical -DEDD-superfamily exonuclease active site in all ε pols is in close agreement with the other DdDps [8]. An invariant, characteristic motif -SYLPQ/VGS- (highlighted in yellow) is found within the PR exo domain in the ε pols of all eukaryotes. This sequence is somewhat similar to the characteristic -SLYPS- motif reported in the other two replicative pols, α and δ [2] and, in general, in all the B-family pols. In all these pols, viz. ε, δ and α, this motif is implicated in dNTP-binding.

The PR exo domain is followed by the pol domain and is also highly conserved in all. Interestingly, the template-binding pair (-YG-), catalytic amino acid (K) and dNTP selection amino acid (Q) are completely conserved in all (highlighted in yellow) and are in close agreement with other DdDps and DdRps [6, 21]. The ε pol's active site amino acids are found within highly conserved large peptides. The pol domain also contains the completely conserved-DxD- type catalytic Mg²⁺ site and is in close agreement with other DNA pols. A unique ZBM that is conserved within the pol domain in all ε pols (highlighted) is suggested to play a role in linking redox status of cells to replication. The pol domain is followed by a linker region which connects the pol to the CTD. The linker region contains a highly conserved NLS-like motif in all pols ε (highlighted). The linker region is not conserved much. The CTD possesses two invariant ZBMs and one of them binds to the 4Fe-4S cluster (highlighted in orange) and a -DxD- type metal-binding motif is found within the first ZBM. The second pol and PR exo active sites do not align in all. Interestingly, the catalytic amino acid K, pairs with -C- as -KC- in plant and animal enzymes, but with -V- as -KV- in yeasts and higher fungal enzymes.

CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) 'Mix and Match' MSA of all the four eukaryotic ε DNA pols (from yeasts, higher fungi, plants and animals)

tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM	ILAGK-----REQRLODCLDSLIDLREYDVPYHVR	FAVDKDVRSGQWY	218
sp P4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	ILAGK-----REQRQDCLDSIVDLREYDVPYHVR	FAIDNDVRSQGQWY	218
tr D7KI06 D7KI06_ARALL	ILAGK-----REQRQDCLDSIVDLREYDVPYHVR	FAIDNDVRSQGQWY	218
tr A0A8I6WFC8 A0A8I6WFC8_HORVV	IYGVK-----RVERPQDYINCIIDLREYDVPYHVR	FAIDNDVRSQGQWY	242
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6_AEGTS	IYGVK-----RVERPQDYINCIIDLREYDVPYHVR	FAIDNDVRSQGQWY	182
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT	IYGVK-----RVERPQDYINCIIDLREYDVPYHVR	FAIDNDVRSQGQWY	237
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE	IHGVK-----RVERPQDYINYIIDLREYDVPYHVR	FAIDNDVRSQGQWY	234
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357_9POAL	IHGVK-----RVERPQDYINYIIDLREYDVPYHVR	FAIDNDVRSQGQWY	228
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL	IHGVK-----RVERPQDYINYIIDLREYDVPYHVR	FAIDNDVRSQGQWY	233
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62_SETIT	IHGVK-----RVERPQDYINYIIDLREYDVPYHVR	FAIDNDVRSQGQWY	237
tr A0A7I8KHB8 A0A7I8KHB8_SPIIN	IFTGK-----SKERPQDFIDCVLREYDVPYHVR	FAIDNDVRSQGQWY	219
tr A0A6I9QIG1 A0A6I9QIG1_ELAGV	IYNGK-----SKERPQDYIDCVLREYDVPYHVR	FAIDNDVRSQGQWY	217
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2_PHODC	MYNGK-----SKERPQDYIDCVLREYDVPYHVR	FAIDNDVRSQGQWY	217
tr A0A9Q0FIP5 A0A9Q0FIP5_9ROSI	ILSGKR--QVFHDMHELTHYFLEQRLODCLDSIVDLREYDVPYHVR	FAIDNDVRSQGQWY	234
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	LLTGKS-----REQRQDCLDSIVDLREYDVPYHVR	FAIDNDVRSQGQWY	220
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034_TRIWF	ILTGK-----REQRQDCLDSIVDLREYDVPYHVR	FAIDNDVRSQGQWY	219
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976_FAGSY	FDISV-----ENKGPQDFIDCVLREYDVPYHVR	FAIDNDVRSQGQWY	238
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6_QUELO	I IAGK-----REQRQDCLDSIVDLREYDVPYHVR	FAIDNDVRSQGQWY	218
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tr A0A6P7J2Q5 A0A6P7J2Q5_9TELE	MLSSALSGGTV--ASA--DEDSISKISIDQLDNIVDMREYDVPYHVR	LSIDLKIHVAHWY	245
tr A0A6P8SZE0 A0A6P8SZE0_GYMAC	MLSSALSGGNV--NTA--EEDGPKSRISDQLDNIVDMREYDVPYHVR	LSIDLKIHVAHWY	243
tr A0A8J0QX44 A0A8J0QX44_XENTR	MLSSALTGNM--GA--EEEGPSKKISDQMDNIVDMREYDVPYHVR	LSIDLKIHVAHWY	242
tr A0A4X2K1K8 A0A4X2K1K8_VOMUR	MLSSALMGGSV--TT--DEEGSKKIADQLDNIVDMREYDVPYHVR	LSIDLKIHVAHWY	229
tr A0A5F4D2S5 A0A5F4D2S5_CANLF	MLSSVLQGGSV--VI--DEEASAKKVTQDLDNIVDMREYDVPYHVR	LSIDLKIHVAHWY	279
tr A0A7J7RQ84 A0A7J7RQ84_RHIFE	MLSSVLQGGSV--IL--DEEASAKKADQLDNIVDMREYDVPYHVR	LSIDLKIHVAHWY	217
tr A0A6P6D0R3 A0A6P6D0R3_PTEVA	MLSSVLQGGGA--II--DEEETSKKIADQLDNIVDMREYDVPYHVR	LSIDLKIHVAHWY	236
tr A0A2K6C1S8 A0A2K6C1S8_MACNE	LLSSVLQGGV--IT--DEEETSKKIADQLDNIVDMREYDVPYHVR	LSIDLKIHVAHWY	244
tr F6QAQ1 F6QAQ1_MACMU	LLSSVLQGGV--IT--DEEETSKKIADQLDNIVDMREYDVPYHVR	LSIDLKIHVAHWY	246
tr G3RQP2 G3RQP2_GORGO	LLSSVLQGGV--IT--DEEETSKKIADQLDNIVDMREYDVPYHVR	LSIDLKIHVAHWY	223
sp Q07864 DPOE1_HUMAN	LLSSVLQGGV--IT--DEEETSKKIADQLDNIVDMREYDVPYHVR	LSIDLKIHVAHWY	244
tr A0A2I3S482 A0A2I3S482_PANTR	LLSSVLQGGV--IT--DEEETSKKIADQLDNIVDMREYDVPYHVR	LSIDLKIHVAHWY	244
tr F6Z911 F6Z911_HORSE	MLSSVLQGGSV--II--DEEETSKKMDQLDNIVDMREYDVPYHVR	LSIDLKIHVAHWY	244
tr A0A5G2RB90 A0A5G2RB90_PIG	MLSSVLQGGSV--VM--DEEETSKKIADQLDNIVDMREYDVPYHVR	LSIDLKIHVAHWY	217
tr A0A420PL83 A0A420PL83_FUSOX	---NGDFDLFDDSRD--DDRNMTALSDFIIVDIREYDVPYHVR	VMIDLDIRAGKQWY	222
tr A0A1V6PGE7 A0A1V6PGE7_PENDC	MSSATASFDLFDDEII--NEQRPN--GNLQASDFIIVDIREYDVPYHVR	VCIDKDIRIGKQWY	257
tr A0A0G4NU82 A0A0G4NU82_PENCA	MTSATAGIDLFDDEII--NEQRPN--GNLQASDFIIVDIREYDVPYHVR	VCIDKDIRIGKQWY	257
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tr A0A167WJ50 A0A167WJ50_PENCH	MTSATAGIDLFDDEII--NEQRPN--GNLQASDFIIVDIREYDVPYHVR	VCIDKDIRIGKQWY	257
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tr A0A401L0U3 A0A401L0U3_ASPAW	ISSANAGFDLFDDELI--NESRPN--ATMNASDFIIVDIREYDVPYHVR	VAIDKDIRIGKQWY	257
tr A0A317VH96 A0A317VH96_ASPCC	ISSANAGFDLFDDELI--NESRPN--ATMNASDFIIVDIREYDVPYHVR	VAIDKDIRIGKQWY	253
tr A0A117E1M7 A0A117E1M7_ASPNG	ISSANAGFDLFDDELI--NESRPN--ATMNASDFIIVDIREYDVPYHVR	VAIDKDIRIGKQWY	257
tr A0A1D8PTD0 A0A1D8PTD0_CANAL	KEI-----ETIMDPSVYIIDIREYDVPYHVR	VSIDRNVRSQGQWY	263
tr C5M3R9 C5M3R9_CANTT	KDV-----DSSSDPSTYIIDIREYDVPYHVR	VSIDKQLRVQKQWY	258
sp Q6FNY7 DPOE_CANGA	SNISNGNGLSSNVNR--FASSVQDKDAKQYIEDIREYDVPYHVR	VSIDKDIRVQKQWY	265
sp P21951 DPOE_YEAST	AAN-----GSEKVDAKHLIEDIREYDVPYHVR	VSIDKDIRVQKQWY	205
tr A0A7H9HLU1 A0A7H9HLU1_9SACH	QGA-----GNSFRDAKSLIEVREYDVPYHVR	VSIDKNIRVQKQWY	255
sp Q6CUS7 DPOE_KLULA	GSD-----YSTRDVKTLEDIREYDVPYHVR	VSIDKNIRVQKQWY	182
sp Q752B8 DPOE_ASHGO	NDT-----TNRDRAKMLIIDIREYDVPYHVR	VCIDKDIRVQKQWY	179

	← NTD →	PR Exo →	
tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM	NVSISSST-D-VLEKRTDILQR	AEVRVCAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAEYDQIMMISYMDVGG	276
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	NVSISSST-D-VLEKRTDILQR	AEVRVCAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAEYDQIMMISYMDVGG	276
tr D7KI06 D7KI06_ARALL	NVSISSST-D-VLEKRTDILQR	AEVRVCAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAEYDQIMMISYMDVGG	276
tr A0A8I6WFC8 A0A8I6WFC8_HORVV	NVSVSGSD-VLLQRREDDLQR	AEVHVCAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAEYDQIMMISYMDVGG	300
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tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357_9POAL	NVSVSGSD-VLLQRREDDLQR	AEVHVCAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAEYDQIMMISYMDVGG	286
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL	NVSVSGSD-VLLQRREDDLQR	AEVHVCAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAEYDQIMMISYMDVGG	291
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62_SETIT	NVSVSGSD-VLLQRREDDLQR	AEVHVCAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAEYDQIMMISYMDVGG	295
tr A0A7I8KHB8 A0A7I8KHB8_SPIIN	DVSISSGIN-VLLQKRNDDLQR	AEVHVCAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAEYDQIMMISYMDVGG	277
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tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2_PHODC	DINVSSSG-ILLQRREDDLQR	AEVHVCAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAEYDQIMMISYMDVGG	275
tr A0A9Q0FIP5 A0A9Q0FIP5_9ROSI	DVSVSSTG-VLMKRRDILLQR	AEVHVCAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAEYDQIMMISYMDVGG	292
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tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976_FAGSY	DVSVSSTG-LMLKRRDILLQR	AEVHVCAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAEYDQIMMISYMDVGG	296
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6_QUELO	DVSVSSTG-LMLKRRDILLQR	AEVHVCAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAEYDQIMMISYMDVGG	276
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tr A0A8C7Q9V4 A0A8C7Q9V4_ONCMY	NVRYRGSAYPPEIILRSDLVER	PDPVVLAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAETDQIMMISYMDVGG	303
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tr A0A8J0QX44 A0A8J0QX44_XENTR	NVRYRGSAYPPEIILRSDLVER	PDPVVLAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAETDQIMMISYMDVGG	303
tr A0A4X2K1K8 A0A4X2K1K8_VOMUR	NVRYRGSAYPPEIILRSDLVER	PDPVVLAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAETDQIMMISYMDVGG	389
tr A0A5F4D2S5 A0A5F4D2S5_CANLF	NVRYRGSAYPPEIILRSDLVER	PDPVVLAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAETDQIMMISYMDVGG	299
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tr A0A6P6D0R3 A0A6P6D0R3_PTEVA	NVRYRGSAYPPEIILRSDLVER	PDPVVLAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAETDQIMMISYMDVGG	296
tr A0A2K6C158 A0A2K6C158_MACNE	NVRYRGSAYPPEIILRSDLVER	PDPVVLAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAETDQIMMISYMDVGG	304
tr F6QAQ1 F6QAQ1_MACMU	NVRYRGSAYPPEIILRSDLVER	PDPVVLAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAETDQIMMISYMDVGG	306
tr G3RQP2 G3RQP2_GORGO	NVRYRGSAYPPEIILRSDLVER	PDPVVLAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAETDQIMMISYMDVGG	283
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tr A0A5G2RB90 A0A5G2RB90_PIG	NVRYRGSAYPPEIILRSDLVER	PDPVVLAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAETDQIMMISYMDVGG	277
tr A0A420PL83 A0A420PL83_FUSOX	FVEAKHGV-TKIPYNEERSLP	AEPVVMVAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAETDQIMMISYMDVGG	280
tr A0A1V6PGE7 A0A1V6PGE7_PENDC	NVQAKHGV-ISLTCLEERLQR	ADPVVLAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAETDQIMMISYMDVGG	315
tr A0A0G4NU82 A0A0G4NU82_PENCA	NVEADHGV--ISLTCLEERLQR	RADPVVLAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAETDQIMMISYMDVGG	315
tr A0A1V6TET5 A0A1V6TET5_9EURO	NVEADHGV-ISLTCLEERLQR	ADPVVLAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAETDQIMMISYMDVGG	315
tr A0A167WJ50 A0A167WJ50_PENCH	NVEADHGV-ISLTCLEERLQR	ADPVVLAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDAETDQIMMISYMDVGG	315
tr A0A3A2Z9P9 A0A3A2Z9P9_9EURO	TVEAKHGL-ISLTCLEERLQR	ADPVVLAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDSVIDQIMMISYMDVGG	315
tr A0A401L0U3 A0A401L0U3_ASPAW	TVEAKHGV-ISLTCLEERLQR	ADPVVLAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDSVIDQIMMISYMDVGG	315
tr A0A317VH96 A0A317VH96_ASEPC	TVEAKHGV-ISLTCLEERLQR	ADPVVLAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDSVIDQIMMISYMDVGG	311
tr A0A117E1M7 A0A117E1M7_ASPNG	TVEAKHGV-ISLTCLEERLQR	ADPVVLAFDIETTKLPLKFFPDSVIDQIMMISYMDVGG	315
tr A0A1D8PTD0 A0A1D8PTD0_CANAL	DVYAKHSK-VDFVDEKKEIAF	ADPVVLAFDIETTKAPLKFPPDAIDQIMMISYMDVGG	321
tr C5M3R9 C5M3R9_CANTT	DVYAKHSK-IEIVDEKKEIAF	ADPVVLAFDIETTKAPLKFPPDAIDQIMMISYMDVGG	319
sp Q6FNY7 DPOE_CANGA	KVTH-----EGFVWPKKIVAF	ADPVVLAFDIETTKAPLKFPPDAIDQIMMISYMDVGG	316
sp P21951 DPOE_YEAST	KVTQ-----QGFIEDTRKIAF	ADPVVMAFDIETTKPPLKFFPDSAVDQIMMISYMDVGG	259
tr A0A7H9HLU1 A0A7H9HLU1_9SACH	KVAS-----DGLHEITEKVAF	ADPVVLAFDIETTKAPLKFPPDSAVDQIMMISYMDVGG	309
sp Q6CUS7 DPOE_KLULA	AVSA-----QGLVELEEKVTF	ADPVVLAFDIETTKAPLKFPPDSAVDQIMMISYMDVGG	236
sp Q752B8 DPOE_ASHGO	RVTS-----GGLVEYTDKIVAF	ADPVVLAFDIETTKAPLKFPPDSAVDQIMMISYMDVGG	233
:	:	: * : * : * * * * : *	

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sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	YNGDFDNPFFERRASHHGIKMNEELGFRCDHNQGECKRAKFCVCHLDCFAWVKRDSYLPQG	393
tr D7KI06 D7KI06_ARALL	YNGDFDNPFFERRASHHGIKMNEELGFRCDHNQGECKRAKFCVCHLDCFAWVKRDSYLPQG	396
tr A0A8I6WFC8 A0A8I6WFC8_HORVV	YNGDFDNPFFLEKRAAAHGHGKMNNEEIGFQCDNSNQGECRAKFCVCHLDCFAWVKRDSYLPQG	417
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6_AEGTS	YNGDFDNPFFLEKRAAAHGHGKMNNEEIGFQCDNSNQGECRAKFCVCHLDCFAWVKRDSYLPQG	357
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tr A0A1V6TET5 A0A1V6TET5_9EURO	YNGDFDNPFFLEKRAAAHGHGKMNNEEIGFQCDNSNQGECRAKFCVCHLDCFAWVKRDSYLPQG	431
tr A0A167WJ50 A0A167WJ50_PENCH	YNGDFDNPFFLEKRAAAHGHGKMNNEEIGFQCDNSNQGECRAKFCVCHLDCFAWVKRDSYLPQG	431
tr A0A3A2Z9P9 A0A3A2Z9P9_9EURO	YNGDFDNPFFLEKRAAAHGHGKMNNEEIGFQCDNSNQGECRAKFCVCHLDCFAWVKRDSYLPQG	431
tr A0A401L0U3 A0A401L0U3_ASPAW	YNGDFDNPFFLEKRAAAHGHGKMNNEEIGFQCDNSNQGECRAKFCVCHLDCFAWVKRDSYLPQG	431
tr A0A317VH96 A0A317VH96_ASEPC	YNGDFDNPFFLEKRAAAHGHGKMNNEEIGFQCDNSNQGECRAKFCVCHLDCFAWVKRDSYLPQG	427
tr A0A117E1M7 A0A117E1M7_ASPNG	YNGDFDNPFFLEKRAAAHGHGKMNNEEIGFQCDNSNQGECRAKFCVCHLDCFAWVKRDSYLPQG	431
tr A0A1D8PTD0 A0A1D8PTD0_CANAL	FNGDFDNPFFENRTRFHMDMFEIEIGFQKD-NEGEYKSKYCVHMDCFRWVKRDSYLPQG	437
tr C5M3R9 C5M3R9_CANTT	FNGDFDNPFFLEKRAAAHGHGKMNNEEIGFQKD-NEGEYKSKYCVHMDCFRWVKRDSYLPQG	432
sp Q6FNY7 DPOE_CANGA	FNGDFDNPFFLEKRAAAHGHGKMNNEEIGFQKD-NEGEYKSKYCVHMDCFRWVKRDSYLPQG	435
sp P21951 DPOE_YEAST	FNGDFDNPFFLEKRAAAHGHGKMNNEEIGFQKD-NEGEYKSKYCVHMDCFRWVKRDSYLPQG	375
tr A0A7H9HLU1 A0A7H9HLU1_9SACH	FNGDFDNPFFLEKRAAAHGHGKMNNEEIGFQKD-NEGEYKSKYCVHMDCFRWVKRDSYLPQG	425
sp Q6CUS7 DPOE_KLULA	FNGDFDNPFFLEKRAAAHGHGKMNNEEIGFQKD-NEGEYKSKYCVHMDCFRWVKRDSYLPQG	352
sp Q752B8 DPOE_ASHGO	FNGDFDNPFFLEKRAAAHGHGKMNNEEIGFQKD-NEGEYKSKYCVHMDCFRWVKRDSYLPQG	349
:	: * * * * : * : * : * : * : * * * * * *	

tr AOA3P5YCF9 AOA3P5YCF9 BRACM	S HGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	453
sp E4HW04 DPOE1 ARATH	S HGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	453
tr D7KI06 D7KI06 ARALL	S HGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	456
tr AOA8I6WFC8 AOA8I6WFC8 HORVV	S DGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	417
tr AOA452YAR6 AOA452YAR6 AEGTS	S DGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	477
tr AOA3B5XXC3 AOA3B5XXC3 WHEAT	S DGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	472
tr AOA1D6H820 AOA1D6H820 MAIZE	S DGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	450
tr AOA835B357 AOA835B357 9POAL	S DGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	463
tr AOA2S3GPC0 AOA2S3GPC0 9POAL	S DGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	468
tr AOA368PL62 AOA368PL62 SETTIT	S DGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	472
tr AOA7I8KHB8 AOA7I8KHB8 SPIIN	S HGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	454
tr AOA6I9QIG1 AOA6I9QIG1 ELAGV	S HGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	452
tr AOA8B8JBC2 AOA8B8JBC2 PHODC	S HGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	459
tr AOA9Q0FIP5 AOA9Q0FIP5 9ROSI	S DGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	452
tr AOA2C9VYJ6 AOA2C9VYJ6 MANES	S DGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	455
tr AOA7J7C034 AOA7J7C034 TRIWF	S DGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	454
tr AOA2N9F976 AOA2N9F976 FAGSY	S DGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	473
tr AOA7N2KME6 AOA7N2KME6 QUELO	S DGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	453
tr AOA4W5MAK2 AOA4W5MAK2 9TELE	S HNLKAAAKAKLGYDPELDPE	EMCRMATEEQPOTLATYVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	481
tr AOA8C7Q9V4 AOA8C7Q9V4 ONCMY	S HNLKAAAKAKLGYDPELDPE	EMCRMATEEQPOTLATYVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	439
tr AOA6P7J2Q5 AOA6P7J2Q5 9TELE	S HNLKAAAKAKLGYDPELDPE	EMCRMATEEQPOTLATYVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	481
tr AOA6P8SZE0 AOA6P8SZE0 GYMAL	S HNLKAAAKAKLGYDPELDPE	EMCRMATEEQPOTLATYVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	479
tr AOA8J0QX44 AOA8J0QX44 XENTR	S HNLKAAAKAKLGYDPELDPE	EMCRMATEEQPOTLATYVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	478
tr AOA4X2K1K8 AOA4X2K1K8 VOMUR	S HNLKAAAKAKLGYDPELDPE	EMCRMATEEQPOTLATYVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	465
tr AOA5F4D2S5 AOA5F4D2S5 CANLF	S HNLKAAAKAKLGYDPELDPE	EMCRMATEEQPOTLATYVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	478
tr AOA7J7RQ84 AOA7J7RQ84 RHIFE	S HNLKAAAKAKLGYDPELDPE	EMCRMATEEQPOTLATYVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	515
tr AOA6P6D0R3 AOA6P6D0R3 PTEVA	S HNLKAAAKAKLGYDPELDPE	EMCRMATEEQPOTLATYVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	453
tr AOA2K6CI58 AOA2K6CI58 MACNE	S HNLKAAAKAKLGYDPELDPE	EMCRMATEEQPOTLATYVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	472
tr F6QAQ1 F6QAQ1 MACMU	S HNLKAAAKAKLGYDPELDPE	EMCRMATEEQPOTLATYVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	480
tr G3RQP2 G3RQP2 GORGO	S HNLKAAAKAKLGYDPELDPE	EMCRMATEEQPOTLATYVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	482
sp Q07864 DPOE1 HUMAN	S HNLKAAAKAKLGYDPELDPE	EMCRMATEEQPOTLATYVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	459
tr AOA2I3S482 AOA2I3S482 PANTR	S HNLKAAAKAKLGYDPELDPE	EMCRMATEEQPOTLATYVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	480
tr F6Z911 F6Z911 HORSE	S HNLKAAAKAKLGYDPELDPE	EMCRMATEEQPOTLATYVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	480
tr AOA5G2RB90 AOA5G2RB90 PIG	S HNLKAAAKAKLGYDPELDPE	EMCRMATEEQPOTLATYVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	453
tr AOA420PL83 AOA420PL83 FUSOX	S SRLKAVTVAKLGYDPELDPE	LMTPYASERPOTLAEYSVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	456
tr AOA1V6PGE7 AOA1V6PGE7 PENDC	S SRLKAVTVAKLGYDPELDPE	LMTPYASERPOTLAEYSVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	491
tr AOA0G4NU82 AOA0G4NU82 PENCA	S SRLKAVTVAKLGYDPELDPE	LMTPYASERPOTLAEYSVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	491
tr AOA1V6TET5 AOA1V6TET5 9EURO	S SRLKAVTVAKLGYDPELDPE	LMTPYASERPOTLAEYSVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	491
tr AOA167WJ50 AOA167WJ50 PENCH	S SRLKAVTVAKLGYDPELDPE	LMTPYASERPOTLAEYSVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	491
tr AOA3A2Z9P9 AOA3A2Z9P9 9EURO	S SRLKAVTVAKLGYDPELDPE	LMTPYASERPOTLAEYSVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	491
tr AOA401L0U3 AOA401L0U3 ASPAW	S SRLKAVTVAKLGYDPELDPE	LMTPYASERPOTLAEYSVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	491
tr AOA317VH96 AOA317VH96 ASPCC	S SRLKAVTVAKLGYDPELDPE	LMTPYASERPOTLAEYSVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	487
tr AOA117E1M7 AOA117E1M7 ASPNG	S SRLKAVTVAKLGYDPELDPE	LMTPYASERPOTLAEYSVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	491
tr AOA1D8PTD0 AOA1D8PTD0 CANAL	S DGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	497
tr C5M3R9 C5M3R9 CANTT	S DGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	492
tr Q6FNY7 DPOE CANGA	S DGLKAVTKAKLGYDPLEVNPE	DMVRFAMEKQPOTMASVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	495
sp P21951 DPOE YEAST	S DGLKAVTQSKLGNPIELDP	LMTPYAEKQPQLSEYSVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	435
tr AOA7H9HLU1 AOA7H9HLU1 9SACH	S DGLKAVTQSKLGNPIELDP	LMTPYAEKQPQLSEYSVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	485
tr Q6CUS7 DPOE KLULA	S DGLKAVTQSKLGNPIELDP	LMTPYAEKQPQLSEYSVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	412
tr Q752B8 DPOE ASHGO	S DGLKAVTQSKLGNPIELDP	LMTPYAEKQPQLSEYSVSVS	DAVATYYLYMTYVHVPFIFS	409

tr AOA3P5YCF9 AOA3P5YCF9 BRACM	LAT IIPMV	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVVE	PR exo ←	→ Pol	NVVC PNKNQADPEKF-YQS	503
sp E4HW04 DPOE1 ARATH	LAT IIPMV	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVVE	PR exo ←	→ Pol	NVVC PNKNQADPEKF-YQN	503
tr D7KI06 D7KI06 ARALL	LAT IIPMV	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQVSTYLPQAQAYKV			NVVC PNKNQADPEKF-YQN	515
tr AOA8I6WFC8 AOA8I6WFC8 HORVV	LAT IIPMS	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			SVICPNKHQADLEKF-YNN	527
tr AOA452YAR6 AOA452YAR6 AEGTS	LAT IIPMS	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NIICPNKHQADLEKF-YNN	467
tr AOA3B5XXC3 AOA3B5XXC3 WHEAT	LAT IIPMS	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NIICPNKHQADLEKF-YNN	522
tr AOA1D6H820 AOA1D6H820 MAIZE	LAT IIPMS	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			SVICPNKHQADLEKF-YNN	500
tr AOA835B357 AOA835B357 9POAL	LAT IIPMS	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NVICPNKHQADLEKF-YNN	513
tr AOA2S3GPC0 AOA2S3GPC0 9POAL	LAT IIPMS	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NVICPNKHQADLEKF-YNN	518
tr AOA368PL62 AOA368PL62 SETTIT	LAT IIPMS	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NVICPNKHQADLEKF-YNN	522
tr AOA7I8KHB8 AOA7I8KHB8 SPIIN	LAT IIPMP	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NVICPNKHQADPEKF-YNN	504
tr AOA6I9QIG1 AOA6I9QIG1 ELAGV	LAT IIPMT	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NIICPNKHQDDPEKF-YNN	502
tr AOA8B8JBC2 AOA8B8JBC2 PHODC	LAT IIPMT	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NIICPNKHQDDPEKF-YNN	502
tr AOA9Q0FIP5 AOA9Q0FIP5 9ROSI	LST IIPMS	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NVICPNKHQSDPEKF-HRN	519
tr AOA2C9VYJ6 AOA2C9VYJ6 MANES	LAT IIPMS	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NVICPNKHQSDPEKF-YKN	505
tr AOA7J7C034 AOA7J7C034 TRIWF	LAT IIPMS	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NVICPNKHQSDPEKF-YKN	504
tr AOA2N9F976 AOA2N9F976 FAGSY	LAT IIPMS	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NVICPNKHQSDPEKF-YTN	523
tr AOA7N2KME6 AOA7N2KME6 QUELO	LAT IIPMS	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NVICPNKHQSDPEKF-YNS	503
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tr AOA8C7Q9V4 AOA8C7Q9V4 ONCMY	LCT IIPME	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NIVFPNKQEQVFNKLTDDG	490
tr AOA6P7J2Q5 AOA6P7J2Q5 9TELE	LCT IIPME	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NIVFPNKQEQVFNKLTDDG	532
tr AOA6P8SZE0 AOA6P8SZE0 GYMAL	LCT IIPME	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NIVFPNKQEQVFNKLTDDG	530
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tr AOA4X2K1K8 AOA4X2K1K8 VOMUR	LCT IIPME	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NIIFPNKQEQVFNKLTDDG	516
tr AOA5F4D2S5 AOA5F4D2S5 CANLF	LCT IIPME	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NIIFPNKQEQVFNKLTDDG	566
tr AOA7J7RQ84 AOA7J7RQ84 RHIFE	LCT IIPME	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NIIFPNKQEQVFNKLTDDG	504
tr AOA6P6D0R3 AOA6P6D0R3 PTEVA	LCT IIPME	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NIVFPNKQEQVFNKLTDDG	523
tr AOA2K6CI58 AOA2K6CI58 MACNE	LCT IIPME	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NIIFPNKQEQVFNKLTDDG	531
tr F6QAQ1 F6QAQ1 MACMU	LCT IIPME	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NIIFPNKQEQVFNKLTDDG	533
tr G3RQP2 G3RQP2 GORGO	LCT IIPME	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NIIFPNKQEQVFNKLTDDG	510
sp Q07864 DPOE1 HUMAN	LCT IIPME	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NIIFPNKQEQVFNKLTDDG	531
tr AOA2I3S482 AOA2I3S482 PANTR	LCT IIPME	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NIIFPNKQEQVFNKLTDDG	531
tr F6Z911 F6Z911 HORSE	LCT IIPME	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NIIFPNKQEQVFNKLTDDG	531
tr AOA5G2RB90 AOA5G2RB90 PIG	LCT IIPME	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NIIFPNKQEQVFNKLTDDG	504
tr AOA420PL83 AOA420PL83 FUSOX	LCT IIPMS	EVLVRKSGSGLCEMLLMVQ			NIVFPNKQEQVFNKLTDDG	506
tr AOA1V6PGE7 AOA1V6PGE7 PENDC	LCT IIPLN	DET LRKGTGTLCMLLMVQ			EIILPNKHKDPEAF-YDG	541
tr AOA0G4NU82 AOA0G4NU82 PENCA	LCT IIPLN	DET LRKGTGTLCMLLMVQ			EIVLPNKHKNPPEAF-YEG	541
tr AOA1V6TET5 AOA1V6TET5 9EURO	LCT IIPLN	DET LRKGTGTLCMLLMVQ			EIVLPNKHKNPPEAF-YEG	541
tr AOA167WJ50 AOA167WJ50 PENCH	LCT IIPLN	DET LRKGTGTLCMLLMVQ			EIVLPNKHKNPPEAF-YEG	541
tr AOA3A2Z9P9 AOA3A2Z9P9 9EURO	LCT IIPLN	DET LRKGTGTLCMLLMVQ			EIVLPNKHKNPPEAF-YEG	541
tr AOA401L0U3 AOA401L0U3 ASPAW	LCT IIPLN	DET LRKGTGTLCMLLMVQ			NIVLPNKHKNPPEAF-YEG	541
tr AOA317VH96 AOA317VH96 ASPCC	LCT IIPLN	DET LRKGTGTLCMLLMVQ			NIVLPNKHKNPPEAF-YEG	537
tr AOA117E1M7 AOA117E1M7 ASPNG	LCT IIPLN	DET LRKGTGTLCMLLMVQ			NIVLPNKHKNPPEAF-YEG	541
tr AOA1D8PTD0 AOA1D8PTD0 CANAL	LCT IIPLN	DET LRKGTGTLCMLLMVQ			NIVLPNKHKNPPEAF-YEG	547
tr C5M3R9 C5M3R9 CANTT	LCT IIPLN	DET LRKGTGTLCMLLMVQ			NIVLPNKHKNPPEAF-YEG	542
tr Q6FNY7 DPOE CANGA	LCT IIPLN	DET LRKGTGTLCMLLMVQ			NIVLPNKHKNPPEAF-YEG	545
sp P21951 DPOE YEAST	LCT IIPLN	DET LRKGTGTLCMLLMVQ			NIVLPNKHKNPPEAF-YEG	485
tr AOA7H9HLU1 AOA7H9HLU1 9SACH	LCT IIPLN	DET LRKGTGTLCMLLMVQ			NIVLPNKHKNPPEAF-YEG	535
tr Q6CUS7 DPOE KLULA	LCT IIPLN	DET LRKGTGTLCMLLMVQ			SVLLPNKHKNPPEAF-YEG	462
tr Q752B8 DPOE ASHGO	LCT IIPLN	DET LRKGTGTLCMLLMVQ			GILLPNKHKNPPEAF-YEG	459

tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM	EKLKRDCEPIREEGPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPPSIVTNEI	678
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	EKLKRDDEPIREEGPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPPSIVTDEI	678
tr D7KI06 D7KI06_ARALL	EKLKRDDEPIREEGPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRLQVHLIS	PSPSIVTDEVT	678
tr A0A816WFC8 A0A816WFC8_HORVV	VSLRDHPTREECPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPPSIVTDVDT	678
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6_AEGTS	VSLRDHPTREECPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPPSIVTDVDT	678
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT	VSLRDHPTREECPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPPSIVTDVDT	678
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE	VSLRDHPTREECPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPPSIVTDVDT	678
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357_9POAL	VSLRDHPTREECPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPPSIVTDVDT	678
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL	VSLRDHPTREECPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPPSIVTDVDT	678
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62_SETIT	VSLRDHPTREECPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPPSIVTDVDT	678
tr A0A718KHB8 A0A718KHB8_SPIIN	QSLRDHPTREECPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPPSIVSDVDT	678
tr A0A619QIG1 A0A619QIG1_ELAGV	IFLRDHPMREECPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPPSIVSDVDT	678
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2_PHODC	ILLRDRPTREECPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPLSIVSDVDT	678
tr A0A90QFIP5 A0A90QFIP5_9ROSI	LSLRDDPVREECPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPPSIVTDEI	678
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	VRLRDEPTREECPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPPSIVTDEI	678
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034_TRIWF	VRLQDEPTREECPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPPSIVTDDVT	678
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976_FAGSY	-----KPPSIVTDEVT	CAACDFNRP	678
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6_QUELO	VRLQGEPIRDEECPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPPSIVTDEVT	678
tr A0A4W5MAK2 A0A4W5MAK2_9TELE	ISLKEVFNRIECPPIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPSAMVDEAT	678
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tr A0A6P8SZE0 A0A6P8SZE0_GYMAC	ISLKEVFNRIECPPIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPSAVVDEAT	678
tr A0A8J0QX44 A0A8J0QX44_XENTR	NSLKEVFNRIECPPIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPSAMVDEAT	678
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tr A0A5F4D2S5 A0A5F4D2S5_CANLF	TSLKDVFNRIECPPIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPSAVVDEAT	678
tr A0A7J7RQ84 A0A7J7RQ84_RHIFE	TSLKDVFNRIECPPIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPSAMVDEAT	678
tr A0A6P6D0R3 A0A6P6D0R3_PTEVA	TSLRDVFNRIECPPIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPSAMVDEAT	678
tr A0A2K6C158 A0A2K6C158_MACNE	ASLKDVPSRIECPPIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPSAMVDEAT	678
tr F6QAQ1 F6QAQ1_MACMU	ASLKDVPSRIECPPIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPSAMVDEAT	678
tr G3RQP2 G3RQP2_GORGO	ASLKDVPSRIECPPIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPSAMVDEAT	678
sp Q07864 DPOE1_HUMAN	ASLKDVPSRIECPPIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPSAMVDEAT	678
tr A0A213S482 A0A213S482_PANTR	ASLKDVPSRIECPPIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPSAMVDEAT	678
tr F6Z911 F6Z911_HORSE	TSLKDVFNRIECPPIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPSAMVDEAT	678
tr A0A5G2RB90 A0A5G2RB90_PIG	TSLKDVFNRIECPPIYHLDAVAAAMPNIILTNRL----	QPSAMVDEAT	678
tr A0A420PL83 A0A420PL83_FUSOX	NKLTKEPTNRNKEPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIIMTNRL----	QPSDMIQESD	678
tr A0A1V6PGE7 A0A1V6PGE7_PENDC	LDLKNPVNRNEVFFIYHLDAVAAAMPNIIMTNRL----	QPSDLIKESD	678
tr A0A0G4NU82 A0A0G4NU82_PENCA	LDLKNPVNRNEVFFIYHLDAVAAAMPNIIMTNRL----	QPSDLIDESN	678
tr A0A1V6TET5 A0A1V6TET5_9EURO	LDLKNPVNRNEVFFIYHLDAVAAAMPNIIMTNRL----	QPSDLIDESN	678
tr A0A167WJ50 A0A167WJ50_PENCH	LDLKNPVNRNEVFFIYHLDAVAAAMPNIIMTNRL----	QPSDLIDESN	678
tr A0A3A2Z9P9 A0A3A2Z9P9_9EURO	ADMRRDPVNRNEVFFIYHLDAVAAAMPNIIMTNRL----	QPSDMIQESN	678
tr A0A401L0U3 A0A401L0U3_ASPAW	IDLKERPHRDEVPFIYHLDAVAAAMPNIIMTNRL----	QPSDMIQESN	678
tr A0A317VH96 A0A317VH96_ASEPC	IDLKERPHRDEVPFIYHLDAVAAAMPNIIMTNRL----	QPSDMIQESN	678
tr A0A117EIM7 A0A117EIM7_ASPNG	IDLKERPHRDEVPFIYHLDAVAAAMPNIIMTNRL----	QPSDMIQESN	678
tr A0A1D8PTD0 A0A1D8PTD0_CANAL	LELKNVPSRQEKPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIIMTNRL----	QPSDMKSEDD	678
tr C5M3R9 C5M3R9_CANTT	LNKLNTPRIREKPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIIMTNRL----	QPSDMKTEDD	678
tr Q6FNY7 DPOE_CANGA	LELKENNRHEKPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIIMTNRL----	QPSDKTEKDD	678
sp P21951 DPOE_YEAST	LELKENNRHEKPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIIMTNRL----	QPSDKTEKDD	678
tr A0A7H9HLU1 A0A7H9HLU1_9SACH	LDLKTNNKRCLEPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIIMTNRL----	QPSDMKTERD	678
tr Q6CUS7 DPOE_KLULA	TDLKNKRNRELEPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIIMTNRL----	QPSDMKDEKDD	678
tr Q752B8 DPOE_ASHGO	QELKMNKRKLEPLIYHLDAVAAAMPNIIMTNRL----	QPSDMKTERD	678

tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM	LRKLEWVWRGTYMMAKSDYYHLKKQIESEFVDAGANIQ--	SSKSFLLDPKVEQQSKLK	736
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	LRKLEWVWRGTYMMAKSDYYHLKKQIESEFVDAGANIM--	SSKSFLLDPKVDQGSKLK	736
tr D7KI06 D7KI06_ARALL	LRKLEWVWRGTYMMAKSDYYHLKKQIESEFVDAGANIQ--	SSKSFLLDPKLDQGSKLK	736
tr A0A816WFC8 A0A816WFC8_HORVV	CLRTLLEWVRGTYTAKKSDYHHRKQIESEMIQAG-GVT--	SSKFFLLDLSKPEHLLK	736
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6_AEGTS	CLRTLLEWVRGTYTAKKSDYHHRKQIESEMIQAG-GVT--	SSKFFLLDLSKPEHLLK	736
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT	CLRTLLEWVRGTYTAKKSDYHHRKQIESEMIQAG-GVT--	SSKFFLLDLSKPEHLLK	736
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE	CLRKLEWVWRGTYMMAKNDYHHRKQIESELIQSG-GIA--	SSKFFLLDLSKPEHLLK	736
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357_9POAL	CLRKLEWVWRGTYMMAKNDYHHRKQIESELIQSG-GIA--	SSKFFLLDLSKPEHLLK	736
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL	CLRKLEWVWRGTYMMAKNDYHHRKQIESELIQSG-GIA--	SSKFFLLDLSKPEHLLK	736
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62_SETIT	CLRKLEWVWRGTYTAKKSDYHHRKQIESELIQSG-GIA--	SSKFFLLDLSKPEHLLK	736
tr A0A718KHB8 A0A718KHB8_SPIIN	CLRKLEWVWRGTYTAKKSDYHHRKQIESELVENG-EDR--	LSKAFLLDLPKSEQQLK	736
tr A0A619QIG1 A0A619QIG1_ELAGV	CLRKLEWVWRGTYMMAKSDYHHRKQIESELVENG-EGQ--	AIKFFLLDLPKSEQQLK	736
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2_PHODC	CLRKLEWVWRGTYMMAKSDYHHRKQIESELVENG-EGQ--	TIKFFLLDLPKSEQQLK	736
tr A0A90QFIP5 A0A90QFIP5_9ROSI	CLRTLLEWVRGTYMMAKSDYHHRKQIESEFVDGA-DGQ--	LSKSFLLDMPKVEQQLK	736
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	CLRKLEWVWRGTYMMAKSDYHHRKQIESEFVDGT-DGQ--	LSKSFLLDMPKVEQQLK	736
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034_TRIWF	CLRKLEWVWRGTYMMAKSDYHHRKQIESEFVGG-NGQ--	LSKSFLLDLPKTEQQLK	736
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976_FAGSY	CLRKLEWVWRGTYMMAKSDYHHRKQIESEFVDGA-GGK--	LPSFLLDLPKTEQQLK	736
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6_QUELO	CLRKLEWVWRGTYMMAKSDYHHRKQIESEFVDGT-GGQ--	LPSFLLDLPKTEQQLK	736
tr A0A4W5MAK2 A0A4W5MAK2_9TELE	CRKMSWQWRGTYMMPASRSEYHRIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	RPRAFHLLNLEEQAQHEK	736
tr A0A8C7Q9V4 A0A8C7Q9V4_ONCMY	CRKMSWQWRGTYMMPASRSEYHRIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	RPRAFHLLNLEEQAQHEK	736
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tr A0A6P8SZE0 A0A6P8SZE0_GYMAC	CRKMAWQWRGTYMMPASRSEYHRIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	RPRAFHLLNLEEQAQHEK	736
tr A0A8J0QX44 A0A8J0QX44_XENTR	CRKMTWQWRGTYMMPASRSEYHRIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	RPRAFHLLNLEEQAQHEK	736
tr A0A4X2K1K8 A0A4X2K1K8_VOMUR	CRKMAWQWRGTYMMPASRSEYHRIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	RPRAFHLLNLEEQAQHEK	736
tr A0A5F4D2S5 A0A5F4D2S5_CANLF	CRKMAWQWRGTYMMPASRSEYHRIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	RPRAFHLLNLEEQAQHEK	736
tr A0A7J7RQ84 A0A7J7RQ84_RHIFE	CRKMAWQWRGTYMMPASRSEYHRIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	RPRAFHLLNLEEQAQHEK	736
tr A0A6P6D0R3 A0A6P6D0R3_PTEVA	CRKMAWQWRGTYMMPASRSEYHRIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	RPRAFHLLNLEEQAQHEK	736
tr A0A2K6C158 A0A2K6C158_MACNE	CRKMAWQWRGTYMMPASRSEYHRIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	RPRAFHLLNLEEQAQHEK	736
tr F6QAQ1 F6QAQ1_MACMU	CRKMAWQWRGTYMMPASRSEYHRIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	RPRAFHLLNLEEQAQHEK	736
tr G3RQP2 G3RQP2_GORGO	CRKMAWQWRGTYMMPASRSEYHRIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	RPRAFHLLNLEEQAQHEK	736
sp Q07864 DPOE1_HUMAN	CRKMAWQWRGTYMMPASRSEYHRIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	RPRAFHLLNLEEQAQHEK	736
tr A0A213S482 A0A213S482_PANTR	CRKMAWQWRGTYMMPASRSEYHRIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	RPRAFHLLNLEEQAQHEK	736
tr F6Z911 F6Z911_HORSE	CRKMAWQWRGTYMMPASRSEYHRIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	RPRAFHLLNLEEQAQHEK	736
tr A0A5G2RB90 A0A5G2RB90_PIG	CRKMAWQWRGTYMMPASRSEYHRIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	RPRAFHLLNLEEQAQHEK	736
tr A0A420PL83 A0A420PL83_FUSOX	DRRLPWAWRGEFLLPAKRDEYNIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	PMRFTFQELSADEQANLVK	736
tr A0A1V6PGE7 A0A1V6PGE7_PENDC	DRRMPWAWRGEFLLPAKRDEYNIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	PMRFTFQELSADEQANLVK	736
tr A0A0G4NU82 A0A0G4NU82_PENCA	DRRMPWAWRGEFLLPAKRDEYNIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	PMRFTFQELSADEQANLVK	736
tr A0A1V6TET5 A0A1V6TET5_9EURO	DRRMPWAWRGEFLLPAKRDEYNIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	PMRFTFQELSADEQANLVK	736
tr A0A167WJ50 A0A167WJ50_PENCH	DRRMPWAWRGEFLLPAKRDEYNIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	PMRFTFQELSADEQANLVK	736
tr A0A3A2Z9P9 A0A3A2Z9P9_9EURO	DRRMPWAWRGEFLLPAKRDEYNIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	PMRFTFQELSADEQANLVK	736
tr A0A401L0U3 A0A401L0U3_ASPAW	DRRMPWAWRGEFLLPAKRDEYNIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	PMRFTFQELSADEQANLVK	736
tr A0A317VH96 A0A317VH96_ASEPC	DRRMPWAWRGEFLLPAKRDEYNIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	PMRFTFQELSADEQANLVK	736
tr A0A117EIM7 A0A117EIM7_ASPNG	DRRMPWAWRGEFLLPAKRDEYNIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	PMRFTFQELSADEQANLVK	736
tr A0A1D8PTD0 A0A1D8PTD0_CANAL	DRRLPWAWRGEFLLPAKRDEYNIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	PMRFTFQELSADEQANLVK	736
tr C5M3R9 C5M3R9_CANTT	DRRLPWAWRGEFLLPAKRDEYNIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	PMRFTFQELSADEQANLVK	736
tr Q6FNY7 DPOE_CANGA	DRRLPWAWRGEFLLPAKRDEYNIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	PMRFTFQELSADEQANLVK	736
sp P21951 DPOE_YEAST	DRRLPWAWRGEFLLPAKRDEYNIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	PMRFTFQELSADEQANLVK	736
tr A0A7H9HLU1 A0A7H9HLU1_9SACH	DRRLKWSWRGEFLLPAKRDEYNIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	PMRFTFQELSADEQANLVK	736
tr Q6CUS7 DPOE_KLULA	DRRLKWSWRGEFLLPAKRDEYNIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	PMRFTFQELSADEQANLVK	736
tr Q752B8 DPOE_ASHGO	DRRLKWSWRGEFLLPAKRDEYNIHQLESEKFPPLFPNG--	PMRFTFQELSADEQANLVK	736

		ZBM			
tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9	BRACM	ERLKKYQKAYKRVLDKPI TELREAGI	CMREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	796
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH		ERLKKYQKAYKRVLDKPI TELREAGI	CMREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	752
tr D7KI06 D7KI06	ARALL	ERLKKYQKAYKRVLDKPI TELREAGI	CMREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	751
tr A0A8I6WFC8 A0A8I6WFC8	HORVV	DRLKKYQKAYKRVLDKPI TELREAGI	CMREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	775
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6	AEGTS	DRLKKYQKAYKRVLDKPI TELREAGI	CMREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	715
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3	WHEAT	DRLKKYQKAYKRVLDKPI TELREAGI	CMREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	770
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0	MAIZE	DRLKKYQKAYKRVLDKPI TELREAGI	CMREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	748
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357	_9POAL	DRLKKYQKAYKRVLDKPI TELREAGI	CMREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	761
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0	_9POAL	DRLKKYQKAYKRVLDKPI TELREAGI	CMREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	766
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62	_SETIT	DRLKKYQKAYKRVLDKPI TELREAGI	CMREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	770
tr A0A7I8KH88 A0A7I8KH88	_SPI IN	ERLKKYQKAYKRVLDKPI TELREAGI	CMREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	752
tr A0A6I9QIG1 A0A6I9QIG1	_ELAGV	ERLKKYQKAYKRVLDKPI TELREAGI	CMREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	750
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2	_PHODC	ERLKKYQKAYKRVLDKPI TELREAGI	CMREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	750
tr A0A9Q0FIP5 A0A9Q0FIP5	_9ROSI	ERLKKYQKAYKRVLDKPI TELREAGI	CMREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	767
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6	_MANES	ERLKKYQKAYKRVLDKPI TELREAGI	CMREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	753
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034	_TRIFW	ERLKKYQKAYKRVLDKPI TELREAGI	CMREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	752
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976	_FAGSY	ERLKKYQKAYKRVLDKPI TELREAGI	CMREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	736
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6	_QUELO	ERLKKYQKAYKRVLDKPI TELREAGI	CMREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	751
tr A0A4W5MAK2 A0A4W5MAK2	_9TELE	KRLGDYCRAYKRVQTK-LEERVTTI	COREN	FYVDTVRAFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	780
tr A0A8C7Q9V4 A0A8C7Q9V4	_ONCMY	KRLGDYCRAYKRVQTK-LEERVTTI	COREN	FYVDTVRAFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	738
tr A0A6F7J2Q5 A0A6F7J2Q5	_9TELE	KRLADYCRAYKRVQTK-LEERVTTI	COREN	FYVDTVRAFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	780
tr A0A6P8SZE0 A0A6P8SZE0	_GYMAC	KRLADYCRAYKRVQTK-LEERVTTI	COREN	FYVDTVRAFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	778
tr A0A8J0QX44 A0A8J0QX44	_XENTR	KRLADYCRAYKRVQTK-LEERVTTI	COREN	FYVDTVRAFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	777
tr A0A4X2K1K8 A0A4X2K1K8	_VOMUR	KRLADYCRAYKRVQTK-LEERVTTI	COREN	FYVDTVRAFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	764
tr A0A5F4D2S5 A0A5F4D2S5	_CANLF	RRLSDYCRAYKRVQTK-VEERLTTI	COREN	FYVDTVRAFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	814
tr A0A7J7RQ84 A0A7J7RQ84	_RHIFE	RRLADYCRAYKRVQTK-VEERLTTI	COREN	FYVDTVRAFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	752
tr A0A6P6D0R3 A0A6P6D0R3	_PTEVA	RRLADYCRAYKRVQTK-VEERLTTI	COREN	FYVDTVRAFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	771
tr A0A2K6C158 A0A2K6C158	_MACNE	RRLADYCRAYKRVQTK-VEERLTTI	COREN	FYVDTVRAFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	779
tr F6QAQ1 F6QAQ1	_MACMU	RRLADYCRAYKRVQTK-VEERLTTI	COREN	FYVDTVRAFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	781
tr G3RQF2 G3RQF2	_GORGO	RRLADYCRAYKRVQTK-VEERLTTI	COREN	FYVDTVRAFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	758
sp Q07864 DPOE1_HUMAN		RRLADYCRAYKRVQTK-VEERLTTI	COREN	FYVDTVRAFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	779
tr A0A2I3S482 A0A2I3S482	_PANTR	RRLADYCRAYKRVQTK-VEERLTTI	COREN	FYVDTVRAFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	779
tr F6Z911 F6Z911	_HORSE	RRLADYCRAYKRVQTK-VEERLTTI	COREN	FYVDTVRAFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	779
tr A0A5G2RB90 A0A5G2RB90	_PIG	RRLADYCRAYKRVQTK-VEERLTTI	COREN	FYVDTVRAFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	752
tr A0A420PL83 A0A420PL83	_FUSOX	KRLQYQSKYKRVVHDKP-TEVREAGI	COREN	FYINTVDFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	754
tr A0A1V6PGE7 A0A1V6PGE7	_PENDC	KRLQYQSKYKRVVHDKP-TEVREAGI	COREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	789
tr A0A0G4NU82 A0A0G4NU82	_PENCA	KRLQYQSKYKRVVHDKP-TEVREAGI	COREN	FYVDTVDFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	789
tr A0A1V6TET5 A0A1V6TET5	_9EURO	KRLQYQSKYKRVVHDKP-TEVREAGI	COREN	FYVDTVRAFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	789
tr A0A167WJ50 A0A167WJ50	_PENCH	KRLQYQSKYKRVVHDKP-TEVREAGI	COREN	FYVDTVRAFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	789
tr A0A3A2Z9P9 A0A3A2Z9P9	_9EURO	KRLQYQSKYKRVVHDKP-TEVREAGI	COREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	789
tr A0A401L0U3 A0A401L0U3	_ASPAW	KRLQYQSKYKRVVHDKP-TEVREAGI	COREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	789
tr A0A317VH96 A0A317VH96	_ASPEC	KRLQYQSKYKRVVHDKP-TEVREAGI	COREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	785
tr A0A117E1M7 A0A117E1M7	_ASPNG	KRLQYQSKYKRVVHDKP-TEVREAGI	COREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	789
tr A0A1D8PTD0 A0A1D8PTD0	_CANAL	KRISDYSRKYVHRVKVSE-IVVERAIV	COREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	795
tr C5M3R9 C5M3R9	_CANIT	KRISDYSRKYVHRVKVSE-IVVERAIV	COREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	790
sp Q6FNY7 DPOE_CANGA		KRISDYSRKYVHRVKVSE-IVVERAIV	COREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	795
sp P21951 DPOE_YEAST		KRLTEYSRKYVHRVKVSE-IVVERAIV	COREN	FYVDTVKSFDRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	735
tr A0A7H9HLU1 A0A7H9HLU1	_9SACH	KRLTDYSRKYVHRVKVSE-IVVERAIV	COREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	785
sp Q6CUS7 DPOE_KLULA		KRLTDYSRKYVHRVKVSE-IVVERAIV	COREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	712
sp Q752B8 DPOE_ASHGO		KRLSEYSRKYVHRVKVSE-SVVEREIV	COREN	FYVDTVRSFRDRRYEYKTLNKKVWKGFL	709

tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9	BRACM	SEAKASGNS-IKIQEADMVYVYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	855	
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH		SEAKASGNS-IKIQEADMVYVYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	811	
tr D7KI06 D7KI06	ARALL	SEAKASGNS-IKIQEADMVYVYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	810	
tr A0A8I6WFC8 A0A8I6WFC8	HORVV	SEAKASGNS-IKIQEADMVYVYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	834	
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6	AEGTS	SEAKASGNS-IKIQEADMVYVYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	774	
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3	WHEAT	SEAKASGNS-IKIQEADMVYVYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	829	
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0	MAIZE	SEAKASGNS-IKIQEADMVYVYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	807	
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357	_9POAL	SEAKASGNS-IKIQEADMVYVYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	820	
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0	_9POAL	SEAKASGNS-IKIQEADMVYVYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	825	
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62	_SETIT	SEAKASGNS-IKIQEADMVYVYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	829	
tr A0A7I8KH88 A0A7I8KH88	_SPI IN	SEAKASGNS-IKIQEADMVYVYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	811	
tr A0A6I9QIG1 A0A6I9QIG1	_ELAGV	SEAKASGNS-IKIQEADMVYVYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	809	
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2	_PHODC	SEAKASGNS-IKIQEADMVYVYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	809	
tr A0A9Q0FIP5 A0A9Q0FIP5	_9ROSI	SEAKASGNS-IKIQEADMVYVYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	826	
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6	_MANES	SEAKASGNS-IKIQEADMVYVYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	812	
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034	_TRIFW	SEAKASGNS-IKIQEADMVYVYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	811	
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976	_FAGSY	SEAKASGNS-IKIQEADMVYVYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	795	
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6	_QUELO	SEAKASGNS-IKIQEADMVYVYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	810	
tr A0A4W5MAK2 A0A4W5MAK2	_9TELE	SAAQESGDA-ALVVKRCKNMEVLYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	839	
tr A0A8C7Q9V4 A0A8C7Q9V4	_ONCMY	SAAQESGDA-ALVVKRCKNMEVLYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	797	
tr A0A6F7J2Q5 A0A6F7J2Q5	_9TELE	STAQDNGDA-AEVKRCNMEVLYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	839	
tr A0A6P8SZE0 A0A6P8SZE0	_GYMAC	SAAQESGDA-AEVKRCNMEVLYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	837	
tr A0A8J0QX44 A0A8J0QX44	_XENTR	SSACESGDA-AEIKRCNMEVLYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	836	
tr A0A4X2K1K8 A0A4X2K1K8	_VOMUR	SAATEMGDA-AEVKRCNMEVLYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	823	
tr A0A5F4D2S5 A0A5F4D2S5	_CANLF	SAAMEVGDGA-AEVKRCNMEVLYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	873	
tr A0A7J7RQ84 A0A7J7RQ84	_RHIFE	CAAVEAGDA-AEVKRCNMEVLYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	811	
tr A0A6P6D0R3 A0A6P6D0R3	_PTEVA	CAAVEAGDA-AEVKRCNMEVLYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	830	
tr A0A2K6C158 A0A2K6C158	_MACNE	SAAVEVGDGA-AEVKRCNMEVLYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	838	
tr F6QAQ1 F6QAQ1	_MACMU	SAAVEVGDGA-AEVKRCNMEVLYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	840	
tr G3RQF2 G3RQF2	_GORGO	SAAVEVGDGA-AEVKRCNMEVLYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	817	
sp Q07864 DPOE1_HUMAN		SAAVEVGDGA-AEVKRCNMEVLYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	837	
tr A0A2I3S482 A0A2I3S482	_PANTR	SAAVEVGDGA-AEVKRCNMEVLYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	838	
tr F6Z911 F6Z911	_HORSE	SAAVEVGDGA-AEVKRCNMEVLYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	838	
tr A0A5G2RB90 A0A5G2RB90	_PIG	SAAVEAGDA-AEVKRCNMEVLYDLSI	LAHK	ILNSFY	YVMRKGARWYSMEMAGVTCFT	811	
tr A0A420PL83 A0A420PL83	_FUSOX	SSLQASGASAAIEAEAKKMI	ILVFDLSI	LAHKV	ILNSFY	YVMRKGSRWYSMEMAGVTCFT	814
tr A0A1V6PGE7 A0A1V6PGE7	_PENDC	DGLQSSGGSAAIEAEAKKMI	ILVFDLSI	LAHKV	ILNSFY	YVMRKGSRWYSMEMAGVTCFT	849
tr A0A0G4NU82 A0A0G4NU82	_PENCA	DGLQSSGGSAAIEAEAKKMI	ILVFDLSI	LAHKV	ILNSFY	YVMRKGSRWYSMEMAGVTCFT	849
tr A0A1V6TET5 A0A1V6TET5	_9EURO	DGLQSSGGSAAIEAEAKKMI	ILVFDLSI	LAHKV	ILNSFY	YVMRKGSRWYSMEMAGVTCFT	849
tr A0A167WJ50 A0A167WJ50	_PENCH	DGLQSSGGSAAIEAEAKKMI	ILVFDLSI	LAHKV	ILNSFY	YVMRKGSRWYSMEMAGVTCFT	849
tr A0A3A2Z9P9 A0A3A2Z9P9	_9EURO	DSLRSAGASAAIEAEAKKMI	ILVFDLSI	LAHKV	ILNSFY	YVMRKGSRWYSMEMAGVTCFT	849
tr A0A401L0U3 A0A401L0U3	_ASPAW	DALKSSGASAAIEAEAKKMI	ILVFDLSI	LAHKV	ILNSFY	YVMRKGSRWYSMEMAGVTCFT	849
tr A0A317VH96 A0A317VH96	_ASPEC	DALKSSGASAAIEAEAKKMI	ILVFDLSI	LAHKV	ILNSFY	YVMRKGSRWYSMEMAGVTCFT	845
tr A0A117E1M7 A0A117E1M7	_ASPNG	DALKSSGASAAIEAEAKKMI	ILVFDLSI	LAHKV	ILNSFY	YVMRKGSRWYSMEMAGVTCFT	849
tr A0A1D8PTD0 A0A1D8PTD0	_CANAL	GKIASNDTI--ARDEAKKMI	ILVFDLSI	LAHKV	ILNSFY	YVMRKGSRWYSMEMAGVTCFT	853
tr C5M3R9 C5M3R9	_CANIT	GKIDASDTI--ARDEAKKMI	ILVFDLSI	LAHKV	ILNSFY	YVMRKGSRWYSMEMAGVTCFT	848
sp Q6FNY7 DPOE_CANGA		SSIDRNDKH--GKDEAKKMI	ILVFDLSI	LAHKV	ILNSFY	YVMRKGSRWYSMEMAGVTCFT	853
sp P21951 DPOE_YEAST		SKIDPSDKH--ARDEAKKMI	ILVFDLSI	LAHKV	ILNSFY	YVMRKGSRWYSMEMAGVTCFT	793
tr A0A7H9HLU1 A0A7H9HLU1	_9SACH	SSIPSADKH--ARDEAKKMI	ILVFDLSI	LAHKV	ILNSFY	YVMRKGSRWYSMEMAGVTCFT	843
sp Q6CUS7 DPOE_KLULA		SKIKPDDVH--SKDEAKKMI	ILVFDLSI	LAHKV	ILNSFY	YVMRKGSRWYSMEMAGVTCFT	770
sp Q752B8 DPOE_ASHGO		SQIDPEDKV--ARDEAKKMI	ILVFDLSI	LAHKV	ILNSFY	YVMRKGSRWYSMEMAGVTCFT	767

tr AOA3P5YCF9 AOA3P5YCF9 BRACM	GAKIIQNAARLLERIGRPLELDTDGIWCALPGSFFPENFTFKTIDM-K-KLTISYPCVMLN	913
sp F4HW04 DPOE1 ARATH	GAKIIQNAARLLERIGRPLELDTDGIWCALPGSFFPENFTFKTIDM-K-KLTISYPCVMLN	869
tr D7KI06 D7KI06 ARALL	GAKIIQNAARLLERIGRPLELDTDGIWCALPGSFFPENFTFKTIDM-K-KLTISYPCVMLN	868
tr AOA8I6WFC8 AOA8I6WFC8 HORVV	GAKIIQNAARLLVDKIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPGSFFPENFTFKTKAE-K-KLTISYPCVMLN	892
tr AOA452YAR6 AOA452YAR6 ABGTS	GAKIIQNAARLLVDKIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPGSFFPENFTFKTKAE-K-KLTISYPCVMLN	832
tr AOA3B5XXC3 AOA3B5XXC3 WHEAT	GAKIIQNAARLLVDKIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPGSFFPENFTFKTKAE-K-KLTISYPCVMLN	887
tr AOA1D6H8Z0 AOA1D6H8Z0 MAIZE	GAKIIQNAARLLVEKIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPGSFFPENFTFKTKAG-K-KLTISYPCVMLN	865
tr AOA835B357 AOA835B357 9POAL	GAKIIQNAARLLVEKIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPGSFFPENFTFKTKAG-K-KLTISYPCVMLN	878
tr AOA2S3GPC0 AOA2S3GPC0 9POAL	GAKIIQNAARLLVEKIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPGSFFPENFTFKTKAG-K-KLTISYPCVMLN	883
tr AOA368PL62 AOA368PL62 SETIT	GAKIIQNAARLLVEKIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPGSFFPENFTFKTKAG-K-KLTISYPCVMLN	887
tr AOA7I8KHB8 AOA7I8KHB8 SPIIN	GAKIIQNAARLLVEKIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPGSFFPENFTFKTKDGR-K-KLTISYPCVMLN	870
tr AOA6I9QIG1 AOA6I9QIG1 ELAGV	GAKIIQNAARLLVEKIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPGSFFPENFTFKTKDGR-K-KLTISYPCVMLN	868
tr AOA8B8JBC2 AOA8B8JBC2 PHODC	GAKIIQNAARLLVEKIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPGSFFPENFTFKTKDGR-K-KLTISYPCVMLN	868
tr AOA9Q0FIP5 AOA9Q0FIP5 9ROSI	GAKIIQNAARLLVDKIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPGSFFPENFTFKTKDGR-K-KLTISYPCVMLN	885
tr AOA2C9VYJ6 AOA2C9VYJ6 MANES	GAKIIQNAARLLVEKIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPGSFFPENFTFKTKDGR-K-KLTISYPCVMLN	871
tr AOA7J7C034 AOA7J7C034 TRIFW	GAKIIQNAARLLVEKIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPGSFFPENFTFKTKDGR-K-KLTISYPCVMLN	870
tr AOA2N9F976 AOA2N9F976 FAGSY	GAKIIQNAARLLVEKIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPGSFFPENFTFKTKDGR-K-KLTISYPCVMLN	854
tr AOA7N2KME6 AOA7N2KME6 QUELO	GAKIIQNAARLLVEKIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPGSFFPENFTFKTKDGR-K-KLTISYPCVMLN	869
tr AOA4W5MAK2 AOA4W5MAK2 9TELE	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	899
tr AOA8C7Q9V4 AOA8C7Q9V4 ONCMY	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	857
tr AOA6P7J2Q5 AOA6P7J2Q5 9TELE	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	899
tr AOA6P8SZE0 AOA6P8SZE0 GYMAC	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	897
tr AOA8J0QX44 AOA8J0QX44 XENRT	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	896
tr AOA4X2K1K8 AOA4X2K1K8 VOMUR	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	883
tr AOA5F4D2S5 AOA5F4D2S5 CANLF	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	933
tr AOA7J7RQ84 AOA7J7RQ84 RHIFE	GASIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	871
tr AOA6P6D0R3 AOA6P6D0R3 PTEVA	GASIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	890
tr AOA2K6C158 AOA2K6C158 MACNE	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	898
tr F6QAQ1 F6QAQ1 MACMU	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	900
tr G3RQF2 G3RQF2 GORGO	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	877
sp Q07864 DPOE1 HUMAN	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	898
tr AOA2I3S482 AOA2I3S482 PANTR	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	898
tr F6Z911 F6Z911 HORSE	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	898
tr AOA5G2RB90 AOA5G2RB90 PIG	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	871
tr AOA420PL83 AOA420PL83 FUSOX	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	872
tr AOA1V6PGE7 AOA1V6PGE7 PENDC	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	907
tr AOA0G4NU82 AOA0G4NU82 PENCA	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	907
tr AOA1V6TET5 AOA1V6TET5 9EURO	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	907
tr AOA167WJ50 AOA167WJ50 PENCH	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	907
tr AOA3A2Z9P9 AOA3A2Z9P9 9EURO	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	907
tr AOA401L0U3 AOA401L0U3 ASPAW	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	907
tr AOA317VH96 AOA317VH96 ASPEF	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	903
tr AOA117E1M7 AOA117E1M7 ASPNG	GANIIITQARELVEQIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	907
tr AOA1D8PTD0 AOA1D8PTD0 CANAL	GATIIQMARALVERIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	911
tr C5M3R9 C5M3R9 CANNT	GATIIQMARALVERIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	906
tr Q6FNY7 DPOE CANGA	GATIIQMARALVERIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	911
sp P21951 DPOE YEAST	GATIIQMARALVERIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	851
tr AOA7H9HLU1 AOA7H9HLU1 9SACH	GATIIQMARALVERIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	901
tr Q6CUS7 DPOE KLULA	GATIIQMARALVERIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	828
tr Q752B8 DPOE ASHGO	GATIIQMARALVERIGRPLELDTDGIWCLPNTFFENFVVKTSNEKKPKVTTISYPCVMLN	825

tr AOA3P5YCF9 AOA3P5YCF9 BRACM	LSSDHKVDIRLIIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KV-ANPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1195
sp F4HW04 DPOE1 ARATH	---SDVGIRLIIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KV-ANPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1143
tr D7KI06 D7KI06 ARALL	---SDVGIRLIIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KV-ANPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1160
tr AOA8I6WFC8 AOA8I6WFC8 HORVV	---TEANIRFILDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KI-SNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1166
tr AOA452YAR6 AOA452YAR6 ABGTS	---TEANIRFILDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KI-SNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1106
tr AOA3B5XXC3 AOA3B5XXC3 WHEAT	---TEANIRFILDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KI-SNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1161
tr AOA1D6H8Z0 AOA1D6H8Z0 MAIZE	---SDANIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KI-SNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1139
tr AOA835B357 AOA835B357 9POAL	---SDASIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KI-SNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1152
tr AOA2S3GPC0 AOA2S3GPC0 9POAL	---SDASIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KI-SNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1157
tr AOA368PL62 AOA368PL62 SETIT	---SDANIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KI-SNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1161
tr AOA7I8KHB8 AOA7I8KHB8 SPIIN	---SDVGIRSIIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KV-SNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1144
tr AOA6I9QIG1 AOA6I9QIG1 ELAGV	---SDVGIRSIIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KV-SNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1142
tr AOA8B8JBC2 AOA8B8JBC2 PHODC	---SDVGIRSIIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KV-SNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1142
tr AOA9Q0FIP5 AOA9Q0FIP5 9ROSI	---TDIGIRSIIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KV-SNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1159
tr AOA2C9VYJ6 AOA2C9VYJ6 MANES	---LDVGIRSIIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KV-ANPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1145
tr AOA7J7C034 AOA7J7C034 TRIFW	---LDIGIRSIIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KV-TNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1144
tr AOA2N9F976 AOA2N9F976 FAGSY	---SDVGIRSIIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KV-ANPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1128
tr AOA7N2KME6 AOA7N2KME6 QUELO	---SDVGIRSIIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KV-ANPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1143
tr AOA4W5MAK2 AOA4W5MAK2 9TELE	---SLHDDLIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO DV-KNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1175
tr AOA8C7Q9V4 AOA8C7Q9V4 ONCMY	---SLHDDLIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO DV-KNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1133
tr AOA6P7J2Q5 AOA6P7J2Q5 9TELE	---SLHDDLIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO DV-KNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1175
tr AOA6P8SZE0 AOA6P8SZE0 GYMAC	---SLHDDLIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO DV-KNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1173
tr AOA8J0QX44 AOA8J0QX44 XENRT	---SLQDFDIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO DV-KNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1172
tr AOA4X2K1K8 AOA4X2K1K8 VOMUR	---SLQDFDIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO DV-KNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1159
tr AOA5F4D2S5 AOA5F4D2S5 CANLF	---SLQDFDIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO DV-KNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1209
tr AOA7J7RQ84 AOA7J7RQ84 RHIFE	---SLQDFDIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO DV-RNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1147
tr AOA6P6D0R3 AOA6P6D0R3 PTEVA	---SLQDFDIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO DV-KNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1166
tr AOA2K6C158 AOA2K6C158 MACNE	---FFCLDIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO DV-KNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1151
tr F6QAQ1 F6QAQ1 MACMU	---SLQDFDIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO DV-KNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1176
tr G3RQF2 G3RQF2 GORGO	---SLQDFDIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO DV-KNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1153
sp Q07864 DPOE1 HUMAN	---SLQDFDIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO DV-KNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1174
tr AOA2I3S482 AOA2I3S482 PANTR	---SLQDFDIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO DV-KNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1174
tr F6Z911 F6Z911 HORSE	---SLQDFDIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO DV-KNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1147
tr AOA5G2RB90 AOA5G2RB90 PIG	---P-TDTPRALLDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KV-RNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1147
tr AOA420PL83 AOA420PL83 FUSOX	---P-GDMDPRTVIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KL-RNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1182
tr AOA1V6PGE7 AOA1V6PGE7 PENDC	---P-GDMDPRTVIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KL-RNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1182
tr AOA0G4NU82 AOA0G4NU82 PENCA	---P-GDMDPRTVIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KL-RNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1182
tr AOA1V6TET5 AOA1V6TET5 9EURO	---P-GDMDPRTVIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KL-RNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1182
tr AOA167WJ50 AOA167WJ50 PENCH	---P-GDMDPRTVIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KL-RNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1182
tr AOA3A2Z9P9 AOA3A2Z9P9 9EURO	---P-GDMDPRTVIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KL-RNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1182
tr AOA401L0U3 AOA401L0U3 ASPAW	---P-GDMDPRTVIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KL-RNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1182
tr AOA317VH96 AOA317VH96 ASPEF	---P-GDMDPRTVIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KL-RNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1178
tr AOA117E1M7 AOA117E1M7 ASPNG	---P-GDMDPRTVIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO KL-RNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1182
tr AOA1D8PTD0 AOA1D8PTD0 CANAL	---SLNKFSPRVIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO DV-KNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1185
tr C5M3R9 C5M3R9 CANNT	---SLNKFSPRVIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO DV-KNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1180
tr Q6FNY7 DPOE CANGA	---SLNDFDIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO NV-PNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1187
sp P21951 DPOE YEAST	---SLEDLDIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO GV-SNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1127
tr AOA7H9HLU1 AOA7H9HLU1 9SACH	---SLEDLDIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO NI-PNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1177
tr Q6CUS7 DPOE KLULA	---SLNDFDIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO NI-KNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1104
tr Q752B8 DPOE ASHGO	---SLNDFDIRSIDWSYKQRLSSA QKVIITIPAAMO NV-NNPVRV LHPDWLHKKVREK	1101

tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM	KNVDYQGWLEVKRKRKWKVLE	KKKKRRLGDOR	SLKQIES	-----HEIKKKVTVQRRGVG	1335
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	KSNVYQGWLELKKRKKWKVLE	KKKKRRLGDLR	SSNQVDT	-----HEINQKVGQGRGGVG	1282
tr D7KI06 D7KI06_ARALL	KSNVYQGWLELKKRKKWKVLE	KKKKRRLGDLR	SPNQSDA	-----HEINQKVGQGRGGVG	1299
tr A0A816WFC8 A0A816WFC8_HORVV	RSTDYQGWLEAARRKKWKVYRE	QKRRRLGAAA	SSEGPSNNLF	--SARNQSOLHGNRNRS	1319
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6_AEGTS	RSTDYQGWLEAARRKKWKVYRE	QKRRRLGAAA	SSEGPSNNLF	--SARNVSLHGNRNRS	1259
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT	RSTDYQGWLEAARRKKWKVYRE	QKRRRLGAAA	SSEGPSNNLF	--SARNDSQLHGNRNRS	1314
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE	KGTDYQGWLDARRKKWKVYRE	QKRRRLGAAA	FFDDP-NALL	--SARHANQLPVNSRNRS	1293
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357_9POAL	RSDDYQGWLDARRKKWKVYRE	QKRRRLGAAA	FFDGPNTALL	--SSRNANQLPGNSRNRS	1307
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL	RSTDYQGWLDARRKKWKVYRE	QKRRRLGAAA	FFDGPNTALL	--SSRNVSQPLPGNSRNRA	1312
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62_SETIT	RSTDYQGWLDARRKKWKVYRE	QKRRRLGAAA	FFDGPNTALL	--SSRNVSQPLPGNSRNRS	1316
tr A0A718KHB8 A0A718KHB8_SPIIN	RNVYDQGWLDARRKKWKVYRE	QKRRRLGAMD	SSSQFVAMAGNHESMTSNKHN	IAKNGAV	1317
tr A0A619QIG1 A0A619QIG1_ELAGV	RNIDYQAWLEVKRKRKWKVLE	ERKKRRLGITK	MSQQSAGAALKPASFNFYRRHQ	DRNGVS	1301
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2_PHODC	RNVYDQAWLEVKRKRKWKVLE	ERKKRRLGITK	MSQQSAGAALKPASFNFYRRHQ	DRSGVS	1301
tr A0A900FIP5 A0A900FIP5_9ROSI	RNVYDQGWLVVKKRKKWKVLE	RRKKRRLGSLG	FSRGSDFGAHEHLSLGTGEAKQR	TGCVG	1327
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	RNVYDQGWLELKKRKKWKVLE	RRKKRRLGSLR	NSNRANGASEPLGSLINNKKAQHR	TGCVG	1308
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034_TRIWF	KNKDYQGWLELKKRKKWKVLE	RRKKRRLGSSR	PHRADGASEVMEGMISKRGGQAKT	GVG	1301
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976_FAGSY	RNVYDQGWLELKKRKKWKVLE	RRKKRRLSNSR	PPHRGNGVSDLLGGVTNGKDTQ	GRSGVG	1298
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6_QUELO	RNVYDQGWLELKKRKKWKVLE	RRKKRRLSNSR	PPRRGKGVLEVLGDVTHNKDTQ	GRSGVG	1302
tr A0A4W5MAK2 A0A4W5MAK2_9TELE	TQEARLVWLRVYHKKKWLQAR	QRERRRKRRRL	L-----DGEVQAMGGVIRDAGPAT	GLG	1318
tr A0A8C7Q9V4 A0A8C7Q9V4_ONCMY	TQEARLVWLRVYHKKKWLQAR	QRERRRKRRRL	L-----DGEVQAMGGVIRDAGPAT	GLG	1280
tr A0A6P7J2Q5 A0A6P7J2Q5_9TELE	TKERLVWLRVYHKKKWLQAR	QRERRRKRRRL	L-----DGEVQAMGGVIRDAGPAT	GLG	1316
tr A0A6P8SZE0 A0A6P8SZE0_GYMCA	SREELVWLRVYHKKKWLQAR	QRERRRKRRRL	L-----DGEVQAMGGVIRDAGPAT	GLG	1316
tr A0A8J0QX44 A0A8J0QX44_XENTR	TKERLVWLRVYHKKKWLQAR	QRERRRKRRRL	L-----DGDVAPGAGGVIRE-TQAAGL	G	1315
tr A0A4X2K1K8 A0A4X2K1K8_VOMUR	TKERLVWLRVYHKKKWLQAR	QRERRRKRRRL	L-----DGDVAPGAGGVIRE-TQAAGL	G	1301
tr A0A5F4D2S5 A0A5F4D2S5_CANLF	TQEWLVWLRVYHKKKWLQAR	QLRACKRRCRV	L-----VAEGEPLP-GAIRE-RPATGL	G	1351
tr A0A7J7RQ84 A0A7J7RQ84_RHIFE	TQEWLVWLRVYHKKKWLQAR	QLRACKRRCRV	L-----VAEGEPLP-GAIRE-RPATGL	G	1289
tr A0A6P6D0R3 A0A6P6D0R3_PTEVA	TQEWLVWLRVYHKKKWLQAR	QLRACKRRCRV	L-----VAEGEPLP-GAIRE-RPATGL	G	1308
tr A0A2K6CI58 A0A2K6CI58_MACNE	TQEWLVWLRVYHKKKWLQAR	QLRACKRRCRV	L-----VAEGEPLP-GAIRE-RPATGL	G	1293
tr F6QAQ1 F6QAQ1_MACMU	TQEWLVWLRVYHKKKWLQAR	QLRACKRRCRV	L-----VAEGEPLP-GAIRE-RPATGL	G	1318
tr G3RQP2 G3RQP2_GORGO	TQEWLVWLRVYHKKKWLQAR	QLRACKRRCRV	L-----VAEGEPLP-GAIRE-RPATGL	G	1295
sp Q07864 DPOE1_HUMAN	TQEWLVWLRVYHKKKWLQAR	QLRACKRRCRV	L-----VAEGEPLP-GAIRE-RPATGL	G	1316
tr A0A2I3S482 A0A2I3S482_PANTR	TQEWLVWLRVYHKKKWLQAR	QLRACKRRCRV	L-----VAEGEPLP-GAIRE-RPATGL	G	1316
tr F6Z911 F6Z911_HORSE	TQEWLVWLRVYHKKKWLQAR	QLRACKRRCRV	L-----VAEGEPLP-GAIRE-RPATGL	G	1316
tr A0A5G2RB90 A0A5G2RB90_PIG	TQEWLVWLRVYHKKKWLQAR	QLRACKRRCRV	L-----VAEGEPLP-GAIRE-RPATGL	G	1289
tr A0A420PL83 A0A420PL83_FUSOX	ASENYEAFLLMYQKQKWKIQK	QARIRRRQ	L-----GDRRGGAV-NNLQ	G	1271
tr A0A1V6PGE7 A0A1V6PGE7_PENDC	MSEDYEEFLKYQKQKWKIQK	QARIRRRQ	L-----GDRRGGAV-NNLQ	G	1308
tr A0A0G4NU82 A0A0G4NU82_PENCA	MSENYEGFLKYQKQKWKIQK	QARIRRRQ	L-----GDRRGGAV-NNLQ	G	1308
tr A0A1V6TET5 A0A1V6TET5_9EURO	MSENYEGFLKYQKQKWKIQK	QARIRRRQ	L-----GDRRGGAV-NNLQ	G	1308
tr A0A167WJ50 A0A167WJ50_PENCH	MSENYEGFLKYQKQKWKIQK	QARIRRRQ	L-----GDRRGGAV-NNLQ	G	1308
tr A0A3A2Z9P9 A0A3A2Z9P9_9EURO	ITEDYVGFLLKYQKQKWKIQK	QARIRRRQ	L-----GDRRGGAV-NNLQ	G	1309
tr A0A401L0U3 A0A401L0U3_ASPAW	MADDYVGFLLKYQKQKWKIQK	QARIRRRQ	L-----GDRRGGAV-NNLQ	G	1312
tr A0A317VH96 A0A317VH96_ASPAC	MADDYVGFLLKYQKQKWKIQK	QARIRRRQ	L-----GDRRGGAV-NNLQ	G	1308
tr A0A117E1M7 A0A117E1M7_ASPNG	MEDDYVGFLLKYQKQKWKIQK	QARIRRRQ	L-----GDRRGGAV-NNLQ	G	1312
tr A0A1D8PTD0 A0A1D8PTD0_CANAL	MTEDYQGFLFYQKQKWKIQK	QARIRRRQ	L-----GDRRGGAV-NNLQ	G	1304
tr C5M3R9 C5M3R9_CANTT	MLDDYVGFLLKYQKQKWKIQK	QARIRRRQ	L-----GDRRGGAV-NNLQ	G	1299
sp Q6FNY7 DPOE_CANGA	MEEDYVSWLSYQIKWKIQK	QARIRRRQ	L-----GDRRGGAV-NNLQ	G	1304
sp P21951 DPOE_YEAST	MEDDYVGFLLKYQKQKWKIQK	QARIRRRQ	L-----GDRRGGAV-NNLQ	G	1247
tr A0A7H9HLU1 A0A7H9HLU1_9SACH	LDEDYVVKLLYQKQKWKIQK	QARIRRRQ	L-----GDRRGGAV-NNLQ	G	1296
sp Q6CUS7 DPOE_KLULA	MLDDYVGFLLKYQKQKWKIQK	QARIRRRQ	L-----GDRRGGAV-NNLQ	G	1217
sp Q752B8 DPOE_ASHGO	IDEDYVGFLLKYQKQKWKIQK	QARIRRRQ	L-----GDRRGGAV-NNLQ	G	1212

	Linker ←	→ CTD	
tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM	S	FFRRPEEALTSSSHWOI	-----IQLVPS-PQ 1360
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	S	YFRRPEEALTSSSHWOI	-----IQLVPS-PQ 1307
tr D7KI06 D7KI06_ARALL	S	YFRRPEEALTSSSHWOI	-----IQLVPS-PQ 1327
tr A0A816WFC8 A0A816WFC8_HORVV	T	FFQKQELSLFRSHWQ	-----IIQLAPS-TM 1344
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6_AEGTS	T	FFQKQELSLFRSHWQ	-----IIQLAPS-TL 1284
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT	T	FFQKQELSLFRSHWQ	-----IIQLAPS-TL 1339
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE	T	FFQKQELSLFRSHWQ	-----IIQLAPS-TL 1352
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357_9POAL	T	FFQKQELSLFRSHWQ	-----IIQLASS-TV 1332
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL	T	FFQKQELSLFRSHWQ	-----IIQLASS-TT 1337
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62_SETIT	T	FFQKQELSLFRSHWQ	-----IIQLASS-TT 1341
tr A0A718KHB8 A0A718KHB8_SPIIN	S	FFRRQELLLVHNHWQ	-----IIQFVPS-AK 1342
tr A0A619QIG1 A0A619QIG1_ELAGV	S	FFRRQELALVQSHWQ	-----IIQLVPS-TQ 1326
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2_PHODC	S	FFRRQELALVQSHWQ	-----IIQLVPS-TQ 1326
tr A0A900FIP5 A0A900FIP5_9ROSI	S	YFTRPEVVLTRCHWQ	-----IIQLVPS-SL 1352
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	S	YFATHIELSLTRCHWQ	-----IIQLVPS-SH 1333
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034_TRIWF	S	YFRRHEVALTRCHWQ	-----IIQLVPS-SQ 1326
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976_FAGSY	S	YFRRQELALVTRCHWQ	-----IIQLVPS-SE 1323
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6_QUELO	S	YFKRHEASLTRCHWQ	-----IIQLVPS-S- 1326
tr A0A4W5MAK2 A0A4W5MAK2_9TELE	S	FLRRTARSILDMPWQ	-----IVQIAET-SH 1343
tr A0A8C7Q9V4 A0A8C7Q9V4_ONCMY	S	FLRRTARSILDMPWQ	-----IVQIAET-SH 1305
tr A0A6P7J2Q5 A0A6P7J2Q5_9TELE	S	FLRRTARSILDMPWQ	-----IVQIAET-SH 1341
tr A0A6P8SZE0 A0A6P8SZE0_GYMCA	S	FLRRTARSILDMPWQ	-----IVQIAET-SH 1341
tr A0A8J0QX44 A0A8J0QX44_XENTR	S	FLRRTARSILDMPWQ	-----IVQIGES-SH 1340
tr A0A4X2K1K8 A0A4X2K1K8_VOMUR	H	FLRRTARSILDLPWQ	-----VVQISET-NQ 1326
tr A0A5F4D2S5 A0A5F4D2S5_CANLF	G	FLRRTARSILDLPWQ	-----VVQISET-SQ 1376
tr A0A7J7RQ84 A0A7J7RQ84_RHIFE	G	FLRRTARSILDLPWQ	-----VVQISET-TQ 1314
tr A0A6P6D0R3 A0A6P6D0R3_PTEVA	G	FLRRTARSILDLPWQ	-----VVQISET-SQ 1333
tr A0A2K6CI58 A0A2K6CI58_MACNE	S	FLRRTARSILDLPWQ	-----VVQISET-SQ 1318
tr F6QAQ1 F6QAQ1_MACMU	S	FLRRTARSILDLPWQ	-----VVQISET-SQ 1343
tr G3RQP2 G3RQP2_GORGO	S	FLRRTARSILDLPWQ	-----VVQISET-SQ 1320
sp Q07864 DPOE1_HUMAN	S	FLRRTARSILDLPWQ	-----VVQISET-SQ 1341
tr A0A2I3S482 A0A2I3S482_PANTR	S	FLRRTARSILDLPWQ	-----VVQISET-SQ 1341
tr F6Z911 F6Z911_HORSE	G	FLRRTARSILDLPWQ	-----VVQISET-SQ 1341
tr A0A5G2RB90 A0A5G2RB90_PIG	G	FLRRTARSILDLPWQ	-----VVQISET-SQ 1314
tr A0A420PL83 A0A420PL83_FUSOX	Q	TFMKQAHTYMSNHWQ	-----VLHLKAT-ET 1296
tr A0A1V6PGE7 A0A1V6PGE7_PENDC	H	FFRNQAQLLYISTWQ	-----VLQLCET-GR 1333
tr A0A0G4NU82 A0A0G4NU82_PENCA	N	FFRNQAQMLYISTWQ	-----VLQLCET-GV 1333
tr A0A1V6TET5 A0A1V6TET5_9EURO	N	FFRNQAQMLYISTWQ	-----VLQLCET-GV 1333
tr A0A167WJ50 A0A167WJ50_PENCH	N	FFRNQAQMLYISTWQ	-----VLQLCET-GV 1333
tr A0A3A2Z9P9 A0A3A2Z9P9_9EURO	N	YFRNQAELLYINTWQ	-----VLQLRET-GR 1334
tr A0A401L0U3 A0A401L0U3_ASPAW	N	LFRNQAELLYINTWQ	-----VLQLRET-GR 1337
tr A0A317VH96 A0A317VH96_ASPAC	N	LFRNQAELLYINTWQ	-----VLQLRET-GR 1333
tr A0A117E1M7 A0A117E1M7_ASPNG	N	LFRNQAELLYINTWQ	-----VLQLRET-GR 1337
tr A0A1D8PTD0 A0A1D8PTD0_CANAL	G	MIRKRAENIAGTNSWE	-----ILEYKLDPTK 1330
tr C5M3R9 C5M3R9_CANTT	G	MIRKRAENIAGTNSWE	-----ILEYKLDPTK 1325
sp Q6FNY7 DPOE_CANGA	S	MIRKQAEYANSTWE	-----VLQYRDN-YE 1329
sp P21951 DPOE_YEAST	S	MIRKQAEYANSTWE	-----VLQYRDN-YE 1272
tr A0A7H9HLU1 A0A7H9HLU1_9SACH	G	MIRKQAEYANSTWE	-----VLQYRDN-YE 1321
sp Q6CUS7 DPOE_KLULA	N	LIRKHVESYADKNSWE	-----ILQCKPS-ID 1242
sp Q752B8 DPOE_ASHGO	N	IKKHAESYADKNSWE	-----ILQCKPS-SE 1237

tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM	LHRYMCKV	FALLLTDLRR	LGATIIFADFSKVIDT	GKFDLSAAKAYCDSLLTAVGNSDIF	1866
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	LHRYMCKV	FALLLTDLRR	LAIIYADFVKVITD	TKFDLSAAKAYCESLLTVRNSDIF	1847
tr D7K106 D7K106_ARALL	LHRYMCKV	FALLLTDLRR	LGANVIFANFSKII	DTGKVDLSAAKAYCESLLTQTRDLF	1865
tr A0A816WFC8 A0A816WFC8_HORVU	LHNVMKVF	FALLLAEFRK	LGANVIFANFSKII	DTGKVDLPSARAYCDSLLTQTRDLF	1879
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6_AEGTS	LHNVMKVF	FALLLAEFRK	LGANVIFANFSKII	DTGKVDLPSARAYCDSLLTQTRDLF	1819
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT	LHNVMKVF	FALLLAEFRK	LGANVIFANFSKII	DTGKVDLPSARAYCDSLLTQTRDLF	1874
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE	LHNVMKVF	FALLLAEFRK	LGANVIFANFSKII	DTGKVDLPSARAYCDSLLTQTRDLF	1887
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357_9POAL	LHNVMKVF	FALLLAEFRK	LGANVIFANFSKII	DTGKVDLPSARAYCDSLLTQTRDLF	1865
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL	LHNVMKVF	FALLLAEFRK	LGANVIFANFSKII	DTGKVDLPSARAYCDSLLTQTRDLF	1872
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62_SETIT	LHNVMKVF	FALLLAEFRK	LGANVIFANFSKII	DTGKVDLPSARAYCDSLLTQTRDLF	1876
tr A0A718KHB8 A0A718KHB8_SFIIN	LHKLMRKF	FALLLSELRK	LGATIVFANFPKI	IVDTGKTDLPAARAYCDDLKALQARDLL	1874
tr A0A619QIG1 A0A619QIG1_ELAGV	LHKVMRKL	FALLLAEFRK	LGATIFANFSKVIDT	GKIDLSAARAYCDDLKLTQTRDLF	1864
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2_PHODC	LHKVMRKL	FALLLAEFRK	LGATIFANFSKVIDT	GKIDLSAARAYCDDLKLTQTRDLF	1867
tr A0A9Q0FIP5 A0A9Q0FIP5_9ROSI	LHKVMCKV	FALLLAEFRK	LGATIFANFAKVI	IDTGFNLSAAQAYCNSLVTLQSRERF	1907
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	LHKVMCKV	FALLLAEFRK	LGATIFANFSKVIDT	GKLSAAKAYCDSLLTQSRERF	1874
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034_TRIWF	LHKVMCKV	FALLLAEFRK	LGATIFANFSKVIDT	GKSDIAAAKAYCDSLVKALQTRERF	1866
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976_FAGSY	LHKVMCKV	FALLLAEFRK	LGATIFANFSKVIDT	GKFDLSAAKAYCDSLLTQNRDLF	1864
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6_QUELO	LHKVMCKV	FALLLAEFRK	LGATIFANFSKVIDT	GKFDLSAAKAYCDSLLTQNRDLF	1867
tr A0A4W5MAK2 A0A4W5MAK2_9TELE	LHNMMKVF	LQLVAEFRK	LGSTVVYGNFNRI	LLCTKKRRIIDDAIGYVEYITNSIHSREIF	1902
tr A0A8C7Q9V4 A0A8C7Q9V4_ONCMY	LHNMMKVF	LQLVAEFRK	LGSTVVYGNFNRI	LLCTKKRRIIDDAIGYVEYITNSIHSREIF	1864
tr A0A6P7J2Q5 A0A6P7J2Q5_9TELE	LHNMMKVF	LQLVAEFRK	LGSTVVYGNFNRI	LLCTKKRRIIDDAIGYVEYITNSIHSREIF	1900
tr A0A6P8SZE0 A0A6P8SZE0_GYMCA	LHNMMKVF	LQLVSEFRK	LGSTVVYGNFNRI	LLCTKKRRIIDDAIGYVEYITNSIHSREIF	1900
tr A0A8J0QX44 A0A8J0QX44_XENTR	LHNMMKVF	LQLVAEFRK	LGSSVVIYANFNRI	LLCTKKRRIIDDAIGYVEYITNSIHSREIF	1898
tr A0A4X2K1K8 A0A4X2K1K8_VOMUR	LHSMMRKL	LQLVAEFRK	LGSSVVIYANFNRI	LLCTKKRRIIDDAIGYVEYITNSIHSREIF	1885
tr A0A5F4D2S5 A0A5F4D2S5_CANLF	LHNMMKVF	LQLVAEFRK	LGSSVVIYANFNRI	LLCTKKRRIIDDAIGYVEYITNSIHSREIF	1935
tr A0A7J7RQ84 A0A7J7RQ84_RHIFE	LHGVMRKL	LQLVAEFRK	LGSSVVIYANFNRI	LLCTKKRRIIDDAIGYVEYITNSIHSREIF	1873
tr A0A6P6D0R3 A0A6P6D0R3_PTEVA	LHSMMRKL	LQLVAEFRK	LGSSVVIYANFNRI	LLCTKKRRIIDDAIGYVEYITNSIHSREIF	1892
tr A0A2K6C1S8 A0A2K6C1S8_MACNE	LHNMMKVF	LQLVAEFRK	LGSSVVIYANFNRI	LLCTKKRRIIDDAIGYVEYITNSIHSREIF	1877
tr F6QAQ1 F6QAQ1_MACMU	LHNMMKVF	LQLVAEFRK	LGSSVVIYANFNRI	LLCTKKRRIIDDAIGYVEYITNSIHSREIF	1902
tr G3RQP2 G3RQP2_GORGO	LHNMMKVF	LQLVAEFRK	LGSSVVIYANFNRI	LLCTKKRRIIDDAIGYVEYITNSIHSREIF	1879
sp Q07864 DPOE1_HUMAN	LHNMMKVF	LQLVAEFRK	LGSSVVIYANFNRI	LLCTKKRRIIDDAIGYVEYITNSIHSREIF	1900
tr A0A2I3S482 A0A2I3S482_PANTR	LHNMMKVF	LQLVAEFRK	LGSSVVIYANFNRI	LLCTKKRRIIDDAIGYVEYITNSIHSREIF	1900
tr F6Z911 F6Z911_HORSE	LHNMMKVF	LQLVAEFRK	LGSSVVIYANFNRI	LLCTKKRRIIDDAIGYVEYITNSIHSREIF	1900
tr A0A5G2RB90 A0A5G2RB90_PIG	LHGMMRKL	LQLVAEFRK	LGSSVVIYANFNRI	LLCTKKRRIIDDAIGYVEYITNSIHSREIF	1873
tr A0A420PL83 A0A420PL83_FUSOX	VQMSRRAF	QQLMADFRF	GVSVIYANFNRI	LLCTKKRRIIDDAIGYVEYITNSIHSREIF	1847
tr A0A1V6PGE7 A0A1V6PGE7_PENDC	VFLLSRKS	FORLMAEFRF	GVSNVIFASPT	RLRLQTTKTEVGNAYAYSQVVLKIRANPSF	1885
tr A0A0G4NU82 A0A0G4NU82_PENCA	VFLLSRKS	FORLMAEFRF	GVSNVIFASPT	RLRLQTTKTEVGNAYAYSQVVLKIRANPSF	1884
tr A0A1V6TET5 A0A1V6TET5_9EURO	VFLMSRKS	FORLMAEFRF	GVSHVIFASPT	RLRLQTTKTEVGNAYAYSQVVLKIRANPSF	1884
tr A0A167WJ50 A0A167WJ50_PENCH	VFLMSRKS	FORLMAEFRF	GVSHVIFASPT	RLRLQTTKTEVGNAYAYSQVVLKIRANPSF	1884
tr A0A3A2Z9P9 A0A3A2Z9P9_9EURO	VFLMSRKS	FORLMAEFRF	GVSHVIFASPT	RLRLQTTKTEVGNAYAYSQVVLKIRANPSF	1887
tr A0A401L0U3 A0A401L0U3_ASPAW	VFLMSRKS	FORLMAEFRF	GVSNVIFASPT	RLRLQTTKTEVGNAYAYSQVVLKIRANPSF	1891
tr A0A317VH96 A0A317VH96_ASPEC	VFLMSRKS	FORLMAEFRF	GVSNVIFASPT	RLRLQTTKTEVGNAYAYSQVVLKIRANPSF	1887
tr A0A117E1M7 A0A117E1M7_ASPNG	VRLMSRKS	FORLMAEFRF	GVSNVIFASPT	RLRLQTTKTEVGNAYAYSQVVLKIRANPSF	1891
tr A0A1D8PTD0 A0A1D8PTD0_CANAL	VHNLTKKAL	LQLLSEFRK	MGQVIFANRNK	MLIQTSKISVENSAYGQYLKAAKRSKPLF	1877
tr C5M3R9 C5M3R9_CANTT	VHNLTKKAL	LQLLSEFRK	MGQVIFANRNK	MLIQTSKISVENSAYGQYLKAAKRSKPLF	1872
sp Q6FNY7 DPOE_CANGA	IHNLTAKS	LQLLMNEFRF	LGSTVVSADR	NRLIKTKNISPETCYAYSHYMKISRSNPMF	1891
sp P21951 DPOE_YEAST	VHNLTKKAL	LQLLMNEFRF	LGSTVVSADR	NRLIKTKNISPETCYAYSHYMKISRSNPMF	1835
tr A0A7H9HLU1 A0A7H9HLU1_9SACH	IHNLTAKS	LQLLMNEFRF	LGSTVVSADR	NRLIKTKNISPETCYAYSHYMKISRSNPMF	1882
sp Q6CUS7 DPOE_KLULA	IHTLTKAV	LQLLNEFRK	LAGSLLIFADR	NKLLIKTKQKRSVENSAYGQYLKAAKRSKPLF	1798
sp Q752B8 DPOE_ASHGO	VNMLTKAL	LQLLNEFRF	MGSTVVSADR	NRLIKTKNISPETCYAYSHYMKISRSNPMF	1793

tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM	-----	ILFLKLCFAVMKRNLLKY	INVKEFAAAEF	FLDPGPFILPNVA	SNCDAYD	2082
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	-----	VMRKSLLYIKVKECAAAE	FLDPGPFILPNVA	SNCDAYD	2048	
tr D7K106 D7K106_ARALL	-----	LISGNLVLETMFTNRV	MKGLLKYIKVKECAAAE	FLDPGPFILPNVA	SNCDAYD	2128
tr A0A816WFC8 A0A816WFC8_HORVU	-----	-----	RMKRLKLVVRKEFAPEAQ	FDPQPCASFTLNPVI	SYGNDCR	2110
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6_AEGTS	-----	-----	RMKRLKLVVRKEFAPEAQ	FDPQPCASFTLNPVI	SYGNDCR	2050
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT	-----	-----	RMKRLKLVVRKEFAPEAQ	FDPQPCASFTLNPVI	SYGNDCR	2105
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE	-----	-----	RMKRLKLVVRKEFAPEAQ	FDPQPCASFTLNPVI	SYGNDCR	2113
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357_9POAL	-----	-----	RMKRLKLVVRKEFAPEAQ	FDPQPCASFTLNPVI	SYGNDCR	2095
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL	-----	-----	RMKRLKLVVRKEFAPEAQ	FDPQPCASFTLNPVI	SYGNDCR	2100
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62_SETIT	-----	-----	RMKRLKLVVRKEFAPEAQ	FDPQPCASFTLNPVI	SYGNDCR	2104
tr A0A718KHB8 A0A718KHB8_SFIIN	-----	-----	RMKRLKLVVRKEFAPEAQ	FDPQPCASFTLNPVI	SYGNDCR	2105
tr A0A619QIG1 A0A619QIG1_ELAGV	-----	-----	RMKRLKLVVRKEFAPEAQ	FDPQPCASFTLNPVI	SYGNDCR	2099
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2_PHODC	-----	-----	RMKRLKLVVRKEFAPEAQ	FDPQPCASFTLNPVI	SYGNDCR	2102
tr A0A9Q0FIP5 A0A9Q0FIP5_9ROSI	-----	-----	VMRNLKLVVRKEFAPEAQ	FDPQPCASFTLNPVI	SYGNDCR	2147
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	-----	-----	VMRNLKLVVRKEFAPEAQ	FDPQPCASFTLNPVI	SYGNDCR	2113
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034_TRIWF	-----	-----	VMRNLKLVVRKEFAPEAQ	FDPQPCASFTLNPVI	SYGNDCR	2093
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976_FAGSY	-----	-----	VMRNLKLVVRKEFAPEAQ	FDPQPCASFTLNPVI	SYGNDCR	2056
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6_QUELO	-----	-----	VMRNLKLVVRKEFAPEAQ	FDPQPCASFTLNPVI	SYGNDCR	2096
tr A0A4W5MAK2 A0A4W5MAK2_9TELE	-----	-----	KLKRDLLRLVDVGEFSEEAQ	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2166
tr A0A8C7Q9V4 A0A8C7Q9V4_ONCMY	-----	-----	KLKRDLLRLVDVGEFSEEAQ	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2134
tr A0A6P7J2Q5 A0A6P7J2Q5_9TELE	-----	-----	KLKRDLLRLVDVGEFSEEAQ	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2171
tr A0A6P8SZE0 A0A6P8SZE0_GYMCA	-----	-----	KLKRDLLRLVDVGEFSEEAQ	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2171
tr A0A8J0QX44 A0A8J0QX44_XENTR	-----	-----	KLKRDLLRLVDVGEFSEEAQ	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2168
tr A0A4X2K1K8 A0A4X2K1K8_VOMUR	-----	-----	KLKRDLLRLVDVGEFSEEAQ	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2149
tr A0A5F4D2S5 A0A5F4D2S5_CANLF	-----	-----	KLKRDLLRLVDVGEFSEEAQ	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2154
tr A0A7J7RQ84 A0A7J7RQ84_RHIFE	-----	-----	KLKRDLLRLVDVGEFSEEAQ	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2137
tr A0A6P6D0R3 A0A6P6D0R3_PTEVA	-----	-----	KLKRDLLRLVDVGEFSEEAQ	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2164
tr A0A2K6C1S8 A0A2K6C1S8_MACNE	-----	-----	KLKRDLLRLVDVGEFSEEAQ	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2145
tr F6QAQ1 F6QAQ1_MACMU	-----	-----	KLKRDLLRLVDVGEFSEEAQ	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2170
tr G3RQP2 G3RQP2_GORGO	-----	-----	KLKRDLLRLVDVGEFSEEAQ	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2147
sp Q07864 DPOE1_HUMAN	-----	-----	KLKRDLLRLVDVGEFSEEAQ	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2168
tr A0A2I3S482 A0A2I3S482_PANTR	-----	-----	KLKRDLLRLVDVGEFSEEAQ	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2168
tr F6Z911 F6Z911_HORSE	-----	-----	KLKRDLLRLVDVGEFSEEAQ	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2168
tr A0A5G2RB90 A0A5G2RB90_PIG	-----	-----	KLKRDLLRLVDVGEFSEEAQ	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2139
tr A0A420PL83 A0A420PL83_FUSOX	-----	-----	LRKELLALFVREFSKDGT	FTNPSERLQISDSTMMR	2065	
tr A0A1V6PGE7 A0A1V6PGE7_PENDC	-----	-----	LRKELLALFVREFSKDGT	FTNPSERLQISDSTMMR	2112	
tr A0A0G4NU82 A0A0G4NU82_PENCA	-----	-----	LRKELLALFVREFSKDGT	FTNPSERLQISDSTMMR	2110	
tr A0A1V6TET5 A0A1V6TET5_9EURO	-----	-----	LRKELLALFVREFSKDGT	FTNPSERLQISDSTMMR	2110	
tr A0A167WJ50 A0A167WJ50_PENCH	-----	-----	LRKELLALFVREFSKDGT	FTNPSERLQISDSTMMR	2110	
tr A0A3A2Z9P9 A0A3A2Z9P9_9EURO	-----	-----	LRKELLALFVREFSKDGT	FTNPSERLQISDSTMMR	2111	
tr A0A401L0U3 A0A401L0U3_ASPAW	-----	-----	LRKELLALFVREFSKDGT	FTNPSERLQISDSTMMR	2114	
tr A0A317VH96 A0A317VH96_ASPEC	-----	-----	LRKELLALFVREFSKDGT	FTNPSERLQISDSTMMR	2110	
tr A0A117E1M7 A0A117E1M7_ASPNG	-----	-----	LRKELLALFVREFSKDGT	FTNPSERLQISDSTMMR	2114	
tr A0A1D8PTD0 A0A1D8PTD0_CANAL	-----	-----	ILKLELLIFDVRDPSKAT	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2108
tr C5M3R9 C5M3R9_CANTT	-----	-----	ILKLELLIFDVRDPSKAT	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2104
sp Q6FNY7 DPOE_CANGA	-----	-----	ILKLELLIFDVRDPSKAT	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2114
sp P21951 DPOE_YEAST	-----	-----	ILKLELLIFDVRDPSKAT	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2058
tr A0A7H9HLU1 A0A7H9HLU1_9SACH	-----	-----	ILKLELLIFDVRDPSKAT	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2108
sp Q6CUS7 DPOE_KLULA	-----	-----	ILKLELLIFDVRDPSKAT	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2022
sp Q752B8 DPOE_ASHGO	-----	-----	ILKLELLIFDVRDPSKAT	FRDPCRSYILPEVI	HSNFCR	2017

Accession	Gene	Protein	Sequence	Position
tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9	BRACM	I GRDPALLT-----	←EKEWQADISCGSKIYDREQMENSLLQMVRRQERMYHMDDLV	2132
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	ARATH	I CRDPALLT-----	EKEWQADISCGSKIYDREQMESSLLEVMRQERMYHMDDV	2098
tr D7KI06 D7KI06	ARALL	I CRDPALLT-----	EKEWQADISCGSKIYDREQMESSLLEVMRQERMYHMDDLV	2178
tr A0A8I6WFC8 A0A8I6WFC8	HORVV	I CRDSTLQ-----	GHEWRRQAVPQGGQPYHREEMENALLQIVRQERLYHLQDVL	2159
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6	ABGTS	I LCRDSTLQ-----	GHEWRRQAVPQGGQPYHREEMENALLQIVRQERLYHLQDVL	2099
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3	WHEAT	I LCRDSTLQ-----	GHEWRRQAVPQGGQPYHREEMENALLQIVRQERLYHLQDVL	2159
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0	MAIZE	I LCRDSTLQ-----	GHEWRRQAVPQGGQPYHREEMENALLQIVRQERLYHLQDVL	2162
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357	9POAL	I LCRDSTLQ-----	GHEWRRQAVPQGGQPYHREEMENALLQIVRQERLYHLQDVL	2144
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0	9POAL	I LCRDSTLQ-----	GHEWRRQAVPQGGQPYHREEMENALLQIVRQERLYHLQDVL	2149
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62	SETIT	I LCRDSTLQ-----	GHEWRRQAVPQGGQPYHREEMENALLQIVRQERLYHLQDVL	2153
tr A0A7I8KHB8 A0A7I8KHB8	SPIIN	I LSRDSALL-----	EQEWRRAVPPQGGQPYDRGQMESALLQIVRQERLYHLQDVL	2154
tr A0A6I9QIG1 A0A6I9QIG1	ELAGV	I LCRDSALS-----	DNEWRRQAVPQGGQSYNREQMENSLLQIVRQERLYHLQDVL	2148
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2	PHODC	I LCRDSALS-----	DSWRRQAVPQGGQSYNREQMENSLLQIVRQERLYHLQDVL	2151
tr A0A9Q0FIP5 A0A9Q0FIP5	9ROSI	I LCRDSTALL-----	SQWRRQAVPQGGQPYDREVMENALLQIVRQERLYHLQDVL	2196
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6	MANES	I LCRDSTALL-----	AQWRRQAVPQGGQPYDREVMENALLQIVRQERLYHLQDVL	2162
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034	TRIFW	I LCRDSALL-----	AHEWRRQAVPQGGQPYDREVMENALLQIVRQERLYHLQDVL	2142
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976	FAGSY	I LCRDSALL-----	AQWRRQAVPQGGQPYDREVMENALLQIVRQERLYHLQDVL	2105
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6	QUELO	I LCRDSTALL-----	AQWRRQAVPQGGQPYDREVMENALLQIVRQERLYHLQDVL	2145
tr A0A4W5MAK2 A0A4W5MAK2	9TELE	I LCKDPSVAQDG-----	SVLPQWFL--SNQIYQYETES IEMALVEALQKLLMAYTLLQDLA	2218
tr A0A8C7Q9V4 A0A8C7Q9V4	ONCMY	I LCKDPSVAQDG-----	SVLPQWFL--SNQIYQYETES IEMALVEALQKLLMAYTLLQDLA	2186
tr A0A6P7J2Q5 A0A6P7J2Q5	9TELE	I LCKDPSVAQDG-----	SVLPQWFL--SNQIYQYETES IEMALVEALQKLLMAYTLLQDLA	2223
tr A0A6P8SZE0 A0A6P8SZE0	GYMAC	I LCKDPSVAQDG-----	SVLPQWFL--SNQIYQYETES IEMALVEALQKLLMAYTLLQDLV	2223
tr A0A8J0QX44 A0A8J0QX44	XENTR	I LCKDPAINQDG-----	SVLPQWFL--TNQIYQYETES IEMALVEALQKLLMAYTLLQDLV	2220
tr A0A4X2K1K8 A0A4X2K1K8	VOMUR	I LCKDPAINQDG-----	SILPQWFL--TNQIYQYETES IEMALVEALQKLLMAYTLLQDLV	2201
tr A0A5F4D2S5 A0A5F4D2S5	CANLF	I LCKEFAFSQDG-----	AVLPQWFL--SNQIYQYETES IEMALVEALQKLLMAYTLLQDLV	2206
tr A0A7J7RQ84 A0A7J7RQ84	RHIFE	I LCRDPSVQDG-----	AVLPQWFL--SNQIYQYETES IEMALVEALQKLLMAYTLLQDLV	2189
tr A0A6P6D0R3 A0A6P6D0R3	PTEVA	I LCRDPSVQDG-----	AVLPQWFL--SNQIYQYETES IEMALVEALQKLLMAYTLLQDLA	2216
tr A0A2K6C158 A0A2K6C158	MACNE	I LCKDSSFSQDG-----	AVLPQWFL--SNQIYQYETES IEMALVEALQKLLMAYTLLQDLV	2197
tr F6QAQ1 F6QAQ1	MACMU	I LCKDSSFSQDG-----	AVLPQWFL--SNQIYQYETES IEMALVEALQKLLMAYTLLQDLV	2222
tr G3RQP2 G3RQP2	GORGO	I LCKDSSFSQDG-----	AVLPQWFL--SNQIYQYETES IEMALVEALQKLLMAYTLLQDLV	2199
sp Q07864 DPOE1_HUMAN	HUMAN	I LCKDSSFSQDG-----	AVLPQWFL--SNQIYQYETES IEMALVEALQKLLMAYTLLQDLV	2220
tr A0A2I3S482 A0A2I3S482	PANTR	I LCKDSSFSQDG-----	AVLPQWFL--SNQIYQYETES IEMALVEALQKLLMAYTLLQDLV	2220
tr F6Z911 F6Z911	HORSE	I LCKDPSFSQDG-----	AVLPQWFL--SNQIYQYETES IEMALVEALQKLLMAYTLLQDLV	2220
tr A0A5G2RB90 A0A5G2RB90	PIG	I LCKEFSFSQDG-----	AVLPQWFL--SNQIYQYETES IEMALVEALQKLLMAYTLLQDLV	2191
tr A0A420PL83 A0A420PL83	FUSOX	I LCRDEDLFGE-----	GAWRRQAVPQGGQPYEFDRVAIEERLLGIVESWIVVWQTQDLK	2114
tr A0A1V6PGE7 A0A1V6PGE7	PENDC	I LCRDEDLVDPDG-DTSK-TPKPWR	PECHAEYDRLAQEEILLIGQIYQYIVGWQTQDLK	2168
tr A0A0G4NU82 A0A0G4NU82	PENCA	I LCRDEDLVDPDASAEASK-STQFWR	PECHAEYDRLAQEEILLIGQIYQYIVGWQTQDLK	2167
tr A0A1V6TET5 A0A1V6TET5	9EURO	I LCRDEDLVDPDASAEASK-STQFWR	PECHAEYDRLAQEEILLIGQIYQYIVGWQTQDLK	2167
tr A0A167WJ50 A0A167WJ50	PENCH	I LCRDEDLVDPDASAEASK-STQFWR	PECHAEYDRLAQEEILLIGQIYQYIVGWQTQDLK	2167
tr A0A3A2Z9P9 A0A3A2Z9P9	9EURO	I LCRDEDLVDPDGSVDVT-TTKFWR	PECHAEYDRLAQEEILLIGQIYQYIVGWQTQDLK	2168
tr A0A401L0U3 A0A401L0U3	ASPAW	I LCRDEDLVDPDGSVDASKTSTKFWR	PECHAEYDRLAQEEILLIGQIYQYIVGWQTQDLK	2172
tr A0A317VH96 A0A317VH96	ASPEC	I LCRDEDLVDPDGSVDASKTSTKFWR	PECHAEYDRLAQEEILLIGQIYQYIVGWQTQDLK	2168
tr A0A117E1M7 A0A117E1M7	ASPNG	I LCRDEDLVDPDGSVDASKTSTKFWR	PECHAEYDRLAQEEILLIGQIYQYIVGWQTQDLK	2172
tr A0A1D8PTD0 A0A1D8PTD0	CANAL	I LCREE-----	INWNR--LNRKRAYNKIALEEEIINQFNKLFVKFYQDLD	2153
tr C5M3R9 C5M3R9	CANTT	I FCCQNE-----	ESVWNR--SNCHKPYDKSAIEEIGIISQLNKLKFKVYFQDLD	2149
sp Q6FNY7 DPOE_CANGA	CANGA	I LCRDGL-----	DGKFC--PDKSINDSLLEQHEMIQNLAEYQTYITQDLR	2159
sp P21951 DPOE_YEAST	YEAST	I FCKAAP-----	ESIFSC--VRCRKAFAFQVLLQEHLLQKLRSDIESYLLQDLR	2103
tr A0A7H9HLU1 A0A7H9HLU1	9SACH	I FCRDNF-----	STIFDC--SNCHKELNKRGLLQERLIHNIYVEIESYLLQDLR	2153
sp Q6CUS7 DPOE_KLULA	KLULA	I ICRESM-----	ERVFTQ--QSNRSLNKNLIEEHVIERLQAVQVATYITQDVK	2067
sp Q752B8 DPOE_ASHGO	ASHGO	I ICMSDL-----	RSMFKC--SKCYRTLKRPFIENLQKLRQTLQTYAITSQDLR	2062

Accession	Gene	Protein	Sequence	Position
tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9	BRACM	C FRCRQVKAHHLTEQCGSGSFRCKESGS-----		2161
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	ARATH	C FRCRQVKAHHLTEQCGSGSFRCKESGS-----		2127
tr D7KI06 D7KI06	ARALL	C FRCRQVKAHHLTEQCGSGSFRCKESGS-----		2207
tr A0A8I6WFC8 A0A8I6WFC8	HORVV	C VFCRQVKAHHLVSEOCGSGSFRCKEEAP-----		2188
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6	ABGTS	C VFCRQVKAHHLVSEOCGSGSFRCKEEAP-----		2128
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3	WHEAT	C VFCRQVKAHHLVSEOCGSGSFRCKEEAP-----		2183
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0	MAIZE	C VFCRQVKAHHLVSEOCGSGSFRCKEEAP-----		2191
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357	9POAL	C LFCRQVKAHHLSEOCGSGSFRCKEESS-----		2173
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0	9POAL	C LFCRQVKAHHLSEOCGSGSFRCKEESS-----		2178
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62	SETIT	C LFCRQVKAHHLSEOCGSGSFRCKEESS-----		2182
tr A0A7I8KHB8 A0A7I8KHB8	SPIIN	C LFCRQVKAHHLSEOCGSGSFRCKEESS-----		2183
tr A0A6I9QIG1 A0A6I9QIG1	ELAGV	C LFCRQVKAHHLSEOCGSGSFRCKEDSF-----		2177
tr A0A8B8JBC2 A0A8B8JBC2	PHODC	C LFCRQVKAHHLSEOCGSGSFRCKEDSF-----		2180
tr A0A9Q0FIP5 A0A9Q0FIP5	9ROSI	C LFCRQVKAHHLSEOCGSGSFRCKEDVS-----		2225
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6	MANES	C LFCRQVKAHHLSEOCGSGSFRCKEDVS-----		2191
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034	TRIFW	C LFCRQVKAHHLSEOCGSGSFRCKEDVS-----		2171
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976	FAGSY	C LFCRQVKAHHLSEOCGSGSFRCKEDLT-----		2134
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6	QUELO	C LFCRQVKAHHLSEOCGSGSFRCKEDLT-----		2174
tr A0A4W5MAK2 A0A4W5MAK2	9TELE	C CAKCRGVKEANMPLYCAGDFELTFFPTK-----		2247
tr A0A8C7Q9V4 A0A8C7Q9V4	ONCMY	C CAKCRGVKEANMPLYCAGDFELTFFPTK-----		2215
tr A0A6P7J2Q5 A0A6P7J2Q5	9TELE	C CNKCRGVKEANMPLYCAGDFELTFFSAK-----		2252
tr A0A6P8SZE0 A0A6P8SZE0	GYMAC	C CTCCRGVKEANMPLYCAGDFELTFFSAK-----		2252
tr A0A8J0QX44 A0A8J0QX44	XENTR	C CMKCRGVKEANMPLYCAGDFELTFFSAK-----		2249
tr A0A4X2K1K8 A0A4X2K1K8	VOMUR	C LKCRGVKEANMPLYCAGDFELTFFSAK-----		2230
tr A0A5F4D2S5 A0A5F4D2S5	CANLF	C LKCRGVKETHMPTVYCAAGDFELTFFSAK-----		2266
tr A0A7J7RQ84 A0A7J7RQ84	RHIFE	C LKCRGVKETHMPTVYCAAGDFELTFFSAK-----		2218
tr A0A6P6D0R3 A0A6P6D0R3	PTEVA	C LKCRGVKETHMPTVYCAAGDFELTFFSAK-----		2245
tr A0A2K6C158 A0A2K6C158	MACNE	C LKCRGVKETHMPTVYCAAGDFELTFFSAK-----		2226
tr F6QAQ1 F6QAQ1	MACMU	C LKCRGVKETHMPTVYCAAGDFELTFFSAK-----		2251
tr G3RQP2 G3RQP2	GORGO	C LKCRGVKETHMPTVYCAAGDFELTFFSAK-----		2228
sp Q07864 DPOE1_HUMAN	HUMAN	C LKCRGVKETHMPTVYCAAGDFELTFFSAK-----		2249
tr A0A2I3S482 A0A2I3S482	PANTR	C LKCRGVKETHMPTVYCAAGDFELTFFSAK-----		2249
tr F6Z911 F6Z911	HORSE	C LKCRGVKETHMPTVYCAAGDFELTFFSAK-----		2249
tr A0A5G2RB90 A0A5G2RB90	PIG	C VFCRQVKAHHLVSEOCGSGSFRCKEEAP-----		2220
tr A0A420PL83 A0A420PL83	FUSOX	C CAKCRGVKEANMPLYCAGDFELTFFSAK-----		2143
tr A0A1V6PGE7 A0A1V6PGE7	PENDC	C CFKCRGLKISEFMEHCAGAWTATVDRK-----		2197
tr A0A0G4NU82 A0A0G4NU82	PENCA	C CFKCRGLKISEFMEHCAGAWTATVDRK-----		2196
tr A0A1V6TET5 A0A1V6TET5	9EURO	C CFKCRGLKISEFMEHCAGAWTATVDRK-----		2196
tr A0A167WJ50 A0A167WJ50	PENCH	C CFKCRGLKISEFMEHCAGAWTATVDRK-----		2196
tr A0A3A2Z9P9 A0A3A2Z9P9	9EURO	C CFKCRGLKISEFMEHCAGAWTATVDRK-----		2197
tr A0A401L0U3 A0A401L0U3	ASPAW	C CFKCRGLKISEFMEHCAGAWTATVDRK-----		2201
tr A0A317VH96 A0A317VH96	ASPEC	C CFKCRGLKISEFMEHCAGAWTATVDRK-----		2197
tr A0A117E1M7 A0A117E1M7	ASPNG	C CSKCGTLKLVDFMEHCAGAWTATVDRK-----		2201
tr A0A1D8PTD0 A0A1D8PTD0	CANAL	C CNKCRQIRQNNMDLHCKSGNWIETVDYH-----		2182
tr C5M3R9 C5M3R9	CANTT	C CNKCRQIRGNYMDLHCKSGNWIETVDYH-----		2178
sp Q6FNY7 DPOE_CANGA	CANGA	C CFKCRHTVKRDLMTNCKSGNWCCTTKPE-----		2188
sp P21951 DPOE_YEAST	YEAST	C CSRCRHKVRRDYMSAHCPCAGAWTATVDRK-----		2132
tr A0A7H9HLU1 A0A7H9HLU1	9SACH	C CFKCRNVKQDNMSDYCAGSFRCKESGS-----		2182
sp Q6CUS7 DPOE_KLULA	KLULA	C CNKCRHKIKEDAMSPYCAAGSFRCKESGS-----		2096
sp Q752B8 DPOE_ASHGO	ASHGO	C CAKCRKIKSDTMSAYCAAGSFRCKESGS-----		2091

//End of pol ε sequences from all the four eukaryotes			
tr A0A3P5YCF9 A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM	--	2205	
sp F4HW04 DPOE1_ARATH	--	2161	
tr D7KI06 D7KI06_ARALL	--	2241	
tr A0A8I6WFC8 A0A8I6WFC8_HORVV	--	2224	
tr A0A452YAR6 A0A452YAR6_AEGTS	--	2160	
tr A0A3B5XXC3 A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT	--	2215	
tr A0A1D6H8Z0 A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE	--	2223	
tr A0A835B357 A0A835B357_9POAL	--	2205	
tr A0A2S3GPC0 A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL	--	2210	
tr A0A368PL62 A0A368PL62_SETIT	--	2214	
tr A0A7I8KHB8 A0A7I8KHB8_SPIIN	--	2215	
tr A0A6I9QIG1 A0A6I9QIG1_ELAGV	--	2209	
tr A0A8B8JBU2 A0A8B8JBU2_PHODC	--	2212	
tr A0A9Q0FIP5 A0A9Q0FIP5_9ROSI	--	2257	
tr A0A2C9VYJ6 A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES	--	2223	
tr A0A7J7C034 A0A7J7C034_TRIWF	--	2203	
tr A0A2N9F976 A0A2N9F976_FAGSY	--	2166	
tr A0A7N2KME6 A0A7N2KME6_QUELO	--	2206	
tr A0A4W5MAK2 A0A4W5MAK2_9TELE	--	2286	
tr A0A8C7Q9V4 A0A8C7Q9V4_ONCMY	--	2254	
tr A0A6P7J2Q5 A0A6P7J2Q5_9TELE	--	2292	
tr A0A6P8SZE0 A0A6P8SZE0_GYMAC	TS	2298	
tr A0A8J0QX44 A0A8J0QX44_XENTR	--	2286	
tr A0A4X2K1K8 A0A4X2K1K8_VOMUR	--	2267	
tr A0A5F4D2S5 A0A5F4D2S5_CANLF	--	2319	
tr A0A7J7RQ84 A0A7J7RQ84_RHIFE	--	2255	
tr A0A6P6D0R3 A0A6P6D0R3_PTEVA	--	2282	
tr A0A2K6CI58 A0A2K6CI58_MACNE	--	2263	
tr F6QAQ1 F6QAQ1_MACMU	--	2288	
tr G3RQP2 G3RQP2_GORGO	--	2265	
sp Q07864 DPOE1_HUMAN	--	2286	
tr A0A2I3S482 A0A2I3S482_PANTR	--	2286	
tr F6Z911 F6Z911_HORSE	--	2286	
tr A0A5G2RB90 A0A5G2RB90_PIG	--	2257	
tr A0A420PL83 A0A420PL83_FUSOX	--	2175	
tr A0A1V6PGE7 A0A1V6PGE7_PENDC	--	2229	
tr A0A0G4NU82 A0A0G4NU82_PENCA	--	2228	
tr A0A1V6TET5 A0A1V6TET5_9EURO	--	2228	
tr A0A167WJ50 A0A167WJ50_PENCH	--	2228	
tr A0A3A2Z9P9 A0A3A2Z9P9_9EURO	--	2229	
tr A0A401L0U3 A0A401L0U3_ASPAW	--	2233	
tr A0A317VH96 A0A317VH96_ASPEC	--	2229	
tr A0A117E1M7 A0A117E1M7_ASPNG	--	2233	
tr A0A1D8PTD0 A0A1D8PTD0_CANAL	--	2211	
tr C5M3R9 C5M3R9_CANTT	--	2207	
sp Q6FNY7 DPOE_CANGA	--	2217	
sp P21951 DPOE_YEAST	--	2162	
tr A0A7H9HLU1 A0A7H9HLU1_9SACH	--	2212	
sp Q6CUS7 DPOE_KLULA	--	2125	
sp Q752B8 DPOE_ASHGO	--	2120	

From PLANTS

A0A3P5YCF9_BRACM, *Brassica campestris*
D7KI06_ARALL, *Arabidopsis lyrata*
A0A452YAR6_AEGTS, *Aegilops tauschii*
A0A1D6H8Z0_MAIZE, *Zea mays*
A0A2S3GPC0_9POAL, *Panicum hallii*
A0A7I8KHB8_SPIIN, *Spirodela intermedia*
A0A8B8JBU2_PHODC, *Phoenix dactylifera*
A0A2C9VYJ6_MANES, *Manihot esculenta*
A0A2N9F976_FAGSY, *Fagus sylvatica*

From ANIMALS

A0A6P7J2Q5_9TELE, *Parambassis ranga*
A0A6P7J2Q5_9TELE, *Hucho hucho*
A0A8J0QX44_XENTR, *Xenopus tropicalis*
A0A5F4D2S5_CANLF, *Canis lupus familiaris*
A0A6P6D0R3_PTEVA, *Pteropus vampyrus*
F6QAQ1_MACMU, *Macaca mulatta*
Q07864|DPOE1_HUMAN, *Homo sapiens*
F6Z911_HORSE, *Equus caballus*

From YEASTS and HIGHER FUNGI

A0A420PL83_FUSOX, *Fusarium oxysporum*
A0A0G4NU82_PENCA, *Penicillium camemberti*
A0A167WJ50_PENCH, *Penicillium chrysogenum*
A0A401L0U3_ASPAW, *Aspergillus awamori*
A0A117E1M7_ASPNG, *Aspergillus niger*
C5M3R9_CANTT, *Candida tropicalis*
P21951|DPOE_YEAST, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*
Q6CUS7|DPOE_KLULA, *Kluyveromyces lactis*

F4HW04|DPOE1_ARATH, *Arabidopsis thaliana*
A0A8I6WFC8_HORVV, *Hordeum vulgare* subsp. *Vulgare*
A0A3B5XXC3_WHEAT, *Triticum aestivum*
A0A835B357_9POAL, *Digitaria exilis*
A0A368PL62_SETIT, *Setaria italica*
A0A6I9QIG1_ELAGV, *Elaeis guineensis* var. *tenera*
A0A9Q0FIP5_9ROSI, *Turnera subulata*
A0A7J7C034_TRIWF, *Tripterygium wilfordii*
A0A7N2KME6_QUELO, *Quercus lobata*

A0A8C7Q9V4_ONCMY, *Oncorhynchus mykiss*
A0A6P8SZE0_GYMAC, *Gymnodraco acuticeps*
A0A4X2K1K8_VOMUR, *Vombatus ursinus*
A0A7J7RQ84_RHIFE, *Rhinolophus ferrumequinum*
A0A2K6CI58_MACNE, *Macaca nemestrina*
G3RQP2_GORGO, *Gorilla gorilla*
A0A2I3S482_PANTR, *Pan troglodytes*
A0A5G2RB90_PIG, *Sus scrofa*

A0A1V6PGE7_PENDC, *Penicillium decumbens*
A0A1V6TET5_9EURO, *Penicillium flavigenum*
0A3A2Z9P9_9EURO, *Aspergillus sclerotialis*
A0A317VH96_ASPEC, *Aspergillus eucalypticola*
A0A1D8PTD0_CANAL, *Candida albicans*
Q6FNY7|DPOE_CANGA, *Candida glabrata*
A0A7H9HLU1_9SACH, *Torulaspora* sp.
Q752B8|DPOE_ASHGO, *Ashbya gossypii*

Figure 5 Mix and Match MSA of all the four eukaryotic ε DNA polymerase catalytic subunits**3.3. ZBM and their role(s) in eukaryotic replicative polymerases**

All the three eukaryotic replicative DNA pols (α, ε and δ) invariably possess the two completely conserved ZBMs at the CTDs of their catalytic subunits, and are known as CysA and CysB, suggesting an important role(s) in eukaryotic genome replication and regulation. In pol ε, the CysA (-Cx₂Cx_nCx_{2/4}C-) site is the regular ZBM, where a Zn²⁺ binds, but a [4Fe-

4S]²⁺ binds to the CysB (-C_{X2}C_{X11}C_XC-) site. The [4Fe-4S]²⁺ cluster is implicated in the redox signaling and regulation of the replication process in eukaryotes. In fact, the CysB motif is present in all the four yeast's B-family DNA pols which include the DNA mutagenesis enzyme pol ζ [22]. Interestingly, the ε pols contain an additional ZBM within the pol domain which is also shown to bind an [4Fe-4S]²⁺ cluster. Based on spectroscopic and other data, Jain *et al.* [23] suggested that the three highly conserved C residues (C⁶⁶⁵, C⁶⁶⁸, C⁶⁷⁷ and C⁷⁶³) in yeast ε pol's pol domain are involved in binding to [4Fe-4S] cluster (Fig. 3). This was based on their observation that the wild-type yeast pol ε's catalytic core was yellowish-brown, but a mutant in which all the three residues (C⁶⁶⁵, C⁶⁷⁷ and C⁷⁶³) were mutated, the mutant enzyme was colourless and its UV-Vis spectrum lacked the broad peak centered at 400 nm. Besides, they also found that this triple mutant was deficient only in the DNA pol activity, but not in the PR exonuclease activity, suggesting a link between the pol activity and the [4Fe-4S] cluster suggesting its possible involvement in the eukaryotic genome replication and regulation. Thus, the additional ZBM found exclusively in the ε pols suggests that ε pols are more sensitive to oxidative stress than the other two replicative pols [23]. Furthermore, Pinto *et al.* [24] have shown that the [4Fe-4S]²⁺ cluster of yeast DNA polymerase ε is redox active and can undergo DNA-mediated signaling. A double cysteine-to-serine mutant (C⁶⁶⁵→S and C⁶⁶⁸→S) of Pol2_{COREEXO}, which lacked the [4Fe-4S] cluster, showed no redox signal upon oxidation as the wildtype enzyme. Significantly, protein oxidation yielded a sharp decrease in polymerization, while rereduction restored the activity almost to the level of the untreated enzyme.

It is interesting to note that pol δ also possesses two ZBMs at its CTD, viz. CysA (-C_{X2}C_nC_{X2}C-) and CysB (-C_{X2}C_{X9}C_{X4}C-) [2]. Similar SDM experiments on pol δ by Netz *et al.* [22] have shown that the CysB motif was bound to [4Fe-4S] cluster and involved in the formation of the pol active complexes. For example, the loss of [4Fe-4S] cluster binding by Cys-ligand mutagenesis of pol δ, destabilized the CTD and abolished interactions between the polD1 and polD2 subunits. They found that the conversion of the C residues in the CysB site, viz. C¹⁰⁵⁶, C¹⁰⁵⁹, C¹⁰⁶⁹, C¹⁰⁷⁴ to A residues abolished the [4Fe-4S] binding [22]. Furthermore, a lethal double mutation C¹⁰⁵⁹→S/C¹⁰⁷⁴→S in CysB site of pol δ disrupted its binding to both polD1 and polD2. However, in marked contrast, a lethal double mutation in CysA site (C¹⁰¹²→S/C¹⁰²⁷→S) did not alter the subunit composition of the purified pol δ complex, and also did not affect the pol δ interactions with the subunits as evidenced from a yeast two hybrid analysis. However, the double mutation severely decreased PCNA-dependent replication processivity, suggesting the utmost importance of this metal centre for polymerase function. Thus, the CysA (PCNA-binding) and CysB (subunits interactions) motifs play distinct roles in the eukaryotic replicative pols.

4. Active site analyses of the DNA polymerase ε

The pol domain's active site amino acids of the pol ε from plant and animal sources is mostly arrived at from the data available on the yeast enzyme. The active sites of the yeast enzyme were analyzed by SDM, deletion mutagenesis and crystallographic studies [16, 19, 25, 26]. Pavlov *et al.* [16] found that in the yeast enzyme, the Y⁸³¹→A replacement by SDM reduces replication fidelity and its participation in chromosomal replication suggesting its involvement in the pol active site. Interestingly, the present study shows that the Y⁸³¹ (highlighted in dark blue in Table 1) is in the proposed and highly conserved template-binding -Y⁸³¹G- pair of the yeast pol ε.

Kesti *et al.* [20] found that a yeast strain with an N-terminal deletion, which deletes the pol domain of the pol ε (*pol2*) gene, but retaining the C-terminal region intact, grew slowly and was viable. Their in-frame deletion experiment lacked the sequence, encoding amino acids 176–1134 of the 2222-amino-acid pol ε protein containing all of the conserved motifs associated with the DNA pol and PR exonuclease functions. They found that such a large N-terminal deletion of the yeast enzyme consisting of all the known pol and PR exonuclease domains was dispensable for DNA replication, repair, and cell viability. Furthermore, such deletion of the PR and pol catalytic domains of pol ε from the NTD was not lethal and did not block chromosomal DNA replication [20]. Besides, they found that the C-terminal portion of the enzyme was both necessary and sufficient for viability and hence, suggested that another polymerase could possibly substitute for the polymerization function of pol ε in their N-terminal deletion mutant. Interestingly, the present study has shown that the presence of one more putative pol active site in the CTD (highlighted in yellow) could have possibly compensated for the pol function in their N-terminal deletion mutants. In another deletion analysis, Ohya *et al.* [27] found a pol ε deletion mutant of yeast was temperature-sensitive, exhibited severe defects in chromosomal DNA replication at the permissive temperature, and underwent premature senescence, suggesting the role of PR function in such deletion mutants as the CTD does not possess a functional PR active site in the yeast pol ε (Table 1).

The crystal structure of yeast DNA pol ε catalytic subunit has been solved by Jain *et al.* [25]. The yeast enzyme adopts the universal 'right-hand' DNA pol fold with an active site formed by a 'palm' (holding the catalytic residues for dNTP addition), a 'thumb' (that binds the template-primer duplex) and 'fingers' (interacting with incoming nucleotides) and an exonuclease domain. The enzyme's palm subdomain was found to be larger and more elaborate than that is found in pols α and δ. In the pol ε, the pol and exo active sites are separated by ~41 Å in a direction roughly perpendicular to the

DNA axis. Pol ϵ 's fidelity to a nascent Watson-Crick base-pairing was determined primarily by residues V⁸²⁵, N⁸²⁸, S⁸²⁹, Y⁸³¹ and G⁸³² from the fingers' domain (all the five amino acids are in the proposed catalytic core of the enzyme) and by Y⁶⁴⁵ from the palm domain. As discussed elsewhere, the Y⁸³¹→A replacement in pol ϵ reduced replication fidelity and its participation in chromosomal replication, but without eliminating an additional function that is essential for viability [25]. It is interesting to note that the same invariant Y⁸³¹G⁸³² pair is proposed here as the template-binding pair by sequence similarity and is in close agreement with other DdDps and DdRps. The pol active site is characterized by the catalytic metal-binding residues, D⁶⁴⁰ and D⁸⁷⁷. Both (-HVD⁶⁴⁰- and -DTD⁸⁷⁷-) are found to be completely conserved in the eukaryotic ϵ pols. The PR exonucleases active site amino acids are further confirmed by SDM and X-ray crystallographic data. When the D²⁹⁰ and E²⁹² of the first triad in the PR exonuclease were mutated to A (highlighted in dark blue in Table 1), the exonuclease activity was abolished, confirming their direct involvement in PR function [15]. The x-ray crystallographic data further confirmed that the PR exo domain was located on the opposite side of the DNA of the thumb domain and contained the catalytic residues (D²⁹⁰, E²⁹² and D⁴⁷⁷ and D²⁷⁵, E²⁷⁷ (numberings are based on the yeast and human enzymes, respectively) for PR activity [25]. A catalytic metal ion was found to be coordinated by D²⁹⁰ (D²⁷⁵ in human enzyme) (Fig. 5A). These active site amino acids are in complete agreement with the present MSA analysis (highlighted in light blue).

Table 1 shows a comparative account of the active site amino acids in the PR exonuclease and pol domains of the eukaryotic DNA pol ϵ from different sources from yeasts to humans. The PR exonuclease and pol active sites are almost identical in all eukaryotes from lower (yeasts and higher fungi) to higher (plants and animals) except for a small difference where the plant and animal enzymes use a -KC- pair at the proton abstraction site and the yeast and higher fungal enzymes use a -KV- pair without altering the invariant K in all. The putative second pol active site amino acids are also identified in the CTD. However, the second PR exonuclease active site in the CTD is not complete in all ϵ pols (Table 1).

Table 1 Proposed active site amino acids of PR exonuclease and pol domains of eukaryotic ϵ pols

	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	<i>A. thaliana</i>	<i>Homo sapiens</i>
PR Exo-1 (NTD)	D ²⁹² E ²⁹² F ³⁸³ D ⁴⁷⁷	D ²⁴⁹ E ³⁴⁰ F ⁴³¹ D ⁴³⁵	D ²⁷⁵ E ²⁷⁷ F ³⁶⁷ D ³⁶⁸ E ⁴⁵⁸ S ⁴⁵⁹ D ⁴⁶²
Pol-1(NTD)	⁸¹⁶ YDSL Q LAH K VILNSF Y ⁸³⁴ G ⁸³²	⁷⁷⁴ YDSL Q LAH K CILNSF Y ⁷⁹² G ⁷⁹²	⁸⁰¹ YDSL Q LAH K CILNSF Y ⁸¹⁹ G ⁸¹⁹
PR Exo-2 (CTD)	D ¹²¹⁶ E ¹²¹⁶ ? ? ?	D ¹¹⁸⁰ E ¹¹⁸⁰ ? ? ?	D ¹⁴²⁴ E ¹⁴²⁴ L ¹⁵¹⁶ D ¹⁵¹⁶ Y ¹⁶³⁶ D ¹⁶⁴⁰
Pol-2 (CTD)	¹⁸³⁷ H N LT K K ALLQLVNEFSAL ¹³ G S-	¹⁷⁸⁹ H K VM K K VFALLTLRRL ¹³ G A-	¹⁸⁴² H N MM K K LFLQLIAEFKRL ¹³ G S-

Adapted from Palanivelu [8]; Active site amino acids in dark blue are confirmed by SDM analysis; Mutations in pol ϵ PR exo active site region (highlighted in dark blue) lead to several types of cancers, e.g., D²⁷⁵ leads to endometrial, breast, glioblastoma, colorectal, lung cancers; F³⁶⁷ leads to endometrial, colon cancers; S⁴⁵⁹ leads to colon, endometrial, glioblastoma, duodenal cancers.

The 3'→5' PR exonucleolytic activity is intrinsic to the replicative DNA pols ϵ and δ and is essential for the faithful replication of the genomic DNA. Figs. 6A, B and C show the proposed active site amino acids at the PR exonuclease active sites of yeast, plant and human ϵ pols, respectively, which is based on the crystallographic, SDM and MSA data.

Figures 6A, B and C. Proposed amino acids at the PR exonuclease active sites of DNA pols ϵ of *S. cerevisiae* (A), *A. thaliana* (B) and humans (C)

The proposed two-metal ion in the active site in the PR exonucleases is based on Beese and Steitz's observation of similar active site structure in the 3'→5' PR exonuclease active site in *E. coli* pol I [28] and is also further confirmed from a large number DdRps [6].

5. Conclusions

Understanding the functions of the replicative pols, viz. α , ϵ and δ , which make the replisome complex, is a prerequisite for understanding the mechanism of genome replication and maintenance of genome integrity in eukaryotes. The present study unravels striking similarities of one of the main replicative pols ϵ from lower to higher eukaryotes at the molecular level. The MSA analysis has shown that the ϵ pols in all eukaryotes contain the same template-binding pairs, catalytic and nucleotide selection amino acids and also the same catalytic metal-binding motifs. Furthermore, the two completely conserved ZBMs in the CTDs of all the three replicative pols suggest their essential roles in genome replication and regulation. A unique [4Fe-4S]²⁺ cluster-binding motif in the ϵ pol domain is implicated in the redox signaling and the regulation of the replication process in eukaryotes as this enzyme links the DNA replication machinery to S-phase checkpoint-control in eukaryotes. Moreover, the PR exonuclease active site amino acids are identical in all eukaryotic enzymes and belong to the DEDD(Y) superfamily of PR exonucleases. These findings establish that the pol, PR exonuclease and CTD domains of the ϵ pols and their roles in genome replication, maintenance of genome integrity and regulation are highly conserved across all eukaryotes, from yeasts to higher animals. The highly conserved pol, PR exonuclease and CTD domains strongly suggest a possible common evolutionary origin of the ϵ pols in eukaryotes.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author has declared that no competing interests exist.

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